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Building Royally: Expressions of Magnificence in the Palaces of Henry VII (1485–1509)

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Abstract

The early Tudor period (1485–1558) witnessed the establishment of the Tudor dynasty and a political, social, and cultural revolution. It was an age of architectural developments as medieval traditions were gradually abandoned and numerous royal palaces and their gardens were constructed or reconstructed corresponding to new trends, the current fashion, and the personal taste of the reigning monarch. Royal palaces and their adjoining gardens served as representations of the power and wealth of the dynasty by conveying magnificence. The paper discusses early Tudor textual records and the ways these documents give evidence of the magnificence of royal residences, together with presenting a possible typology based on the way of expression for the categorisation of the historical textual records.

Keywords: early modern textual records, Tudor architecture, royal palaces, magnificence and power

1 The Newly Established Dynasty

The Tudor period began with Henry VII (1485–1509) seizing the crown in the Battle of Bosworth Field in 1485 and lasted for almost 120 years. During the successive reigns of Henry VIII (1509–1547), Edward VI (1547–1553), Mary I (1553–1558), and Elizabeth I (1558–1603), England was subject to major political and religious changes. In addition to these developments, the architectural achievements of the period are also remarkable, as during the age of the Renaissance in England, numerous iconic buildings were constructed or reconstructed. The construction of the greatest Tudor palaces all took place during the early Tudor period, and the extensive volume of architectural undertakings was partly a result of the lavish spending of Henry VIII. Elizabeth I, however, placed a greater emphasis on her progresses than on her building activity, and as Osborne summarises, the Queen’s “power was based on the love of her subjects” (1989: 15) and “Elizabeth I believed [...] that rapport with her people was vital to her sovereignty and to the prosperity of her kingdom” (1989: 15).

With the accession of Henry VII, a new era of internal peace and prosperity was introduced to England; moreover, the great intellectual movement called “the English Renaissance” began during this period. As a monarch, Henry VII sought to legitimise his right to the throne¹ and solidify the Tudors as the ruling dynasty of England. First of all, when Henry Tudor arrived in London after his victory in the Battle of Bosworth Field, he appeared before his first Parliament to affirm that “the crown had come to him both by hereditary succession and by the true judgement of God given in battle” (Meagher 1968: 45). Secondly, he fulfilled his previous promise made to the Yorkists and married Elizabeth of York, and this marriage did not only unite the rivalling Lancaster and York families but helped to assure Tudor succession with the birth of Arthur in 1486 (Guy 1988: 57). Even though Henry VII had taken precautions in order to solidify his power, he had to face several revolts up until 1499, the most serious one – with dynastic intentions – being that of Perkin Warbeck (Guy 1988: 57). However, he proved to be successful eventually, as he managed to establish his dynasty and

revive the efficiency of kingship. He had outstanding achievements in the field of finance, which were made possible by the great efforts that he had put into his administration, where he established complete personal authority (Kar 1980: 852).

Henry VII can be regarded as a pioneer when it comes to the art and practice of royal power. By the time he came to the throne, the English monarchy had been half a century old, and as a consequence, the king inherited an already well-developed system of government and royal residences that included medieval fortified castles of the countryside (such as Kenilworth Castle) and more fashionable London residences (such as Greenwich). He began to effectively use the power of architecture as a means of conveying his wealth and authority as the monarch of England. It was during his reign that medieval architectural traditions were gradually abandoned, and new, fashionable architectural trends were adopted. This paper discusses in detail two residences of Henry VII (Baynard's Castle and Richmond Palace) in order to illustrate how royal power was perceived through architectural achievements during the early Tudor period, and by presenting the ways perceptions took effect, it intends to present a typological classification of textual historical records. The paper proposes the following three categories based on the manner of reference a textual record employs to present the concept of magnificence: first, the record refers to the financial costs of the construction, second, the record refers to the physical features of the building that convey magnificence, and third, the record refers to the personal impressions concerning magnificence. The study presents examples of historical records that give account of Baynard's Castle and Richmond Palace as case studies without claiming to be exhaustive.

2 Stately Magnificence

The use of magnificence and the practice of the art of power were not Tudor inventions; according to Anglo, it was fundamentally a classical, Aristotelian principle that was reinforced several times during the successive eras (1992: 6). Aristotle, in his *Nicomachean Ethics*, differentiates between liberality and prodigality² based on the modes of using one's wealth. Rooted in the idea of liberality and prodigality, the philosopher mentions and discusses the notion of magnificence, which according to him, appears to be a virtue concerned with wealth (1956: 205). Aristotle compares magnificence to liberality, thus providing a definition of the term: "it does not, however, like Liberality, extend to all actions dealing with wealth, but only refers to the spending of wealth; and in this sphere it surpasses Liberality in point of magnitude, for, as its name itself implies, it consists in suitable expenditure on a great scale" (1956: 205); he further clarifies the definition by adding that "the term magnificence denotes someone who spends suitably on great objects" (1956: 205) and that "the magnificent man is an artist in expenditure: he can discern what is suitable, and spend great sums with good taste" (1956: 207). Finally, it is established that "a poor man cannot be magnificent, since he has not the means to make a great outlay suitably" (1956: 209).

While Aristotle discusses magnificence as a universal virtue of the ordinary man, John Fortescue³ associates the concept with rules and mentions magnificence as one of the "extraordinary charges of a king" in his *The Governance of England* (c. 1470). Skeel emphasises that Fortescue had a significant impact on the early Tudor period and on various practices of Henry VII. The King favoured constitutional forms and made efforts to reduce the power of the nobles. However, above all, during his reign he was perceived by foreign observers as an especially wealthy king; as a proof, Skeel cites impressions from the *Milanese*

Calendar where the King is viewed as “very powerful in money” and someone who “has a very great treasure which increases daily” (1916: 84). According to Fortescue, it is needed that the king has great treasures, as he might make new buildings for his pleasure and for magnificence (1885: 125). Not only will the king dress richly, but he will also care for the rich decoration and ornaments for his royal estate (1885: 125). Aristotle’s basic condition, that a man needs to be wealthy in order to be magnificent, is supported in Fortescue’s *The Governance of England*.

The connection between architecture and magnificence might be established on several terms. Vitruvius’ classical work, *Ten Books on Architecture* draws attention to the importance of symmetry and harmony – principles in connection with the overall beauty of a building that need to be carefully observed by the architect and both of which contribute to the perception of magnificence (1914: 72). A less practical and more theoretical and idealistic approach is formulated by Moore, who claims that “buildings are not purely functional [...] there is an intangible something about them that has to do with emotion” (2013: 15) and that “architecture is intimate with power [...] it requires authority, money, and ownership” (2013: 145).

3 The Building Activity of Henry VII

Architectural styles and practices are subject to constant change and are exposed to social and economic changes of the current era. By the beginning of the early modern era, aristocratic houses started to transform and take on a new look. This transformation could be explained by a change in their ways of life. Due to the decrease of household mobility⁴, early modern households spent much longer periods in one place (Thurley 2014: 318). Therefore, a need for more spacious chambers and more convenient accommodations appeared.

Henry VII contributed on several occasions to many of the existing palaces of the realm, as the financial resources needed to do so were already at his disposal. The *Letters and Papers of Henry VIII* Vol. XI, No. 1244. is not a strictly contemporary record, however, it gives a valuable account of how Henry VII’s financial achievements, wealth, and power were perceived a few decades after his death (in 1536). The account starts with a reference to the wealth of Henry VIII’s father: “If the King will be rich, let him follow the trade of his father, the second Solomon, who enhanced his riches by wisdom and mercy” (qtd. in Pollard 1914: 5). The extract also gives evidence of the phenomena that Henry VII was clever with money. It explains how the king appointed chaplains of his favour for vacant positions, thus increasing his riches. Also, the fact that the king appreciated overseas merchants who brought in “buloyn” which intends to refer to the modern English word “bullion” (which is applied to gold or silver in the form of bars). These measures all contributed to the riches of the realm, while Henry VII was both loved and feared by contemporaries, and the “reyme so inrychde and hymselfe also that yt was spokyn to the worldes end that in thys reyme was the goldyn hyll” (qtd. in Pollard 1914: 5).

Henry VII constructed a new privy chamber block, to be exact, a privy tower at Windsor Castle between 1489 and 1501 (Thurley 2019: 29). Thurley emphasised the relevance of towers as architectural features from the Saxon times. It was no coincidence that Henry VII himself renovated only parts of royal residences, these parts being towers. It was expensive to build, but they were dominant when looked at as they represented might and power together with providing defence, and at the same time, they were pleasant places to live as they offered extensive views. These towers stood more independently at the beginning of the 15th century;

however, by the end of the century they were more integrated with the principal lodgings of the house (2014: 321). Besides Windsor Castle, Greenwich Palace also became a preferred residence with the accession of Henry VII, where he often spent Christmas (Rait 1911: 52).

4 Palaces with Symbolical Connotations

Baynard's Castle was of symbolic significance for Henry VII, as this house had been granted to his father, Edmund Tudor, in March 1453 (Thurley 2019: 12). Thurley finds the significance of the grant in the fact that "it can be said to have marked the founding of the Tudor dynasty, for that year Henry VI had ennobled his two half-brothers, Jasper as Earl of Pembroke and Edmund as Earl of Richmond..." (2019: 12). Later, however, the residence became the main Yorkist residence in London when it was confiscated from Edmund Tudor and was given to Richard, Duke of York (Thurley 2019: 12).

Baynard's Castle is one striking example of abandoning medieval architectural practices during the early Tudor period. Baynard's was originally a fortress-like castle; a detailed history of the building is presented in *A Survey of London Written in the Year 1598* by John Stow⁵ which demonstrates in what way medieval fortresses were often remodelled into magnificent royal residences during the early modern period. Stow clarifies the origin of the castle by claiming that it was built by a nobleman called Baynard who arrived in England as a companion of William the Conqueror (1066–1087), and gives a brief description of the characteristic of the original building by mentioning "two most strong castles [...] are built with walls and rampires [...] banking on the river Thames" (2005: 71). Based on the description, one could imagine a fortress on the riverbank with high stone walls and miniature windows. Stow's *Survey* also gives account of the remodelling of the castle in the following way: "Henry VII., about the year 1501, and the 16th of his reign, repaired, or rather new built this house, not embattled, or so strongly fortified castle like, but far more beautiful and commodious for the entertainment of any prince or great estate" (2005: 76). It was Henry VII's apparent intention to refurbish the residence that bore a symbolic meaning to his dynasty into a more attractive and comfortable one and display it to distinguished guests and ambassadors – the usage of a magnificently renovated building as a symbol of royal power is evident. However, as the King was uncertain due to his questionable legitimacy to the throne, he has not completely disposed of towers and bastions that served the defence of the building. The modernisation of Baynard's Castle is recorded by an early modern sketch of Anthonis van den Wyngaerde⁶ and further explained by Thurley: "a substantially new building [...] was of brick and showed to the river a façade animated by a series of great bay windows [...] at either end were massive towers with machicolations⁷ and turrets, making the house look, from the river, like an exotic little castle" (2019: 37). Based on Thurley's description, Baynard's still resembled more of a castle (it is also justified by features such as machicolations), nonetheless, gradually leaving behind the medieval traditions, as it is now perceived as "exotic". As this paper concerns contemporary textual records and the perception of royal magnificence in those records, therefore early modern visual records now should be mentioned because they are valuable sources for confirming descriptions and serve as a good basis for comparison. Stow's account of Baynard's Castle echoes the physical properties of the residence; therefore, it could be said that it is an objective description, free of emotionally charged expressions, which also saves the details of the costs of the construction.

Considering Henry VII's aspirations to convey royal power and wealth through buildings in order to solidify his ruling dynasty, another palace should be discussed, namely Sheen or as later known, Richmond Palace. Besides Baynard's Castle, Richmond Palace also came to signify Henry VII's ancestry and bore a symbolic meaning. Thurley highlights the fact that "he was fiercely proud of his own patrimony, in particular his title, Richmond, which had been given to his father, Edmund Tudor, by Henry VI and which, on his birth, Henry had inherited" (2019: 40).

*Hall's Chronicle*⁸ records the history of Richmond Palace in the following way: "Also in this yere was burned a place of the kynges called the maner of Shene Situate, & liynge nygh the Thamys side, which he after buylded agayne sumptuously & costly, and chaunged the name of Shene, and called it Rychemond, because hys father and he were erles of Richemonde" (1809: 491).

This record gives account of the fact that Sheen was not simply rebuilt but was endowed a new symbolic role as the family seat of the Tudors, signifying both the dynasty's wealth and power and ancestry. Edwards Hall includes the fact that this renovation work was a costly matter; thus, implying the obvious; in order to convey magnificence through buildings, the king needed to be wealthy – as mentioned earlier, Henry VII was clever with money, and as a result, he managed to financially stabilise his country after the conflicts of the Wars of the Roses. By using the expression "sumptuously", Hall indicates that the palace was rebuilt in a way that is both impressive and seems expensive.

Kingsford's *Chronicles of London*⁹ first mentions Sheen in connection with Edward III (1327–1377), who built himself this medieval residence and who also died at Sheen (Kingsford 1905: 15). Moreover, it records the unfortunate incident from 1497, the fire at Sheen, and gives a detailed account of the fact that in 1497 the King spent Christmas at his manor of Sheen, and that during the Christmas wake around nine o'clock a great fire began within the king's lodgings; during the fire the great part of the old building was burnt (Kingsford 1905: 222). The Chronicle also reports that a great sum of money was necessary for the rebuilding of the palace; accordingly, this record discusses the renovation in terms of financial costs, besides also mentioning the renaming of the palace:

In this yere the king, after he had ffynysshed a greate parte of the buyldyng of his Manoir of Shene, which as before is said was consumed by ffire [...] And also that the Reedifyng of the said Manoir had cost, and after shuld cost or it were pursued, grete and notable sumes of money, where before that season it was ones called or named Shene, ffrom this tyme forward it was commauned by the kyng that it shuld be called or named Rich mount. (Kingsford 1905: 233)

*The Receyt of the Ladie Kateryne*¹⁰ is another significant manuscript regarding Tudor palaces and Renaissance festivities. Even though it is an elaborate description of the wedding of Henry VII's son, Arthur (1486–1502) to Katherine of Aragon (1485–1536), it provides valuable mentions of Richmond Palace as well. As for the historical facts in connection with the marriage, it was Henry VII's initial intention to complete renovation works at Richmond Palace for this major diplomatic event. Kipling highlights the significance of *The Receyt of the Ladie Kateryne* by stating that it "provides the best single source of information about the Tudor festival it describes" (Kipling 1990: xi), furthermore the prestige of the event for Henry VII as the "the successful culmination of his dynastic and political ambitions" (Kipling 1990: xiii).

The 9th chapter of Book IV gives an account "of the huntyng in the Kinges parke and of the description of the Place of Rychemont". It praises "the pleasaunt Place of Richemond

[...] That is to sey, this erthly and secunde paradise of oure region of England” (Kipling 1990: 71). Then the text continues with a detailed description of the courtyard, the galleries, the great hall, the chapel and other spaces within the palace. The author mentions aspects of convenience several times, which further supports the formerly mentioned claim, that the medieval architectural traditions were progressively abandoned, and new factors became significant, such as convenience and pomp. The author refers to the palace as a building “of great comodities, pleasures, and excellent goodlynes” and also mentions that “uppon ich side of this goodly courte there are galeres with many wyndowes full lightsume and commodious” (Kipling 1990: 71). This record builds on the subjective perceptions of the author, who is undoubtedly impressed by the atmosphere of the palace.

Henry VII considered Richmond his family seat, his most important residence of all; this is supported by the fact that the king died at Richmond Palace. The occurrence is recorded by Kingsford’s *Chronicles of London* as well as the *Chronicles of the Grey Friars of London*¹¹; “Thys yere the xxii day of Aprill dyde kyng Henry the VIIth at Richmonde, and browth to London [...] and the nexte day to Westmynster nobylly and there buryd” (Nichols 1852: 29).

If one thinks about it, the name of the palace, Richmond can also be interpreted as a “rich mount” (as mentioned earlier by quoting the *Letters and Papers of Henry VIII*, in which there was a reference to a golden hill in the realm of Henry VII). Rawlinson further emphasises this “pun” by stating that Henry VII’s intention was both to identify this renovated palace with his ancestral dynasty and praise it as a “rich mount” (2016: 95). This idea and image are further confirmed by the painting *The Family of Henry VII with St George and the Dragon* (c. 1503–9), which represents Richmond Palace in a more fantastical and allegorical environment. In the painting, the palace can be observed high on the top of a mountain, thus it can be described as a “rich mount.” These are all subjective perceptions of the expression of magnificence in a building.

5 Conclusion

Rawlinson points out that early modern contemporaries did perceive architecture as an expression of power and wealth and supports his claim by quoting John Skelton’s verses in Colin Clout (1521–22) (2016: 101)

Buyldyng royally
 Theyr mancyons curiously,
 With turrets and with toures,
 With halles and with boures,
 Stretchynge to the starres,
 With glasse wyndowes and barres ;
 Hangynge aboute the walles
 Clothes of golde and palles

(Skelton 1983: 270-71)

The perception of magnificence and wealth, however, does not always have a positive connotation. Skelton’s poem, *Colin Clout* is unquestionably a satire, and according to Burrow, it has a single target as it is addressed to the rulers of the Church, the bishops, and especially Cardinal Wolsey¹², archbishop of York (2016: 469). It is interesting to see that some were not

impressed by the magnificence and splendour, however, the exact opposite happened, some felt a strong disgust towards the wealthy individual. This aversion is conveyed in Skelton's *Colin Clout*, when he refers to prelates as haughty, i.e., arrogantly superior. Skelton, similarly to other contemporaries, perceives wealth and power conveyed by magnificent buildings, however, the impressions and feelings attached to this perception are quite different.

Cardinal Wolsey's grandiose spending was merely a forerunner to that of Henry VII's son and successor, Henry VIII. During his reign, a large-scale change occurred in terms of royal constructions, as the new monarch surpassed all previous rulers in this respect; even his father, as he used buildings and the power of royal splendour in his dynastic rivalry with his contemporary, Francis I of France (1515–1547) and in order to demonstrate his power to continental Europe as well. Henry VIII's building activity is more widely documented than that of Henry VII, which justifies the topic's exclusion from the present study.

As a conclusion, based on the examples presented in the paper, Henry VII was efficient in using his buildings to convey his royal power, wealth, and magnificence – which all contributed to the eventual consolidation of the Tudor dynasty. Early modern textual records present the evident perception of magnificence conveyed by palaces by referring to the physical features (*Survey of London* by John Stow), the cost of the construction (*Hall's Chronicle* or *Chronicles of London*), or personal impressions (*The Receyt of the Ladie Kateryne*).

Notes

1. Henry Tudor's claim to the English throne was dubious; therefore, at the beginning of his reign, the security and stability of the Tudor rule were a crucial concern for him. His father, Edmund Tudor, earl of Richmond, was half-brother to Henry VI (1422–1461 and 1470–1471) through his mother, Catherine of Valois. His mother, Margaret Beaufort, was the great-granddaughter of King Edward III's son, John of Gaunt, who legitimised the Beaufort descendants by an Act of Parliament; however, the Act excluded them from succession to the throne (Gunn 2016: 4).
2. Liberality and prodigality are important terms to discuss if one attempts to gain understanding of the notion of magnificence. Liberality is a virtue, a virtue of giving and getting wealth, but especially giving and refraining from taking more than it is due (Aristotle 1956: 189). Prodigality is a mode of excess and of deficiency; prodigality exceeds in giving and is deficient in getting (Aristotle 1956: 197).
3. Sir John Fortescue served as a chief councillor to Henry VI (1422–1461 and 1470–1471), tutor to Prince Edward, and propagandist for the Lancastrian family during the Wars of the Roses (Gill 1971: 333). It was between 1471 and 1476 that Fortescue wrote his constitutional treatise, *The Governance of England*. According to Skeel, as it was the author's last work, it embodies the observations of a lifetime (1916: 82). The influence of Fortescue's writings can be proved by the fact that under the Tudors many of his suggestions were actually in practice (Skeel 1916: 83).
4. This change in lifestyle might be due to the fact that a great part of land was tenanted. Strong points out that landownership has always represented economic wealth, political power, or social status, and with the emergence of cartography, land was looked at in terms of ownership; in summary, civic virtue depended on landownership (2001: 99).
5. John Stow (1525–1605) was one of the most renowned Renaissance historians, chroniclers, and antiquarians of the Elizabethan Age. His greatest work, *A Survey of London* is a type of "chorographic" (i.e., the systematic description and mapping of specific regions or areas) historical narration, where the organising model is the physical layout of London (Hall 1991: 1). One can observe that the narrative is organised both along a topographic and chronological line. The description of Baynard's Castle is reported according to the progression of time, highlighting the successive proprietors of the building.

6. Anthonis van den Wyngaerde was one of the most productive topographical artists of the Renaissance Period, as between 1544 and 1570 he created numerous views in different locations in the Netherlands, France, Spain, Italy, and also in England. As reported by Haverkamp-Begemann the topographer himself wrote that “among all joys that the delightful and ingenious art of painting has to offer, there is not one that I hold in higher esteem than the representation of sites” (1969: 357). Wyngaerde’s illustrations contribute to a better understanding of the architectural practices of early modern England and the layout of palaces and gardens.
7. According to the *Cambridge Dictionary*, machicolation is “a series of holes in a floor that projects (=sticks out over the edge) around the top of a castle, through which the people inside can drop or throw objects with the intention of causing injury or damage” (“Machicolation”).
8. The original title of Edward Hall’s chronicle is *Union of the Two Noble and Illustre Families of Lancaster and York* and was first published in the middle of the 16th century, in 1548. According to Smith, Hall is not a first-hand author for the reigns from Henry IV to the death of Henry VIII – one may believe that he was not an original writer of history, but rather a collector of the chronicles of others (1918: 254).
9. *Chronicles of London* is an edition by Charles Lethbridge Kingsford, who made a compilation of three original mid-fifteenth-century manuscript copies as indicated by the 1905 editions Contents page. His introduction to the editions discusses in detail the authorship, contents, and dates of the manuscripts.
10. According to Kipling, the editor of the account, the author of the original manuscript was almost certainly a member of the King’s household – he bases his statement on the fact that the narrator reports from the point of view of an attendant at court; eyewitness experiences from a position very close to the King (1990: xliv).
11. The *Chronicles of the Grey Friars of London* is a valuable textual historical record from the Tudor period and was edited by John Gough Nichols in the middle of the 19th century. It documents events starting from the reign of Richard I (1189–1199); referring to him as “Kynge Rychard the Furst surnamed Cure de Lyon” (1852: 1) highlighting his informal title of Richard the Lionheart.
12. Thomas Wolsey (1475–1530) was a cardinal and statesman who dominated the government of England under Henry VIII, between 1515 and 1529. He amassed great wealth and power and with his roles in the church he acquired estates as well, such as York Place. He took over Hampton Court, a medieval manor, situated outside of London on the north bank of the River Thames and between 1515 and 1521 he transformed it into a remarkable palace and one of England’s most significant great houses of the early Tudor age (Foyle 2002: 128).

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Celtic Tiger Ireland, Irish Cinema and Darragh Byrne's *Parked* (2010)

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Abstract

Daragh Byrne's first feature-length film is about a man's reintegration into mainstream Irish society following his return from England. Parked (2010) reflects on various social and economic issues that have arisen during the Celtic Tiger period and the first year of the Global Recession. Specifically, the article reviews how the issues of homelessness, unemployment, substance abuse, and migration are addressed in the film. In order to contextualise the movie, the article provides a wide-ranging, yet thorough analysis of Ireland's social, economic, and political circumstances at the turn of the millennium, as well as a short, but relevant history of the "returning Irishman" topos in cinematic representations of Ireland during the twentieth century.

Keywords: Ireland, Celtic Tiger, Irish cinema, social criticism

1 Ireland during the Celtic Tiger Period

Darragh Byrne's multi-award-winning film, *Parked*, was filmed in three weeks, which meant an intense work schedule for those in the leading parts, Colm Meaney, Colin Morgan, and Milka Aloth. The main setting chosen was a long-abandoned car park in Ireland's capital city, located "on the edge of an area of reclaimed land overlooking Dublin Bay" (*CultBox* 2012). Director Byrne described this place as one "strangely trapped in its own world," "cut off from the busy modern ebb and flow of the nearby city" (*CultBox* 2012). According to Byrne, the location was "a perfect mirror to the central characters dilemma:" they were "stuck in a 'no mans land' [*sic!*] of uncertainty" and were "unable to move back or forward until their shared experience creates the impetus for change" (*CultBox* 2012). This shared experience starts with Fred and Cathal's meeting in the car park, where Fred's car is parked facing the Irish Sea. Their story develops from here until its bittersweet end that involves Fred's reintegration into Irish society after many long years living in England.

The Ireland into which Fred tries to settle back has experienced prosperous years during the Celtic Tiger period, and one that is now facing economic and social problems brought about by the Global Financial Crisis (GFC). Ruth Barton draws attention to the fact that films normally take years to develop (2014: 218); hence, the first films of the recession would have been developed during the last prosperous years of the Celtic Tiger. Taking this into consideration, the present analysis of *Parked* considers the film as a product of the last "boom years" and the first "bust years," using Naomi Klein's terms in *The Shock Doctrine* (2007). During the Celtic Tiger, the Irish economy enjoyed unprecedented levels of growth, with high levels of foreign investment and low levels of unemployment. In *The Celtic Tiger: Ireland's Economic Miracle*, Paul Sweeney wrote that "[o]n every data, Ireland consistently outperformed its partners in the EU" and was considered "one of the unsung success stories" (1998: 5). Edward Shinnick remarks in his economic review of the period, "The rise & fall of the Irish Celtic Tiger: why fiscal policy matters," that Irish living standards had increased dramatically, as had the housing bubble, and the Irish government's tax revenues (2013: 58). Foreign direct investment (FDI) increased exponentially during the millennium years (20% of

GDP in 2000), pouring in mostly from the United States of America and the European Union (Shinnick 2013: 57). Irish banks were operating within a global banking system that was thought to be unshakable prior to 2008 and they were offering a “free flow of cheap credits” to both companies and individuals due to the country’s consistently favourable inflation figures and increasingly positive economic output (Shinnick 2013: 57).

Some historians, economists, and social commentators were concerned about the nature and the speed of Ireland’s economic growth even back then. Many found the rate of economic growth and the ways in which the development was generated unsustainable. These commentators were proven right when, following the collapse of the US banking system in 2008, the Irish banking sector was not able to survive without substantial government intervention. Shinnick notes that the Irish government took out an incredible loan to save the Irish banking sector: “€67.5bn in bailout funds from the IMF/EU/ECB were required for the banking and fiscal crises” (2013: 61). “Three decades of financialisation, Europeanisation and worldwide experiments in economic governance” came to an end, writes Seán Ó Riain in *The Rise and Fall of Ireland’s Celtic Tiger: Liberalism, Boom and Bust*, when “Ireland entered the bailout programme in November 2010” (2014: 3 and 2). Following the “boom years,” there was “general disillusionment with the Celtic Tiger,” as Eamon Maher and Eugene O’Brien write in *From Prosperity to Austerity: A Socio-cultural Critique of the Celtic Tiger and its Aftermath* (2014: 7). As a direct consequence of agreeing to the bailout package of the “Troika,” the Irish government had to increase taxes and drastically cut its expenditures. This was happening in a country where unemployment figures were on the rise and economic production was seriously on the decrease (Maher and O’Brien 2014: 4). Maher and O’Brien note that, interestingly, during the Celtic Tiger period, Irish novelists seemed to have avoided exposing certain societal and economic problems for fear of losing funding (2014: 6). Therefore, it is even more interesting that director Byrne decided to engage with some of the pressing social issues of the times: homelessness, unemployment, substance abuse and migration.

2 Irish Cinema during the Celtic Tiger Period

Debbie Ging makes a compelling case for cinema being a form of social criticism. In “Screening the Green: Cinema under the Celtic Tiger,” she traces the trait of social-sensitivity back to the 1970s and early 1980s. Ging argues that a main characteristic of First Wave Irish Cinema was an interest in marginalised characters, who lived on the outskirts of mainstream society (2002: 178–179). Joe Comerford’s documentarist-style films, for instance, portrayed characters who were experiencing social exclusion, as witnessed in *Withdrawal* (1973), *Down the Corner* (1978), and *Traveller* (1982) (2002: 180). Second Wave Cinema (i.e., cinema after 1987) “moved steadily toward easy, globally-digestible narratives” but characters and storylines became “increasingly stereotypical and bland,” argues Ging (2002: 185). Gerard Stembridge’s romantic comedy, *About Adam* (2001), for example, steered clear of the socio-realism of documentarist cinema. This film is rich in images of wealthy, modern life: the title character is owner of a light-blue Jaguar, and lives in a busy, modern Dublin. Hugh Linehan notes that Second Wave Cinema presented a new image of Ireland as a “modern, dynamic society ideal for investment by multinational conglomerates” (1999: 46). There were economic factors behind the change of outlook that were consequences of the Irish government’s Programme for National Recovery, introduced in 1987. This programme stabilized the

economy and laid the foundations of the new economic growth of the Celtic Tiger era (Ní Mháille Battel 2003: 99). The country's new-found confidence as an emerging economic power on the European and the global scene was emphasised in the representation of a new kind of masculinity in *About Adam*. Ireland's Third Wave Cinema of the late 2000s and early 2010s found a balance between domestic concerns and global appeal. This bore fruit in films that have brought national and international success: *Once* (Carney 2006), *Garage* (Abrahamson 2007), *What Richard Did* (Abrahamson 2012), *Brooklyn* (Crowley 2015), and *Room* (Abrahamson 2015). These films have won recognition in the Academy Awards, Irish Film & Television Awards, Critics' Choice Awards, Golden Globe Awards, and British Academy Film Awards, and have produced positive financial returns on initial government, EU, and private sector investments. Finally, the film mentioned above promoted the country in a way that was envisioned in the *Final Report of the Film Industry Strategic Review Group (FRFISRG)* and their "Vision of the Future" published in 1999.

As Ruth Barton argues in *Irish National Cinema*, Irish cinema needed to be aware of both its national and international audience, especially during the Celtic Tiger. There was the question of the indigenous, the diasporic, and the international audiences, and the means of financing Irish films through American, European, and local investments (Barton 2004: 4–5 and 7–8). In *Irish Cinema in the Twenty-first Century* (2019), she devotes further attention to the debate around the global and the local as she summarises the economic, social, and political changes in Ireland. She details the changes in Ireland's economic circumstances, in its population through political and economic migration, and in its relation to the Catholic Church, which, for centuries, had provided a social and moral framework for Irish society (2019: 4–5). She remarks on the decline in the number of socially conscious films and the almost complete abandonment of the social-realist documentaries (2019: 15–16). Irish society was coming to terms with its own past and with the political and religious scandals of the past decades, while at the same time, it was welcoming increasing amounts of political and economic migrants from inside and outside the European Union. On the level of the economy, it was embracing modern-day consumer capitalism as it was witnessing growing differences between the wealthy and the poor. Among the results of these developments was a marked indifference to historical narratives, like that of *Michael Collins* (Jordan 1996). As Barton writes in "Between Modernity and Marginality: Celtic Tiger Cinema" (2014), films of the period "have shown themselves to be largely unconcerned with history, locating their narratives firmly in the present, and most often in present-day Dublin" (2014: 222). Those interested in socially charged themes tried their hands at genre films, such as the crime/caper movies, for example, being Lenny Abrahamson's *Adam and Paul* (2004) and *Garage* (2007) (Barton 2014: 227). The mainstream film industry of a now prosperous, multicultural country promoted films that reflected the new social and economic circumstances. Barton asks the following questions concerning this: can mainstream Irish cinema still function as a "social mirror;" and is it still possible for it to reflect on Irish society, as opposed to embracing the changes wholeheartedly? (2019: 6). Barton was not alone in asking these questions; a decade earlier, similar issues had been raised about modern Irish drama in Christopher Murray's seminal critical work *Twentieth-Century Irish Drama: Mirror up to Nation* (1997).

3 *Parked* and the Irish Cinematic Tradition

Documentarist Darragh Byrne brought out his first feature-length film in 2010. *Parked* is a good example of the transnational cooperations that create cinema in Ireland in the twenty-first century: the film was made by Ripple World Pictures, Helsinki Filmi, Bord Scannán na hÉireann/Irish Film Board, Suomen Elokuvasäätiö/Finnish Film Foundation, and Radio Teilifis Éireann (RTÉ). As a work of transnational collaboration, it was financially supported by the MEDIA Programme of the European Union. *Parked* had its roots in First Wave Irish Cinema in that it is indebted to the tradition of portraying marginalised characters. Its concept was not dissimilar to that of Joe Comerford's realist short films from the 1970s and 1980s in its representation of the "underground" world of substance abuse that is presented as a direct consequence of a series of societal failures and personal mistakes. *Withdrawal* was intended to be an unabashed representation of "institutional confinement" to which heroin addicts were subjected in psychiatric wards (Finn 2012: 21). When it came to cinematography, Comerford used a string of close-ups to emphasise the anguish and hopelessness of those who suffered from heroin addiction. Byrne uses a similar technique to highlight Cathal's never-ending struggle with heroin and other chemical substances. Besides *Withdrawal*, *Parked* has a thematic link to Lenny Abrahamson's multi-award-winning *Adam and Paul* (2004), a cult film of Second Wave Irish Cinema that portrayed two heroin addicts from inner-city Dublin. Beckett's *Waiting for Godot* is called into analyses of the film (Monahan 2006), as it traces two junkies' journey through Dublin until one of them dies of overdose in Dublin Bay. Darragh Byrne's *Parked* picks up on the theme but adjusts it to the demands of Third Wave Irish Cinema. *Parked* was to divert from the gruesome realism of Comerford's *Withdrawal* and Abrahamson's *Adam and Paul*, as indicated by Byrne: in an interview with *CultBox* (2012), he said that *Parked* was to have a "warm and engaging story with integrity and charm." This embrace of the audience-friendly style of mainstream Third Wave Cinema was in line with the recommendations of the *Final Report of the Film Industry Strategic Review Group (FRFISRG)* and their "Vision of the Future" mentioned earlier. *Parked* engages with the long-standing cinematic tradition of representing the marginalised, but it reinvents this tradition to meet the needs of commercial cinema that was successful at the beginning of the twenty-first century.

The *Final Report of the Film Industry Strategic Review Group* (1999) outlined the strategies for the development of the Irish film industry between 2000 and 2010, the height of the Celtic Tiger period. Some of the elements of these new strategies were a government-funded script and project development scheme, increased support for the building of indigenous film companies and production environments, and better product management on the global market. Barton writes that, by the end of the Celtic Tiger period, some £17 million a year was spent on indigenous film production (2014: 220), sourced mostly by direct funds from the Irish Film Board and tax incentives offered by the Irish government under Section 481 of the Finance Act (FRFISRG 1999: 14). The Irish Film Board (Bord Scannán na hÉireann) took an active role in the funding and promoting indigenous films, successfully drawing on public, private and European funds (MEDIA Programme). The Irish government offered direct support to small and medium sized Irish firms (SMEs) to assist their growth and their entering the globalised market economy through the Irish film industry (FRFISRG 1999: 31). This amount of money was poured into the Irish film industry because, as the SRG put it, "a substantial and vibrant Irish film and television industry [was] critical to a full realisation of Ireland's cultural and economic potential in the world" (FRFISRG 1999: 13). Ireland, it was suggested, was to

have a ‘strong and distinctive presence’ in the media of film and television, both home and abroad (*FRFISRG* 1999: 13), to boost the country’s image for potential investors. Ireland had been known for its “powerful storytelling tradition” in the field of literature and drama, stated the *FRFISRG*, and Ireland was in a good position to share this tradition with a global audience (1999: 13 and 32). As the document further claimed, a country’s cinematic representation was “the most powerful form of cultural expression [...] at the cutting edge of a global media revolution” (*FRFISRG* 1999: 49).

Parked resonated with the audience and was welcomed by the film industry. It won awards in Boston, Paris, Brussels, Mannheim-Heidelberg, and it bagged the coveted Best First Feature Award at the Galway Film Fleadh, Ireland’s most prestigious film festival. *Parked* was well received internationally and domestically, as were other films in the past that used the topos of the “returning Irishman.” Around the time of the release of *Parked*, there were at least three other feature-length films that used it: *Leap Year* (Tucker 2010), *Jimmy’s Hall* (Loach 2014), and *Brooklyn* (Crowley 2015). The topos itself dates back to the first decades of the twentieth century, to Kalem Brothers’ silent, black-and-white film, *The Lad from Old Ireland* (Olcott 1910). This film tells the story of Terry (Sydney Olcott), the newly elected mayor of New York, who returns to Ireland to save his childhood sweetheart’s family from being evicted from their property. John Ford’s *The Quiet Man* (1952) recounted the story of the re-integration of renowned Irish American boxer Sean Thornton (John Wayne). In this Oscar-winning movie, the title character successfully reclaims his childhood home and marries his Irish sweetheart, Kate Danaher (Maureen O’Hara). Another version of the “returning Irishman” character appears in Alan Parker’s *The Commitments* (1991), a BAFTA-winning adaptation of Roddy Doyle’s novel of the same title from 1987. Saxophonist Joey “the Lips” Fagan (Johnny Murphy) comes back to Ireland to partake in the formation of a new Dublin Motown band, *The Commitments*. Of these iconic films, Alan Parker’s *The Commitments* seems to be the closest to Byrne’s *Parked* in that it represents serious social issues: its main characters are living on the dole or working in poorly paid jobs; they are rehearsing in the shabby backstreets of the northside Dublin, and Ireland’s capital looks dirty and rundown, very different from the modern *chic* of Celtic Tiger Dublin in Stemberge’s *About Adam* (2001). Within this cinematic tradition, the Irish community tended to look upon the “returning Irishman” character as someone successful, especially because they were returning from the prosperous and powerful United States. Byrne’s *Parked* offered a new take on the topos: the main character is broken, homeless, and unemployed. He is unable to save his friend from drug-related violence and heroin overdose. However, his reintegration seems to succeed eventually, with the help of a female character, called Jules. This variation of the topos allowed the filmmakers to reflect on consumer-driven capitalism, while at the same time offering a heartwarming story that audiences would still care to watch.

4 *Parked* as Reflection on Celtic Tiger Ireland

4.1 Homelessness and Unemployment

Fred Daly (Colm Meaney), the “returning Irishman,” is re-engaging Irish society, having spent time in England. He seems to have worked a few manual jobs there, but not much is revealed about his life abroad. He lived in England during the “Cool Britannia” period, when Britain

was “riding the tiger of economic progress” (Kramer 2003: 78).¹ Kramer (2003) explains that during the New Labour Era of Prime Minister Tony Blair (between 1997 and 2007), the UK government prided itself on currency stability, revenue increase, rising employment rates, increasing consumption and interest in communication technologies. Fred’s failure is epitomised in the fact that Fred could not avail of any of the opportunities in Britain, despite New Labour’s minimal wage scheme and programmes of social inclusion. He returns to Ireland only with some cash and starts living in an abandoned car park in Dublin Bay. His weekly visits to the Social Welfare Office lead him nowhere. Fred has no fixed abode; therefore, he is not entitled to social benefits, and the welfare officer does not seem to be able to find work for him. According to Irish law, in order to fulfil the Habitual Residence Condition (HRC) that would have qualified him for social welfare benefits, such as Jobseeker’s Allowance, he would have needed permanent residency in Ireland. Fred returns to Ireland at a challenging time: the country is on the onset of the Global Recession and in talks with the “Troika” of EU/IMF/ECB to agree to the bailout package, as Shinnick explains (2008: 61). Finding work during this time was not easy. While unemployment “was virtually eliminated” in Ireland during the Celtic Tiger, as Peadar Kirby notes in *Celtic Tiger in Collapse: Explaining the Weaknesses of the Irish Model* (2010: 2), there was a sharp rise in unemployment figures in the subsequent years. Predictions for 2010 were reaching 17 per cent of the Irish labour force (Kirby 2010: 2). Kirby further notes another important aspect: “the ratio of social security spending to GDP fell markedly” in a country that had already given “priority to economic growth over social equity” (2010: 8). Neglecting the Irish work force at this important time significantly contributed to the increased unemployment figures post-Celtic Tiger. Unlike *The Commitments*, there are no long queues waiting for news of employment. However, the fact that the welfare officer shuts down all conversation with Fred points out the difficulties that Director Byrne intended to address in the post-Celtic Tiger Ireland of his time.

Apart from unemployment, homelessness, and the housing crisis, are also addresses in *Parked*. Fred’s first trip to Dublin takes him to his childhood home, now occupied by a young family who had bought the house from Fred’s father. Fred is too ashamed to have a long conversation with the family and lies about his current situation. Close-up shots convey Fred’s inner turmoil as he sees his childhood home and his favourite tree now belong to someone else. As sad and devastating as this moment is for Fred, the close-ups director Byrne uses accentuates the film’s message that Fred needs to move away from the memories of the past (*CultBox* 2012) Fred then returns to his worn car in Dublin Bay and sets to work mending watches, an appropriate metaphor for fixing lost time. Fred practically *lives* in his car and is entirely self-sustained: he has water to make a cup of coffee, a table to use for his dinners, a plant to look after, and a notebook that he uses as a diary. He has tools for mending clocks and watches, and warm clothes to wear in the cold weather. His circumstances indicate that he had not moved onto the property ladder in England, and it does not seem likely that the circumstances would be different in Dublin. Denis O’Hearn explains the situation with housing during the Celtic Tiger in “Macroeconomic Policy in the Celtic Tiger: A Critical Reassessment:” house ownership and affordable housing had become largely unattainable by the mid-2000s, with the lack of social housing being an even bigger issue (2003: 49). In *The Celtic Tiger? The Myth of Social Partnership in Ireland*, Kieran Allen states that those in need of appropriate housing at

¹ For further details on the social and economic policies of the “New Labour” government of Prime Minister Tony Blair, see Michael Kitson and Frank Wilkinson’s “The Economics of New Labour: Policy and Performance” (2007), and Martin Powell (eds.), *Modernising the Welfare State: The Blair Legacy* (2008).

the height of the Celtic Tiger was somewhere around 135 000 (2000: 95). As data shows, Ireland's "social provision legged badly behind that of many European countries" (Kirby 2010: 7) and homeless figures doubled between 1996 and 2006 (McVerry 2008: 371). *Parked* prioritises the issue of homelessness, which strongly suggests that Third Wave Irish Cinema was well able to tell stories of social engagement, if filmmakers' will had been there. As the *Final Report of the Film Industry Strategic Review Group* and their "Vision of the Future" recommended, those were the stories that "societies need[ed] to hear" (1999: 49).

4.2 Homelessness and Substance Abuse

Cathal O'Regan's (Colin Morgan) storyline reflects on the issue of substance abuse. Fred and Cathal's scenes on the seashore are shot in greyish-blue colours that emphasise the melancholy of the characters, unsure of their future. Father Peter McVerry, who had been caring for young drug offenders in Dublin for decades, has drawn attention to the correlation between homelessness and drug consumption in Ireland. According to him, during the Celtic Tiger, drug consumption among the young was on the rise due to the increased availability of substances, from heroin and cocaine to cannabis and other chemical substances (2008: 373). Cathal O'Reily is one of those homeless young people who is caught up in Dublin's drug scene. There are scenes in *Parked* when he is being pushed for money, including one in which the drug gang kicks him nearly unconscious. The situation comes to the point where Fred even offers whatever little savings he has to rescue Cathal from the violent gang. He does this in return for Cathal's promise of getting off heroin. Cathal, however, cannot keep this promise; there is a scene in which he is seen rummaging through his father's belongings in search of cash to pay off his dealers. Cathal's return to the family home is fraught with problems as his father blames Cathal and his self-destructive lifestyle for the death of Cathal's mother. The relationship between the father and the estranged son is portrayed sensitively in the film, and the father now sadly succumbed to the inevitable fate of his son. Father Peter McVerry explains that it was not uncommon for families to be giving up on their young as they had no means to change their behaviour, nor their dangerous and violent social circle. McVerry correlates homelessness, substance abuse, and mental health issues in Irish society: "some people became homeless because their families were unable to cope with the behaviour that their mental health problems created; being homeless then intensified their mental health problem" (2008: 372).

Cathal builds a new father-son relationship with Fred. He channels all his boyish affections towards a father figure into his mission to help Fred settle back into Ireland. He assists the older men in his quest for social housing and welfare benefits and encourages them to seek a partner in Jules, the widowed Finnish piano teacher, whom Fred meets regularly in the local swimming pool. Cathal is successful in Fred's social reintegration, but he cannot find a way back to mainstream society. To emphasize this fact, director Byrne uses a modern paraphrase of the first lines of Dante Alighieri's *Inferno* from *La Divina Commedia*: "In the middle of the journey of life, I was in a dark wood, for I had lost the true path, and so we came forth and once again beheld the stars" (1:18:51–1:19:32). Fred quotes these lines while himself and Cathal are sitting in the car on the hilltop, looking down on the "city of fireworks," as Cathal describes night-time Dublin that sparkles with its lights. Cathal indeed seems to have lost "the true path" and was living in his *inferno*. Fred quotes the lines again—this time in full—at Cathal's coffin as he gently lays his notebook with the quotation on Cathal's corpse. Dante's words connect various threads of the story: Fred, too, used to be in the "dark woods"

of his life, until he “beheld the stars” and “came forth” from the state of stasis, with Cathal’s assistance. Further to this, the quotation makes another poignant connection, the one between the “fireworks of stars” that sparkled over night-time Dublin and the roadside bonfire where homeless addicts gather for the cold and windy night. Cathal dies at this bonfire from an overdose of heroin and other mind-altering substances, having been beaten near unconscious again by his drug dealers. Byrne’s film follows reality closely in its depiction of social exclusion and drug abuse, commenting on contemporary Ireland. In his article “Problem Drug Use and the Political Economy of Urban Restructuring: Heroin, Class and Governance in Dublin” (2005), Michael Punch writes that heroin use among the young had been an issue in Ireland’s capital city for decades and argues that there was a direct link between the increase in heroin consumption and the unaffordability of social housing during the Celtic Tiger era. Punch’s findings align with the experiences of those in daily contact with substance users, such as Father Peter McVerry. Poly-drug addiction also became a serious problem in Celtic Tiger Ireland (Windle et al. 2023: 28), one on which Byrne reflects seriously in *Parked*. As a result of the “hedonism [that] was promoted during the boom years as a core economic activity,” “heavy drinking and drug taking became central to the consumer experience of the night-time economy,” write Windle et al (2023: 29). Actor Colin Morgan, who played Cathal, emphasised that his portrayal of Cathal was based on his experience with young poly-drug users whom he had visited in a Dublin rehabilitation centre when preparing for the role (*Cast Interview* 2010). Cathal’s story of substance abuse would have spoken to a wider audience than its most immediate audience in Ireland. In their study, Windle et al. have found, that the poly-drug addiction was not unique to Irish youth; rather, it was a trend in youth culture around Europe (2023: 28). Darragh Byrne had once again chosen to use the path recommended by the *Final Report of the Film Industry Review Group* in their “Vision of the Future.” Director Byrne told a story that resonated both with the domestic audience and audiences worldwide (*FRFISRG* 1999: 33).

4.3 Migration and “Reversed Migration”

Jules’s (Milka Alroth) story taps into the question of migration and “reversed migration,” reflecting on contemporary social debates. As Dermot McAleese states, “Irish GDP per capita at PPP surpass[e]d the UK level in 1996 and the EU average shortly afterwards,” and in 2000 it stood at “115 per cent of EU’s average GDP, compared with the 58 per cent when Ireland joined the Common Market in 1973” (2000: 47). There was a “huge expansion in job opportunities,” with a “reversal from net emigration to significant net immigration” (McAleese 2000: 47). The Irish economy needed an expanding labour force, which resulted in significant population growth between the mid-1990s and 2008 (Fanning 2014: 128). Brian Fanning notes that the number of non-nationals living in Ireland was over 610,000 in 2006 (2014: 130), this number only slightly declining to over 544,000 by the recession year of 2011 (2014: 130).²

² In Ireland, the term “non-nationals” is used to include refugees and asylum seekers. Steve Loyal notes that, despite the growing numbers of asylum seekers in Ireland during the Celtic Tiger years, the scale of political migration was still significantly lower than the levels of economic migration. It is beyond the scope of the present paper to analyse the life and prospects of those seeking refuge in Ireland, and the cinematic representation of political migration around the millennium. For the examination of these themes, see Steve Loyal’s “Welcome to the Celtic Tiger: Racism, Immigration and the State” (2003) and Agnes Kakasi’s “Migration and ‘Intercultural’ Cinema in Ireland: A New Direction?” (2011).

This increase generated debates on the long-term status of the new arrivals, resulting in a referendum on the Irish Nationality and Citizenship Bill in 2004, the creation of a new post, Minister of State for Integration, in 2007, and the government's publication of the *Migration Report* in 2008. Not convinced that the social integration of non-national workers could be realised, some feared the ever-increasing levels of migration to Ireland. *Parked* presents the issue of non-nationals living in Ireland in a positive light. Director Byrne makes Jules's character a *facilitator*, a means through which Fred finds his way back to Irish society. Jules is a liminal character, both an insider and an outsider. She was born in Finland, but she has been living in Ireland. Her living room is full of memorabilia of her life with Liam and their travels around the world as members of a chamber orchestra. As a social person, she involves Fred in social activities, such as aquatic classes and church gatherings. She stands for *inclusivity* in the film; hence, her religious affiliation is left rather vague. Religious life in Ireland had been mired in controversy since the publication of The Ryan Report in May 2004, which exposed an alarming number of cases of child abuse in reformatories and industrial schools that had been run by the Catholic Church and the Irish state between 1936 and 1999. *Parked* conveniently glosses over these debates, making Jules a member of the fictional "Holy Day Church," a relatively new, evangelical church. What *Parked* presents as *important* concerning Jules's character is her spirituality and her belonging to a local community, not the institutionalised nature of her religious practice, or the religious dogmatism of the church she attends. Similar to her character, her church is also both inside and outside of mainstream Irish society. What is important for the film is that Jules a free-spirited artist, who is stuck in her life, like Fred and Cathal. Jules needs Fred as much as he needs her to get "unstuck," or "unparked" in the life she was leading in Ireland, as director Byrne explained in his interview with *CultBox* (2012).

Cinematically, Jules's scenes balance out the night scenes of Cathal's substance abuse and the seaside scenes of Fred's loneliness, coloured in greys, blues, and bluish black. In terms of the narrative strands of the film, Jules's storyline brings together three metaphors director Byrne uses throughout the film: the water, the clocks, and the music. At first, Fred does not dare to dive into the swimming pool, but only after his experiences with Fred and Jules does he feel the courage to take that "leap of faith." At the end, Fred is seen in a brown-hued scene, jumping headfirst into the water at its deep end, as a sign of him being ready to leap into his new life. He has moved his life from the open waters of the Irish Sea in Dublin Bay, exposed to a variety of natural elements, into the warmth and comfort of a concrete setting of an indoor swimming pool. Parallel to this, at the end of the film, Fred is seen sitting in the comfort of his new home that the Irish state now provides him. A series of clocks line his windowsill, all of them working. He has mended the non-working clocks in his life, as he had mended Cathal's father's watch and returned to him after Cathal's funeral, and as he had mended Jules's clock that stood on her mantelpiece, next to her pictures of worldwide travels. Following this scene, Jules comes to leave a piece of music for Fred. She had been composing a new piece throughout the film, and that piece is now completed and is ready to be given to Fred. She is doing so in the realisation that both of them had helped the other to move out of a state of stasis, and that they need to go their separate ways to arrive at their final destination. Jules is moving back to her family in Finland. Director Byrne flirts briefly with the theme of "reversed migration." As Pilar Villar-Argáiz and Jason King (2015) and Eleanor O'Leary and Diane Negra (2016) remind us, the issue of "reversed migration" became much-discussed when the Global Recession set in at the end of the 2000s. Consulting censuses, Brian Fanning noted that, between 2006 and 2011, the Irish labour market shrank by almost 13%, with labourers moving

back to their home countries (2014: 130). Previously, it was believed that the labour market would take care of the social integration of the new non-national labour force (Fanning 2014: 130); however, it became clear with the arrival of the recession years that the integration of non-nationals had been successful only to a certain degree and, as a result, some of the new labourers decided to return to their home countries. In *Parked*, Jules's return to Finland highlights the bittersweet ending of the film: she and Fred will continue their lives in different countries. Jules becomes the "returning character," like Fred, which completes the narrative cycle of the movie. Joachim Vogt Isaksen (2019) noted that, to a smaller and lesser degree, migration patterns in all EU countries were responsive to the fluctuation of economic stability. Hence, the themes of migration and "reverse migration" of Darragh Byrne's *Parked* would have resonated not just with Irish audiences but with audiences across Europe. This communication across cultures through the medium of film was also encouraged in the *Final Report of the Film Industry Strategic Review Group (FRFISRG)* (1999) and in the guidelines of the MEDIA Programme of the European Union that co-funded *Parked*.

5 Conclusion

Darragh Byrne's *Parked* reflects on a number of issues that preoccupied Irish society at the turn of the new millennium, such as homelessness, substance abuse, and migration. These issues are dealt with excessively in *Parked*, while other topics of social debate, such as religion, are entertained only lightly, to maintain the focus on the story of Fred Daly. *Parked* makes use of the topos of the "returning Irishman," which was used surreptitiously in non-indigenous representations of Ireland throughout the twentieth century. At the dawn of the twenty-first century, however, this topos is modified in *Parked* for several reasons: first, to adhere to the realistic strand of First Wave Irish Cinema; second, to use the realistic European tradition of cinema; third, to secure finances from a wide variety of sources, from the Finnish and Irish film industries to the MEDIA support programme of the European Union. The result is a work of art that sends a socially conscious message to both its Irish and its global audiences, a film that serves as a good example of Third Wave Irish Cinema entertaining audiences at the beginning of the twenty-first century.

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From Exclusion to Reintegration: The Case of Street Children in Bernard Ilunga Kayombo's *Quand les enfants crient misère*

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Abstract

The present study seeks to explore the challenges faced by street children in Kayombo's novel Quand les enfants crient misère (2008). The paper establishes that children are found in the street mainly due to abuse and neglect by parents, as well as the breakdown of traditional African family support system. However, these disinherited children were able to reintegrate into the social fabric of their communities and families due to the resilience, tenacity, a collective enterprise essentially carried out by the children themselves. Their success was also due to the careful patronage of a Catholic nun, Sister Consolatrice, who was able to listen and take new initiatives.

Keywords: Street children, parenting, support system, exclusion, resilience, re-integration.

It is not enough to sow the seeds of human life in quick, repeated sessions of ecstasy. Beyond the delight of tears, beyond the passionate intensity of countless orgasms, the future of our own morality and ancestry awaits our constant vigilance and careful nurturing. No seed grows into harvest joys without planter's diligent labour of love. Until we come to understand this as parents, as family, as community, we will forever stand condemned by the anguish in the eyes and the voices of our children, forever guilty of the nurturing of [...] prospective soul(s) into the devouring jaws of the streets.

Kofi Anyidoho, Introduction to *Faceless* (2003: xxi)

1 Introduction

In the introduction to the novel *Faceless*, Anyidoho (2003) says: "The phenomenon of street children has become one of the most widely discussed social tragedies of our time" (*Faceless*, XIX). This assertion shows the extent to which the problem is persisting, spreading and contaminating rapidly the urban cities of independent Africa. This is one of the reasons for which writing about children is of great interest (Koffi 2017). Through this paper, we propose to conduct an analysis of the life of street children, as depicted in Kayombo's novel *Quand les enfants crient misère* (2008). As a spokesperson of the community and voiceless fringes, Kayombo goes "beyond the silence of cemeteries to light on disrupted families, bungled marriages, and street children" (Mohamed 2021: 292).

The child is the future of tomorrow. As a result, he must enjoy special protection to guarantee his well-being. The family and the community remain privileged and favourable places for the protection of the child, in spite of all the other forms of benefits that can be offered by other protection institutions with good accommodation and alternative settings. It is surprising, however, that some children in the world today are found in the streets rather than their homes where they should be safely protected and cared for by parents.

1.1 Defining Street Children

There is no clear definition of street children. However, researchers have attempted to define the term “street children” in different ways, here are some of them. According to Panter-Brick (2002), street children are those who occupy the public spaces of urban centres and whose activities are largely unsupervised by adults, which leads people to view them as different from other children. This scholar argues that the United Nations has defined the term “street children” to include “any boy or girl [...] for whom the street in the widest sense of the word [...] has become his or her habitual abode and/or source of livelihood, and who is inadequately protected, supervised, or directed by responsible adults” (cited in Imtiaz 2009: 151).

According to Lusk (1989), the most commonly used definition comes from UNICEF and distinguishes two groups: Children on the street: these are “Home based” children who spend much of the day on the street but have some family support and usually return home at night. The other group is that of Children of the street: these are “Street based” children who spend most days and nights on the street and are functionally without family support. In the words of Raffaelli and Larson (1999), “The term street youth or street children conceals enormous variation in the experiences of youngsters who share the common condition of being ‘out of place’ in street environments, spending their lives largely outside the spheres typically considered appropriate for children, such as home, school, and recreational settings” (1999: 1). Focussing on Zambia context, Lungwangwa and Macwan’gi (2004: viii) apprise that a street child is understood to be that child aged 18 and below who make the street a place of his/her habitual abode. These scholars further observe that street children are: (i) homeless children who live on the street; (ii) those street children who are detached from their families and live with friends on the streets; and (iii) those children who live with their families on the streets.

Although there are variegated definitions of street children as seen above, they all share a common characteristic, that is, they all emphasize two peculiarities about street children: the *place* they occupy (the streets) and the absence of proper contacts or *links* with adults in the family home and in society. In other words, a street kid lives and sleeps in the rough besides being left at the mercy of cut-throat adults. The definition of street children adopted in this study is the one by Farrow et al. (1992) who argue that street children are typically those in the six and seventeen age range, and they live without the support of traditional societal structures, such as family, school, church, and community institutions.

1.2 Categories of Street Children

Generally, street children are a heterogeneous group of youngsters. In Natasya Rizki Yuanasari’s thesis titled *Vietnamese Children as seen in John Shors’ Dragon House* (2011), the scholar contends that UNICEF (n.d.) presents three categories of street children based on their background and living situation. These include:

a. *Street Living Children*: these are children who have lost ties with their families and live alone in the street.

b. *Children of Street Living Families*: these are the ones living with their families on the street.

c. *Street Working Children*: those who spend all or most of their times working on the street. They earn income on the street for their families or for themselves. These children have a home to return to and do not usually sleep on the street.

Similarly, in a study on street children across the world, Robinson (2014) observes that some street children known as street-living children live entirely on the streets, alone or in small groups. Others, known as street-working children, spend most of their time on the streets trying to survive, but return home from time to time. There are also those who live on the streets with their families. Meanwhile, Stearman (2000: 11) categorizes street children as follows: *Run from* and *Run to* Children. According to this scholar, “Running from” refers to children who are essentially escaping from unresolved personal and/or family problems. They tend to become hard-core gangsters on the street because of the anger they have against people and society at large. They feel let down by the people they thought they could trust. These children are often living in groups on the street, as this serves as the family they do not have. This group is often controlled by older boys or men and everyone has to contribute with what they can which means they have to go begging, working or do crime to have value on the group. Most of these children long for a day when they can be reunited with their families or will be able to live a normal life in a normal home. On the other hand, “Running to” Children are those that often find themselves addicted to drugs on the street as they tend to experiment with everything done on the streets. They find themselves having to go into drug trafficking or prostitution in order to support their addiction. These children often do not want to be reunited with their families or be taken into shelters as their urge for independence and addiction to drugs is too much. They often find themselves owing their lives to other people on the streets like drug lords who supply them with drugs. These children often operate alone and have spot in which you can identify them with (ibid. 2000: 11).

1.3 Causes of Streetism among Children

Perhaps an appropriate question to ask at this juncture is: why are children on the street? The reasons the children are on the streets are not always simple. Various factors have been used to explain the origins of street life involvement in African countries. According to Kopoka (2000), the world and Africa in particular are witnessing rapid and wide ranging socioeconomic and political changes. There is rapid urbanisation, excessive population growth and increasing disparities in wealth. Additionally, the introduction of structural adjustment programmes and globalization are changing the very fabric of African society. One of the negative consequences of these changes is the emergence of large numbers of children on the streets. City residents used different derogatory terms to describe these children; in Tanzania these street dwellers are known as *watoto wa mitaani*, in Kenya they are referred to as *chokora* and in The Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) they are called *moineaux*, meaning “sparrows”. By whatever name these children are called, Kopoka (2000) concludes that what stands out is the sad fact that everywhere, children living and working on the street are ignored, scorned, mistreated and misunderstood by society and by governments.

Meanwhile, Oyaya and Esamai (2001: 624), and Mahlangu (2002: 30) articulate that the street child phenomenon cannot be related to a single causal factor. Most researchers agree that the leading causes of street children are extreme poverty, unemployment, family breakdown (divorces), the death of parents, physical violence within the family, child abuse and neglect (West 2003: 12; Montane 2006: 9; De Moura 2005: 194; Le Roux 2001: 107; Malindi 2009: 4; Lewis 1998: 14; Pare 2004: 221; Plummer et al. 2007: 1532; Vogel 2001: 244; Robinson 2014: 1); as well as dropping out of school, behavioural disorders and civil war (Mahlangu 2002: 18).

In the same breath, Ibrahim (2012) argues that there are two main causes of the phenomenon of street children. The first is the economic stress and poor conditions that families face due to industrialisation and urbanisation. The second cause is changes in the traditional family structure, especially when women became the main contributor to households' economies (Patel 1990; Le Roux and Smith 1998; Lugalla and Mbwambo 1999). Additionally, Ugwuanyi (2020) observes that some of the contributing factors to street children phenomenon include poverty, absentee parents, and misplaced priority on the part of government.

2 Synopsis of the Novel

Authored by the Congolese Catholic Priest and novelist Bernard Kayombo, *Quand les enfants crient misère* (2008) – which I have translated as *When Children Cry Misery* – as the novel has not yet been translated in English – tells the story of some teenage boys in a merciless world dominated by greedy, irresponsible and often cruel adult men and women in their life. The novel is a tale of what can be termed as: “a diseased society that seems to have lost its hold on the lives of its children” (Anyidoho 2003: ix-x). In this novel, the author gives the portrayal of street children that include Sinandugu, Sikosalangu, Bahati, Mulanda, Mambo ya haya, Masikini, Munene and Tshibwabwa, among others. These children left their homes and community for various reasons amongst them poverty, lack of educational opportunities, rural to urban migration (Mambwe 1997; Sampa 1997), social changes, the weakening of family structures and family abuse (Aptekar 1997; Mambwe 1997; Sampa 1997; Suda 1997), alcohol abuse from the parents, family instability, the declining role of the extended family, just to mention the few. Consequently, they find escaping to the streets as a safe heaven. Once on the streets, these children beg, pilfer, grab and steal in order to survive.

According to Chima-Udeh (2011), Achebe sees the African writer as one that functions in the African society as “The record of the lores and experiences of his society, and the voice of vision in his own time” (Chima-Udeh 2011: 159). In this regard, Kayombo (2008) as a novelist, is a social observer; through his searchlight, he records the social malaise that many of us overlook. It is by close observation that Kayombo (2008) is able to capture the problems of Sinandugu, Sikosalangu, Mambo ya Haya, Bahati, Mulanda, Tshibwabwa and many other street children as recorded in *Quand les enfants crient misère* (2008). These children are plunged into the streets primarily by parental neglect and the resultant poverty and hunger they face, as well as disintegration of traditional African family support system. But through their resilience, and united as one man under the guidance of their leader, Sinandugu, these street children decide to make their voice heard and take up the challenge: to leave the street and reintegrate into normal life.

3 Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

Guerin (2005: 16) contends that there is no single theory that is adequate for gaining a complete understanding of a text and that several theories would have to be used together. Thus, this article benefits immensely from the lens of the resilience theory and the concept of exclusion

as frameworks to explore the lived experiences of street youth in Kayombo's novel *Quand les enfants crient misère*.

Resilience has been defined in a variety of ways, including the ability to bounce back or recover from stress, to adapt to stressful circumstances, to not become ill despite significant adversity, and to function above the norm in spite of stress or adversity (Carver 1998; Tusaie & Dyer 2004). Luthar, Cicchetti & Becker (2000) have defined resilience as the "dynamic process encompassing positive adaptation within the context of significant adversity" (2000: 65) or, as Edwards (2007) puts it in the context of developmental psychology, "resilience [...] is a capacity for adaptation along appropriate developmental pathways, despite disruptions such as family, breakdowns" (2007: 62).

We should hasten to add that resilience does not mean giving up. Quite the opposite, it calls for more courage. In a nutshell, resilience emphasises the strengths that people have rather than their vulnerability, through exploring the coping strategies that they exhibit. It should therefore be mentioned that a resilient individual is the one that possesses the quality of "stick-to-it-iveness." Such a person perseveres until the task is completed or the goal is achieved. He or she views obstacles as just one of the many hurdles of life to be jumped.

Another important concept that has been adopted to examine the plight of street children in this paper is exclusion. According to Levitas et al. (2007), social exclusion involves the lack or denial of resources, rights, goods and services, and the inability to participate in the normal relationships and activities, available to the majority of people in a society, whether in economic, social, cultural or political arenas. It affects both the quality of life of individuals and the equity and cohesion of society as a whole.

Additionally, in the analysis of social exclusion in Yemen, Adra (2006) posits that social exclusion refers to relative rather than absolute deprivation. The denial of rights to land ownership in a community where income security depends on land, denial of education or health care when these are available to others, denial of access to community projects or social life in a community; all indicate forms of social exclusion. Adra (2006) further contends that social exclusion is not only disempowering, but it makes it difficult for the excluded to take advantage of opportunities for employment, education and health care, thus keeping them in chronic poverty. Furthermore, Walker and Walker (1997) define social exclusion as: "the process of being shut out, fully or partially, from any of the social, economic, political or cultural systems which determine the social integration of a person in society. Social exclusion may, therefore, be seen as the denial (or non-realization) of the civil, political, and social rights of citizenship" (1997: 8).

For young people who become homeless, social exclusion is experienced in terms of access to shelter and housing, employment, and a healthy lifestyle, for instance. It is also manifest in their restricted access to (and movement within) urban spaces and their limited social capital. In most cases, the process of social exclusion begins before street children become homeless, but it intensifies through their experience living on the streets. This experience of social exclusion is cumulative, making it difficult to escape, particularly when constant exposure to risk compromises health, safety, and opportunity. As an outcome of their homelessness, street children are typically pushed into places and circumstances that impair their ability to ensure their safety and security and, consequently, increase their risk of criminal victimization.

From the above, it is clear that social exclusion is a complex and multifaceted notion. It refers to both individuals and societies, and to disadvantage, alienation and lack of freedom.

While the former case may refer to disadvantage which individuals may perceive, the latter refers more to the institutions that are necessary to minimize exclusion and bring about social integration (Gore 1996).

4 Textual Analysis and Discussion

An old African adage states: “It takes a village to raise a child.” This saying suggests that raising a child is a communal effort. In traditional African society, a shared responsibility involved members of the extended family (older children, aunts and uncles, grandparents and many others). For example, a child’s welfare and conduct was the concern of everybody in the community, and adults could discipline a child for misconduct and the parents would further punish the child if a report was made to them. This is in line with Suda (1997) who aptly argues that in traditional African family, life depended to a great extent on kinship relationships and support networks across extended family lines. Close relatives were expected to take the initial responsibility to provide needy children and other poor members of the family with food, clothing, shelter, health care and education. She says, for example that, “among the Luo of Western Kenya, if a parent died, the surviving members of the extended family were often close at hand to ensure that the children and other dependants were cared and provided for. Part of the obligation of the extended family system was to assist those who were in need” (1997: 200). Adding their voice to the debate, Kilbride and Kilbride (1990) point out that this support network served as a barrier to the problem of child abuse and neglect in East Africa (Cited in Suda 1997: 200). These scholars further posit that the kin-based support system served to ensure that the death of one or both parents did not necessarily spell destitution for orphans or other family members in deprived and difficult circumstances. Consequently, these support networks had the potential to reduce destitute children in the family or community, as such children will not have to be left to cope on their own or to turn to the streets to beg, or to be taken to institutions. In line with this, Ogbeide Victor (2015) observes that “in traditional Africa, little or nothing was heard about the phenomenon of street children as every community took care of its inhabitants” (2015: 147).

In this paper, we propose to evaluate the plight of street children and the resilience strategies they use to emphasize and draw attention on the serious and growing phenomenon of street children, particularly in Africa, and how they eventually reintegrate into the society. The predicament of street children portrayed by Kayombo (2008) in his novel *Quand les enfants crient misère* reveals the social tragedy which the contemporary African society in general, and DRC in particular, is confronted with. One question that comes to our mind is: “why should somebody living under a secure roof let go of his or her child on the streets?” (Awitor 2003: 126). Even if “there is a story behind every street child”, it is obvious that parents, society as a whole and government have failed to cater for them. Their plight is overlooked, ignored or seen as normal. Sent away from home by their own parents, these children find refuge in the “devouring jaws of the streets” (ibid.).

Before going further, let us comment on some of the names of street children that are found in Kayombo’s *Quand les enfants crient misère* (2008). It should be mentioned that, unlike in the Western culture where name is merely a tag, pointer-out which in itself has next to no meaning (Adamic 1942), in many African societies, personal names are not just arbitrarily concatenated words but rather words that reflect the world-view of the people, this explains

why they are not randomly bestowed on people; they are given for specific reasons. Certain names are given based on the circumstances surrounding the birth of a child. For instance, among the Lunda of Zambia, if a child is born soon after the death of any member within the homestead, the child will be named *Kamfunti* “the one who has come back.” This is because such a person is thought to have returned to the homestead where he or she once lived as a family member (Mutunda 2011).

As far as the use of names in literary text is concerned, Wamitila (1999) submits that names of characters go beyond the confine of being seen as a mere tag that distinguishes one character from another to being a semantic, pragmatic, allusive, and symbolic import that must be seen in the perspective of the overall structure of a particular work. In the same breath, Ennin and Nkansah (2016) contend that names play a significant role in the narrative and lend a special aesthetic quality to the story; they foreground particular themes or motifs, reveal the fictional character, situate a character within a specific and identifiable cultural setting, reveal different point of view and even used as a plot device, as a sarcastic or a satirical strategy. It should also be noted that, writers of literary texts have the tendency to use allegorical names that reflect the important traits of a character either humorously or ironically. It is therefore justifiable that we give some attention to the names of the major characters and their meanings in the Kayombo’s (2008) novel,

The street children in *Quand les enfants crient misère* (2008), have circumstantial names. The main character and leader of the street children is Sinandugu, which means “I do not have relatives” in Kiswahili, one of the languages spoken in Lubumbashi (DRC). Sinandugu was nicknamed Rambo by his peers because of his physical strength and character. Thus, the narrator describes him as follows :

Sinandugu [était] surnommé Rambo par ses petits copains à cause de sa force physique. [...] Taille moyenne, torse bien fait [...] Le petit bout d’homme était bâti à chaux et à sable. Ces avantages physiques cohabitaient harmonieusement avec ses qualités morales. [...]

(Kayombo 2008: 9-10)

[Sinandugu [was] nicknamed Rambo by his friends because of his physical strength. [...] Medium waist, well-made torso [...] The little man was well built. These physical advantages matched harmoniously with his moral qualities.

We learn that the man who made Sinandugu’s mother pregnant when she was just seventeen abandoned her. When his child was born, Sinandugu was taken in by his grandmother, who took care of him. At the age of ten, the boy had just finished his fifth year of primary school when his grandmother also passed away. At the time of her death, she told his uncle and aunt to take care of Sinandugu. Living with his uncle was not easy. Soon, his uncle’s wife started accusing him of being a thief and was punished for that. Having had enough, the boy left and sought refuge at his maternal aunt who was a prostitute and homeless; thus, Sinandugu could not count on her. That is how he found himself on the street.

Unlike Sinandugu, Sikosalangu, whose name signifies “it is not my fault” in Kiswahili language, had both parents. Sikosalangu was suffering from albinism, everyone despised him because he was the shame of the family. Each time he was walking on the street with his mother, people pointed at his mother saying: “The mother of the albino child.” Sikosalangu was not only disliked by his family but also in the neighbourhood, at school, and everywhere!

Therefore, having had enough of humiliation, Sikosalangu slammed the door and left for the street.

Like Sikosalangu, Bahati, whose name means “good luck,” in Kiswahili, has a father, whom he vowed never to forgive for being the cause of all his suffering. Bahati had three siblings. When their mother died, they remained with their father. The father was a big drunk, a chaffed and lazy man who did not know how to work and take care of his family. For a long time, it was his wife who sustained the family, thanks to a small business she was doing. When she died, Bahati was seven years old. As a result, the children started dropping out of school, they also had to rely on themselves to find food. The search for food put Bahati in contact with some prostitutes in the neighbourhood. He provided his service as their pimp in exchange for money. One day, a prostitute who had hired him for a week kindly begged Bahati to get out of her house. Consequently, the once lucky provider found himself on the street.

One other street child is Mulanda, meaning “the unfortunate or miserable one,” in Bemba language. Mulanda attributes his misery to the brake up of his parents. His father used to come home late, sometimes he could not return at all. And once he came home it was to scold, beat and insult his wife without any apparent reason. Finally, one day Mulanda’s mother told her sons that she was being sent away by her husband, who wanted to bring in a younger woman. The moment their stepmother moved into their house, she mistreated the children so much that they wondered if she was not a wizard. Having had enough of torments, Mulanda and his brothers decided to run away to their paternal aunt where they took refuge. While there, they were made to understand that they were not wanted. Thus, Mulanda and his brothers ended up onto the street.

One other “child of the street” is Mambo ya haya. In Kiswahili the name means “A shameful matter.” Mambo ya haya was born of an incestuous relationship. His father was his mother's maternal uncle. Mambo ya haya’s scandalous coming into the world was a source of division. His grandmother was repudiated by her husband who wouldn't tolerate the scandal. Not everyone in the family wanted Mambo ya haya except his mother. Eventually, when he felt himself fit to hustle and stand on his own, he took his few belongings and went to the street. Other street children in the novel include Masikini, meaning “Poor person” in Kiswahili. Then comes Munene, which signifies “Fatty or fat boy.” This thirteen-year-old boy was chubby and dark-skinned, hence his peers nicknamed him *Corbeau* or “Crow.” He was sent to the street by his poverty-stricken family.

All of these lines above clearly reveal that these street children known as *moineaux* or “sparrows,” did not land onto the street on their own volition. It was primarily due to what Udogu (2018) terms dysfunctional parenting. Citing Bulus (2013), Udogu (2018: 83-84) argues that parenting is a divine calling that involves not just bringing a child into the world but being involved in promoting and supporting the physical, emotional, social and intellectual development of the child from infancy to adulthood. Being a parent therefore demands making provision for the child’s safety, shelter, nourishment, protection and physical development. However, this was not the case for these street children.

We should mention that in Africa, like elsewhere in the world, there are many people who believe that a man becomes a father when he impregnates a woman. However, fatherhood involves more than just procreation. As Anyidoho (2003) rightly points out: “It is not enough to sow seeds of human life [...]. No seed grows into harvest joys without planter’s diligent labour of love. Beyond the passionate intensity of countless orgasms, the future of our children, of our own morality and ancestry awaits our countless vigilance and careful nurturing” (2003:

xxi). Here, Anyidoho (2003) reminds us that procreation comes with responsibilities. Indeed, like a farmer who expect good yield ensures that he weeds his field of unwanted vegetation, a man should be prepared to fulfil his fatherhood roles and responsibilities in order to see his children grow happily. Surprisingly, not all men accept this role of fatherhood by promoting and supporting the physical, emotional, social, financial, and intellectual development of a child from infancy to adulthood. For such men, abandonment, flight and denial are seen as ways of avoiding fatherhood.

In our view, another important factor contributing to Sinandugu and his friends being on the streets is the declining role of traditional African support system. As alluded to earlier, traditional African family life depended to a great extent on kinship relationships and support networks across extended family lines. For example, among the Luo of Western Kenya, as pointed out earlier, if a parent died, the surviving members of the extended family were often ready to ensure that the children and other dependants were cared and provided for. Part of the obligation of the extended family system was to assist those who were in need. These support networks had the potential to reduce destitute children in the family or community. Such children did not have to be left to cope on their own or to turn to the streets to beg, or to be taken to institutions.

4.1 Hardship and Survival Strategies in the Streets

In *Quand les enfants crient misère* (2008), Sinandugu, Sikosalangu, Bahati, Mulanda, Mambo ya haya, Masikini, Munene, Jeki and Tshibwabwa are deprived kids who have turned the street into a temporary haven to protect themselves against the vicissitudes of a miserable existence. As Mohamed (2021) rightly points out, “the street is then described as problematic as the lives of its occupiers are. From infinitude, [the boys] move towards a finitude dead-end in turning their beings into instrument-bodies that flash out their physical mourning which is accorded to the harsh reality of the street lives” (2021: 296).

Once on the streets, children are exposed to different kinds of vices, abuses, and violence (drug, sex, alcohol, thieving, police mishandling and above all, absence of respect and love). They steal, pickpocket and do odd jobs to survive. Sacked from home by their own parents, they find refuge in the “devouring jaws of the streets” (Darko 2003: 42). Their living environment is a cocktail of explosive evils. Hygiene is lacking, security is absent, as are the possibilities of accessing to the most basic health care. Their dormitory is a space of extreme dehumanity, a perimeter of dumping ground for social effluvia. Misery becomes their all-occasion companion.

4.1.1 Violence and Hostility

Violence and hostility remain some of the main threats to street children’s existence. Indeed, once on the streets, the children are exposed to different kinds of vices, abuses, and violence, untimely and brutal death, and so on. Their fundamental human rights are constantly trampled upon to the extent that they are reduced to the status of animals. In the novel, Masikini, for instance, is killed as he attempts to snatch a bag of money from a market trader:

Un matin, au marché Lusonga (le marché principal de la ville de Lubumbashi), Masikini exerçait son métier de routine : le chapardage. Par manque de prudence, il fut pris la main dans le sac. Le sac d’argent. L’argent d’une vendeuse de choux et de pommes de terre. Mal lui en pris : toute la cohorte de mamans commerçantes [...] fonça sur le frêle être

humain. Une pluie de coups se déversa sur le corps rachitique du pauvre gamin. Et voilà : deux jours après, le gamin s'en fut dans un autre monde.

(Kayombo 2008: 6-7)

[One morning, at the Lusonga market (the main market in the city of Lubumbashi), Masikini was doing his usual job: pilfering. Unfortunately, he was caught with his hand in the bag. The bag of money. The money of a cabbage and potato seller. Unfortunately, [...] the whole cohort of market sellers pounced on the frail human being: a rain of blows poured over the body of the poor kid. And two days later, the boy passed away.]

From the foregoing, we can say that the attitude of the society is averse to street children. They have hardly any social status in the context of larger society. They are looked down upon by society as delinquents and are not trusted. As a result of societal mistrust and lack of love, street children are sometime lynched and even killed.

As the story unfolds, we learn of another incidence of violence. After spending some moment in the street, Sinandugu and his friends find refuge at a place of young adults of doubtful character. Sinandugu and his friends knew that their guests were criminals. But that did not bother them at all. For them, what matters was that they had a roof on their head. Later, we learn that, while the boys were asleep, they heard a booming voice of police officers: “Durango et consort, sortez de votre mesure, les bras en l’air” (*QECM* 42) [Durango and company, come out of your hovel, hands up]. The police raided their hovel and the boys were taken to the police station and tortured, later on they appeared in court where they were charged with aggravated robbery. Despite having claimed their innocence, the boys were locked up in cells. Two days after their release, the children went back to the streets and doing menial jobs such as selling cigarettes in order to survive. The boys returned to the streets with the determination to fight for a better and more humane life. Sinandugu puts their dream in this way:

Je rêve de fonder [...] un mouvement, un rassemblement; quelque chose comme une association de tous les enfants de la rue, qui lutterait pour l’amélioration de nos conditions de vie pour notre réinsertion dans la société.

(Kayombo 2008: 18)

[I dream of founding [...] a movement, a gathering; something like an association of all the street children, which would fight for the improvement of our living conditions for our reintegration into society.]

In the aforementioned excerpt, it is clear that the dream of Sinandugu and his friends is very simple: they want to live like everyone else. What they need is to be secured and know that somewhere there is somebody who cares for them. Unfortunately, they are abandoned to the streets like a vulgar and unwanted burden. Around them there is a void of sympathy and attention. As children, they are already at the margin of their society.

4.1.2 Health Problems

There is no doubt that the unhealthy urban environment in which these children live is a major cause of health problems among them. In a study on the health profile of street children in Africa, Cumber and Tsoka-Gwegweni (2016) observed that among the health problems identified are growth and nutritional disorders, physical injuries, violence, sexual abuse,

communicable diseases including diarrhoea diseases, malaria, respiratory diseases, neglected tropical diseases, mental health issues, substance abuse, reproductive health disorders, mortality, sexually transmitted diseases and HIV/AIDS. According to Rose-Junius (1993), concern with the health of street youth has been due to three factors. First, is their exposure to unhealthy elements, accidents and risks while on the street. Second, the difficulties that they face in accessing medical services including their inability to pay for such services, and lastly, their lack of motivation to use and ignorance of existing medical facilities.

In Kayombo's (2008) novel, we learn for example that when Mulanda fell ill, he had to struggle walking back to their temporal shelter. When his friends returned in the evening, they found him drenched in sweat. Sinandugu went to ask for pills from the three young lads who were temporarily hosting them, but they sent him away. Following that disappointment, the three colleagues of Mulanda contributed some money to buy him some anti-malaria drugs. Sinandugu remembered having seen somewhere in the neighborhood a dispensary. When he got there, he just sneaked into the reception room. The nurse gave him a rather cold welcome and ordered him to leave: "Fripon! [...] ne vois-tu pas que les gens entrent en ordre ? Ouste ? Dégage !" (*QECM* 27) ["Rogue ! [...] don't you see that people are getting in order? Oust? Get away!"]. As he was trying to resist while pleading, the head nurse came over, grabbed the kid and kicked him out.

Despite this disappointment, Sinandugu wanted Mulanda to be cured. He remembered the traditional medicine his grandmother used for curing malaria, which is the leaves of the papaya tree mixed with boiled water. Thus, he sent Thibwabwa to pluck some papaya leaves from the tree at the neighbour's house. Thibwabwa hesitantly knocked on the door of the neighbour who was already in bed. The neighbour asked the boy furiously before opening the door. Keeping a good distance, Thibwabwa answered him by pleading: "Je m'appelle Thibwabwa, l'un de vos voisins. [...] Je voudrais vous demander la permission de cueillir quelques feuilles de votre papayer" (*QECM* 31) ["My name is Thibwabwa, one of your neighbours. [...] I would like to ask for your permission to pluck some leaves from your papaya tree"]. But, before the seemingly furious neighbour could open the door, the boy escaped. Thibwabwa went back home bare-handed and informed his friends of his ordeal. At this point, Sinandugu told his friends to fight so that they could change their life for the better. He thus said:

Il faut que ça change ! Vivre ce n'est pas ça. Tu veux acheter une chloroquine, On te rebrousse. Tu veux demander des feuilles du papayer, on te menace. [...] Nous devons nous battre pour mettre fin à cet état de choses.

(Kayombo 2008: 32)

[Things have to change ! This is not living. You want to buy some chloroquine; they turn you back. You want to ask for papaya leaves, you are threatened. [...] We must fight to put an end to this state of affairs.]

It should be mentioned here that, one of the attributes of resilience is determination. A resilient person does not give up before his objective is attained. Despite the many challenges encountered, a resilient person remains focused and courageous for s/he views obstacles as just one of the many hurdles of life to be jumped. Therefore, after the failed attempt to secure some papaya leaves at their neighbour to cure Mulanda, Sinandugu suggested to his peers

Thibwabwa and Jeki that they seek the help of catholic priests and nuns in order to help save the life of their friend Mulanda.

Thus, determined to find a solution to Mulanda's illness, the trio arrived at the gate of a convent for nuns. As they waited, a slender nun appeared, then Sinandugu rushed to her and presented his request on behalf of his two comrades. But after narrating their problem to the sister, the latter could only give them a meager sum of money which could not even cover the five percent of the amount sought. Disappointed, the three boys went to see a priest. When they got in front of the parish priest's house, the monk appeared and asked for the purpose of their presence at his house. Unfortunately, once again, the three boys received a negative and hostile response. This incident made Thibwabwa doubt about religion: "Si même les hommes de Dieu deviennent mechants, qu'est-ce qui reste encore de bon dans ce pays" (*QECM* 40) ["If even the men of God become so wicked, what is still good in this country," he lamented].

4.2 Road to Reintegration into Normal Life

It has been forcefully argued that a portrayal of children as "vulnerable, incompetent and relatively powerless in society" (Morrow & Richards 1996: 90). However, to present street children as helpless victims of social discrimination does little to recognize their remarkable initiative and ingenuity in coping with difficult circumstances (Ennew 1994; Panter-Brick 2001).

Indeed, as we can see towards the end of novel, the children being tired of the harshness and danger of living in the streets, use their tenacity, initiative and ingenuity to reintegrate into society. Thus, Sinandugu and his peers devised a plan to draw the attention of adults' responsibilities. The collective enterprise essentially carried out by the children themselves help them achieve their objective. Sinandugu, assisted by Tshibwabwa, set up teams of five to seven children to roam the streets of different townships, with the mission of spreading ideas, sensitizing companions in misfortune, winning them over to the cause. Everywhere, marginalized children applauded the project. Under the patronage of the Canadian nun, Sister Consolatrice, the unfortunate children met somewhere in town, at the house of a man who was won over to the cause of children by Sister Consolatrice. At the end of a debate led by Sinandugu, ideas were put forward. The sister assisted the children in preparing a press release to be read in the different Catholic churches of the city. The goal was to refuse to be marginalized.

In one of the churches, Thibwabwa urged to the audience not to abandon them as they were their children: "Chers parents, frères et soeurs, ne nous oubliez pas! [...]" (*QECM* 73) ["Dear parents, brothers and sisters, do not forget us! [...]."] Moved by Tshibwabwa's speech, one lady among in the audience commented: "Voilà, la balle est dans notre camp. Voici venue le moment d'aimer en verité les enfants [...]. Dans la mesure du possible, nous répondrons à votre requête" (*QECM* 73) ["The ball is in our court. Now is the time to truly love the children [...]. As far as possible, we will respond to your request."] After mass, Tshibwabwa and his companion were surrounded and questioned by a group of sympathizing mothers. Some of these women handed banknotes to the two kids, while a journalist asked them what they wanted the most, Tshibwabwa replied: "Nous voulons la suppression ou, au moins, l'allègement du fardeau de nos misères. Nous voulons vivre comme tout le monde [...]" (*QECM* 75) ["We want the removal or, at least, the alleviation of the burden, of our miseries. We want to live like

all men [...]”]. At that moment, a journalist took a picture with the two street boys, which he subsequently published with an accompanying story in a local tabloid the following day.

Elsewhere, after mass at the main Cathedral of the city, Sinandugu was invited by a rich medical doctor and his wife to their home, where he narrated his life story. Sinandugu revealed their dream, he also talked about the kind Canadian nun who help them organise the process of spreading the message in various local churches. Sinandugu’s story reminded the husband of his orphaned past life. After lunch, the doctor’s wife suggested that Sinandugu spend the night at their house, but the boy declined the offer saying that his companions were anxiously waiting to be briefed about his visit.

Back to the meeting with his friends, Sinandugu listened attentively to each person's report. He commended them for the job well done and said:

Dorénavant nous sommes lancés [...] Marchons, mes amis, marchons ensemble! Nous sommes capables de modifier le cours des choses, ensemble! Soyons sérieux. Sérieux et courageux. Courageux tant individuellement et collectivement.

(Kayombo 2008: 80)

[From now on we are launched [...] Let us walk, my friends, let us walk together! We are capable of modifying the course of things, together! Let us be serious. Serious and courageous. Courageous both individually and collectively]

As leader of the street children, Sinandugu has an authority that the others do not have. Here we see how he is encouraging his friends to be resilient, courageous and work together as a group, for they have shown their capability to change the status quo and attain their goal that is to reject the marginalization, so as to improve their living conditions. We can see here that the values of solidarity are put forward.

It is worth mentioning that Sinandugu and his companions succeeded in their fight not only with the help of Sister Consolatrice, but also the tenacity and a collective enterprise essentially carried out by the children themselves; as well as the support of civil and ecclesiastical authorities. In this regard, to answer to the call of their leader Sinandugu, the street children organized a peaceful protest as another way to draw public attention. Sinandugu had meticulously sketched out a plan as well as a programme for the protest. One morning, children from every township of the city gathered in front of the post office downtown. In less than half an hour, the crowd of kids quickly attracted onlookers. There was commotion in town, the Lebanese and other business owners locked their shops and phoned the Governor, while others called the city Police Commissioner, for fear of having their shops looted. At the sight of the police, the kids in panic wanted to flee. But Sinandugu and Tchibwabwa told all them to remain calm. After rounding up some of those who were sitting silently on the ground, the police officers took them to the police station where they were interrogated by the Police Commissioner, who suspected that the kids were supported and sponsored by an opposition political party to cause havoc. However, Sinandugu told the Police Commissioner that their objective was not to cause havoc but to be given a chance to live once again, to be reintegrated into their society and community where they can enjoy their youth and eventually become useful members of society like everyone else.

At the end of the novel, we learn that, thanks to the speeches echoed across the country and even abroad by the media, the Prime Minister was able to learn about the children's request. The Minister of Youth went on national television to address the nation. He first recognized

that the situation of abandoned children was dramatic. He then promised the unfortunate youths a better life in the immediate and distant future. In Lubumbashi, the Governor had offered the association of underprivileged children (A.O.U.C) a large piece of land where, with the help of an international organization, a school of agriculture would be built and managed by the male religious community. The kids were put to work helping with the construction.

The (A.O.U.C) worked mostly well. It succeeded in fitting into families a number of girls and boys; some as adopted children, while others were taken into families as house helpers. In addition, the association set up reception centers in several townships where children could be cared for, fed and protected. All this thanks to the help of international organizations and some citizens of good will.

5 Conclusion

The main purpose of this study was to explore the lived experiences of youth living on the streets of Lubumbashi, a southern city of Katanga Province in the Democratic Republic of Congo (D.R.C). In *Quand les enfants crient misère*, Kayombo (2008) vocalises the troublesome destinies of children in the streets of Lubumbashi. The issue of waifs, which is generally swept under the carpet in African societies, is forthrightly addressed by Kayombo (2008) who points out the ins and outs of such an unsavoury social phenomenon. The street is described in the novel as a social converter, a social transformer through which a human ecology emerges and manifests itself in Lubumbashi. In so doing, the author takes the road of denunciation to paint the street as a mirror of a failing society that can even no longer guarantee its most vulnerable stratum the minimum for a humanly acceptable existence.

The novel is a great indictment on the African family system and values, and the neglect of African leadership respectively. As Darko (2003) observes, children who are churned into the streets come from families who ought to have shielded them from the vagaries of this world. Unfortunately, government has no enduring system or legislation to protect the children's right to a decent life or lacks the will to implement such laws where they exist.

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Conversation Analysis: Creation of Social Identity Among Ha Speakers

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Abstract

Social identity is a complex construct that is continually shaped and reshaped through interactions, including casual conversations. It is during these seemingly inconsequential exchanges that individuals negotiate and create their social identity, often subconsciously. In the discursive negotiations of the creation of social identity, various conversational features are employed. This paper explores the features that Ha speakers use to create social identities by adopting a qualitative approach with which it uses ethnographic design to collect the data. The data gathered were casual conversations. It qualitatively analysed the conversations captured from different contexts to find out how interactants use conversation as a resource to create their social identities. The findings of this paper include a range of interactional devices that Ha speakers employ to create their social identities. These include repair mechanisms, distribution of turns, turn length, code switching and code mixing, membership categorisation, and unfolding of the assumed silent great social identity. The paper demonstrates how interactional devices used in conversations are potential resources when the user of the language is socialised to use them intentionally to gain an advantage over the conversational counterpart. The paper recommends that, since the interactional devices are potential resources that can be used profitably to gain an advantage from the conversational counterpart or an audience, they should be exposed and interactively socialised to the members of the society from childhood.

Keywords: conversation analysis, social identity, Ha, social practice, conversation as a resource.

1 Introduction

Conversation is a form of interactive, spontaneous communication between two or more people who follow rules of etiquette (Clark 1996). Conversation can either be pragmatic or casual. Casual conversation, as defined functionally and in a way negatively by Eggins and Slade (1997), refers to talk that is not motivated by any clear pragmatic purpose. In the words of Levinson, quoted in Hakulinen (2009), conversation is the predominant kind of talk in which two or more participants freely alternate in speaking, which generally occurs outside specific institutional settings.

What all forms of conversation share, however, is the fact that it is through them that we, as human beings, manage our daily affairs and construct and make sense of our lives and activities. In this sense, Gardener (1999: 264) observes that

Ordinary conversation is the default version of the talk (and by implication perhaps of language too), and all other forms of talk-in-interaction are derived from ordinary conversation, and are; thus, culturally, and socially, restricted. For example, modes of talk in education, in law, in the media, and medicine, are likely to be derived from local (cultural) needs and contingencies, and adaptations of talk encompass these.

This observation by Gardner reveals the sense that, from a casual conversation, one can access the hidden treasure of beliefs, customs, and traditions of a particular language community. This is because even a person with whatever disability who can at least speak has an avenue to deposit their cultural intents into their language community reservoir.

In the scenario that other forms of talk in interaction can perform different functions of a language like the referential function, the directive function, the expressive function, the phatic function, the metalinguistic function, and the poetic function, Appel and Muysken (1987), this paper tries to present the view that casual conversation may be used as a resource to perform some social functions one of them being to create social identity. Conversation performs this by the use of different interactional features, referred to as fundamental structures by Far (2008).

Far (2008) worked on conversation. He made an analytical study of casual conversation to find out fundamental structures and notions in a talk-in-interaction. After analysing many conversations, he found that the fundamental structures and notions of a conversation include: turn-taking, overlap, repair, and discourse markers. The observations by Far underlie what Mazeland (2006) states when he defines conversation analysis,

Conversation analysis studies the methods participants orient to when they organize social action through talk. It investigates rules and practices from an interactional perspective and studies them by examining recordings of real-life interactions.

The social action practices referred to by Mazeland may refer to the discursive negotiations of creating social identities made by conversational interactants knowingly or unknowingly. Sacks et al (1974) also studied conversation extensively to examine the organization of turn-taking. The findings of their study presented a landmark contribution in the field of Conversation Analysis. They proposed a model for organising turn-taking organization in conversation, which is summarised below.

The model has two parts, a “turn-constructive component” and a “turn-allocational component.” A turn may be constructed from various syntactic units: it may, for instance, consist of a word, a phrase, a clause, or a sentence. Once an utterance is underway, it should be possible for hearers to guess which unit the speaker is using, and in this way, judge the utterance when it is complete. The first possible completion point of an utterance is called a “transition-relevance place,” since, when this point is reached, the turn is reallocated and may pass on to a new speaker.

The allocation of turn proceeds is as follows. The current speaker may, if he or she wishes, choose the next speaker by using his present utterance a “current-speaker-selects-next” technique, such as an addressed question. This method of allocating the turn has precedence over the others. If the current speaker does not use this option, the other participants may “self-select” by beginning utterances of their own, the first person to speak up acquiring the turn. Finally, if the other participants let this opportunity pass, the previous speaker may, if desired, take another turn. In this case, the same turn-allocation procedure occurs at the next transition-relevance place, until, eventually, the turn is transferred to another participant.

The turn-constructive and turn-allocational components constitute the basic system. In addition, however, Sacks et al. (1974) describe some “repair mechanisms” which come into operation when the basic system breaks down. The commonest problem is a multiple start during self-selection; this is repaired by the abortion of all but one of the overlapping utterances. Another problem is that the first person to speak up during self-selection may

preempt an utterance of higher priority. In such cases, “second-starter techniques” are used - in other words, the first speaker is interrupted.

The model was examined for its compatibility with a list of grossly observable facts about conversation. The results of the examination suggested that a model for turn-taking in conversation would be characterized as locally managed, partly administered, interactionally controlled, and sensitive to recipient design.

The study presented that a model should be capable of accommodating the following actualities, which they observed in any conversation.

- Speaker-change recurs, or at least occurs;
- Overwhelmingly, one party talks at a time;
- Occurrences of more than one speaker at a time are common, but brief;
- Transitions (from one turn to another) with no gap and no overlap are common. Together with transitions characterized by slight gaps or slight overlap, they make up the vast majority of transitions;
- Turn order is not fixed, but varies;
- Turn size is not fixed, but varies;
- The length of the conversation is not specified in advance;
- What participants say is not specified in advance;
- Relative distribution of turns is not specified in advance;
- The number of participants can vary;
- Talk can be continuous or discontinuous;
- Turn-allocation techniques are used. A current speaker may select a next speaker (as when he addresses a question to another party), or participants may self-select by starting to talk;
- Various “turn-constructural units” are employed; e.g., turns can be of just one word, or they can be sentential in length;
- Repair mechanisms exist for dealing with turn-taking errors and violations, if two participants find themselves talking at the same time, one of them will stop prematurely, thus repairing the trouble.

The works discussed above have revealed the efforts of scholars to investigate the features or structures of a conversation. And they have been presented thereof. This paper intends to look at how these structures are discursively used to negotiate for the creation of the desired social identities of the participants in conversations in light of the views by Eggins and Slade (1997: 6, 9) that: (a) Casual conversation is concerned with the joint construction of social reality and (b) In casual conversation we see language being used as a resource to negotiate social identity and interpersonal relations.

Therefore, because of the scholarly works discussed above, this paper strives to achieve the following two objectives.

- i. To find out the interactional features used in conversation to create social identities among Ha speakers;
- ii. To explore how the interactional features (observed in (i)) are used to create social identities in conversation among Ha speakers.

1.1 Ha language

Ha is a Bantu language spoken in Kigoma Region in Western Tanzania. It is classified by Guthrie (1971) under Rundi-Rwanda D 60 as one of the Great Lakes Bantu Languages or Lacustrine Bantu. Rwanda-Rundi D 60 comprises the following languages: Nyarwanda, Rundi, Shubi, Hangaza, Ha, and Vinza. It is one of the 135 living languages of Tanzania (Grimes & Grimes 2000). Ha language is closely related to other languages like Rundi (spoken in Burundi), Nyarwanda (spoken in Rwanda), and Hangaza (spoken in some areas of the Kagera Region of Tanzania). These four languages (Ha, Rundi, Nyarwanda, and Hangaza) are, sometimes, referred to as four dialects of the same language (Kimenyi 1978:1). According to Kimenyi (1978:1), as a single language, Ha would rank second, after Kiswahili, among the Bantu languages, concerning a number of speakers. However, the Ha speakers themselves consider Ha to be a language different from Rundi and Nyarwanda.

2 Theoretical framework

This paper was guided by the *Systemic Functional Linguistics: A Functional-semantic Interpretation of Conversation theory*. The theory was developed by M.A.K. Halliday in the U.K. during the 1960s (1973, 1975, 1978, 1994, and Halliday and Hasan 1985). An important influence of the approach to analysing casual conversation is based on the model of “language as social semiotic.” This theory offers the basic benefits for conversational analysis as presented by Eggins and Slade (1997: 47)

It theorizes the links between language and social life so that conversation can be approached as a way of doing social life. More specifically, casual conversation can be analysed as involving different linguistic patterns which both enact and construct dimensions of social identity and interpersonal relations.

The approach views language as a resource for making not just one meaning at a time, but several strands of meaning simultaneously. These simultaneous layers of meaning can be identified in linguistic units of all sizes: in the word, phrase, clause, sentence, and text. This means that a casual conversation is modelled as the simultaneous exchange of three types of meanings. These three types of meanings can be glossed as follows: ideational meanings, interpersonal meanings, and textual meanings.

As there are different strands of meanings being enacted in talk, the analyst needs to analyse the talk from different perspectives. Thus, different analytical techniques are used to uncover each strand of meaning. For example, to explore the ideational meaning in a text, the analyst focuses on patterns which encode the who, when, where, why, and how of a text, Eggins and Slade (1997: 49).

Therefore, a study of casual conversation can explore all three dimensions of casual talk. However, for theoretical reasons, this paper focuses on the analysis of interpersonal meanings in casual conversation. The paper offers the following two reasons for this focus. First, the paper stands to argue that the primary task of casual conversation is the negotiation of social identity and social relations. Thus, casual conversation is “driven” by interpersonal, rather than ideational or textual meanings.

Second, it is the open-ended, turn-taking organization of conversation that differentiates it from other linguistic activities (Sacks et al. 1974). This turn-by-turn structuring of

conversation is realized through interpersonal patterns of mood and conversational structure. Given this approach, therefore, conversational utterances in all the excerpts included in this paper will be analysed to find out how they shape social life in a way that the participants negotiate to create their social identities.

3 Research methodology

This paper used a qualitative research approach. It employed a qualitative research approach primarily because its main intention is to collect conversations of Ha speakers to determine how they use interactional features to construct their social reality. The paper also employed an ethnographic research design, which involves the study of real-life situations within their natural environment. Hence, the researcher observed people in the settings in which they live by participating in their day-to-day activities.

The design enabled the researcher, while living with the target community, to record naturally occurring conversational data of casual conversations from two purposively selected districts of the Kigoma Region: Kibondo and Kasulu. From the two districts naturally occurring casual conversations were recorded. Conversations were observed and recorded in four distinct domains, which were the friendship domain, economy domain, home domain, and business domain. These were obtained in different locations like homes, marketplaces, rest places, business centers and social ceremonies. The conversational occasions involved three contexts concerning sex: men only, women only, and men and women together engaged in conversation. From the context delineated above, five conversations were collected and have been used in this paper as follows: one conversation was used under the repair mechanism and distribution of number of turns, the two subsections of section four, and the remaining four conversations were used in the subsequent four subsections of section four. Because this method could not capture all the necessary information required for this paper, another method was used to supplement it. In this case, direct observation of participants in conversation was also used.

Data analysis was divided into three major phases. In the first phase, all the recorded data were transcribed. In the second phase, those parts of the excerpts that were identified to be relevant to be presented in the paper as supporting pieces of evidence were translated into English. In the third phase, the data were scrutinized to find out those interactional features that were used to create social identities among Ha speakers in casual conversations.

4 Findings

The findings revealed how conversation functions as a resource to negotiate the creation of social identity among Ha speakers. The concept of the creation of social identity as presented by Bauman and Briggs (1990) and Zimmerman and Wieder (1970) is a process that goes through three social phases. The first phase is presented by Bauman and Briggs (1990), who stipulate that social identity takes place in concrete and specific interactional occasions. It is also presented in other words by Zimmerman and Wieder (1970) that it entails “discursive work.” The second phase is also presented by Bauman and Briggs (1990) that which yields constellations of identities instead of individual or monolithic constructs. The last phase is also presented by Bauman and Briggs (1990) that it does not simply emanating from the individual,

but results from processes of negotiation. Having analysed the data, the interactional features that were found to underlie the process are presented and discussed.

4.1 Repair mechanism

Repair mechanism is a term used in conversational analysis and discourse analysis to refer to the attempt made by participants in a conversation to make good or real and imagined deficiency in the interaction (Crystal 1985). Schegloff et al. (1977) define repair as a mechanism dealing with problems concerning speaking, hearing, and understanding in talk-in-interactions. And Schiffrin (1987) defines repair as a speech activity during which speakers locate and replace a prior information unit. Because they focus on prior information, repairs achieve information transitions anaphorically (forcing speakers to adjust their orientation to what has been said before and respond to it in upcoming talks). She, further, argues that almost anything that anyone says is subjected to repair either by the speaker himself or herself or by the listener.

The repair mechanism as an interactional feature is used to create social identity in its different forms, such as corrections, clarifications, restatements, and emphases. Parts of conversations containing repair works are incorporated in this section to substantiate how a conversation is used by participants as a resource to create social identity among the interactants.

Example:

The conversation took place in a public bar. The participants included a young boy, Funzi, who is a primary school leaver, his friend Toma, and their former primary school teacher. The bar attendant also participated in the conversation.

In the exchange below, Funzi and his friend Toma met their former primary school teacher. Funzi quickly started to befriend him. He bought some local beer and welcomed him to join them. His teacher joined them. From this new relationship that Funzi has achieved, Funzi wants to be given the respect that is equivalent to what is rendered by the bar attendant to his former primary school teacher, a government employee. This is what it means when he is repeatedly demanding respect in the exchange below.

1. Funzi: *ngomb i'heshima.*

I need respect.

2. Bar attendant: *ijoki.*

You are joking.

3. Funzi: *ngomb i'heshima... ijoki?*

I need respect. How can I be joking?

I need respect is an utterance made by one of the interlocutors in a conversation with four participants held in a public bar. Conversation, as a social practice and as a resource, is used by the conversationalist, Funzi, to demand a social attribute that translates itself into a particular social identity. By making such a demand, and if the demand receives a positive response, the participant in that way would have created a social identity. Funzi insists upon his demand by employing an interactional feature, which involves repetition, that is a repair mechanism. By

repeating move number 1 as part of move number 3, the conversationalist employs repair work by repeating an utterance he had made earlier and, thereby, calls for the attention of the addressee and of other participants to pay respect to him. To hammer his demand, he adds another utterance saying, *How can I be joking?* All these efforts of negotiations are made to achieve respect, a matter of social reality. This instance, therefore, is a repair mechanism exercise used in conversation to create social reality, which is a respectful social identity. In another instance, Funzi creates another social reality as presented below.

4. Funzi: *chogukora. Tumanze twirekodi... au manze nkwereke ni memori kadi... ati yivuzwaha ni memori kadi mpiga numuziki... we kowagomba... il u'chumenya ngo ni simu... ni vipi. Irekiyo irerekana ni beteri hano?*

What to do. Let's first record ourselves... or let me first show you a memory card... where it is placed in playing music... however you like... So that you understand whether this is a cell phone... or not. Does the radio show the battery here (pointing at the screen)?

5. Chenda: *hariri i'zerekana (ubutwengo) ha ha ha*
Some do show [laughter] ha ha ha

6. Funzi: *yande yerekana... yande yerekana idyo beteri?*
Whose shows... whose shows a battery?

In the above exchange, which is made up of the three moves, 4, 5, and 6, the manifestations of the creation of social identity are vibrantly observed. In move number 4, Funzi presents himself as a rich man by owning a very special and expensive cell phone. He presents himself as more knowledgeable than others in the conversation. He behaves in a way that shows that he belongs to a different class than the rest of the participants. He does all this by exposing or revealing things he assumes that others do not know. He, boastfully, narrates about the different special functions of his peculiar cell phone. He also brags about various other gadgets that could be used together with the phone. He explains all these to inform his assumed ignorant counterparts that he has a cell phone. In the course of the exchange, he makes a clear demarcation that he owns something that others could not own, and in doing so, he, socially, upscales himself from other conversationalists and locates himself in an enviable position than others.

When Chenda, in move number 5, remarks that even other phones display similar functions in the manner as his, for example, displaying the battery functionalities, Funzi strongly refutes the proposition by demanding evidence in move number 6 by using an interactional feature, a repair mechanism made by repetition, *whose shows? Whose shows a battery?* With this, he intends to establish his superior social position, that he is the only one who owns such a cell phone, displaying his material wealth in the course of the exchange. Here, he discursively negotiates to create an affluent social identity. The negotiations made by Funzi attest the argument made by Benwell & Stokoe (2010) that social identity is “located not in the private realms of cognition, emotion and experience, but in the public realms of discourse, interaction and other semiotic systems of meaning making,” while it is “actively, ongoingly, dynamically constructed, rather than reflected, in talk and texts of all kind.”

4.2 Distribution of the number of turns

The investigation of the interaction order, as a central site for the construction of identities, provides a significant site of analysis and area of reflection in the conversational data. Analysis of interactional processes is also based on a fundamental principle of intersubjectivity that allows identities to be achieved and built through reciprocal moves between interactants (Defina et al. 2006). Interactants can project identifications or rejections towards their partners through cooperative or uncooperative management of conversation (ibid.). They can also confirm and fine-tune local identities that place them in relationships with others, such as “expert” versus “novice” through the use of taking turns frequently more than others (ibid.). The argument made by Defina et al. (2006) that interactants can project identifications or rejections towards their partners through cooperative or uncooperative management of conversation is attested in the data presented below as follows: in this data, the participant, Funzi, projects himself in this scenario by taking more turns than other participants. He frequently self-selects to become the current speaker. In doing so, he manages to make more turns than other participants as it is presented in the table below.

Table 1: Distribution of Number of Turns

Name of a participant	Number of turns	Percentage
Funzi	56	48.7
Bar attendant	30	26.08
Limu	20	17.3
Chanda	9	7.82
Total	115	100

As a result of taking more turns than others, Funzi manages to make other participants have a particular image (social identity) of him. The social identity that Funzi manages to make is that he has money, and, therefore, he can even offer his former primary school teacher a beer. He achieves this by using conversation, a social practice as a resource of negotiation in discourse. This was done in moves 7, 8, and 9.

Example:

7. Funzi: *ngugura... nawe uragahangayikira... ngotunywe... mm... (long pause) halafu mwalimu wewe waranfundishije ... ugirase ngo jewe sinkhumenya... waranfundishije ... nayidya siku walanguliy u'bhubgabga utamenya kwamba nuyu mwanafunzi wondafundishije... wewe yichara kwa vire unywa yino nzoga...*

That you buy... you also suffer to get it... let's drink... mm... (long pause) you, also, taught me teacher... you think I do not know you... you taught me. And on that day, you bought me some rice without knowing that this is the pupil I taught... please sit, after all, you take this beer.

In the above move, Funzi projects his social identity by showing his positive recognition towards people who once did good things to him and how he handles them with respect and rewards them with great honour. That is what he does to his former primary school teacher.

8. Funzi: *wagomb u'girenthe? sasa ngaha tugomba duhe bga miya tatu.*

What did you want to do? Now here we want you to give us (local beer) of three hundred.

In this move, once again, Funzi projects his monetary ability as an insignia of his social identity. With his financial ability, he orders local beer for three hundred, which he offers to his former teacher and his colleagues in the conversational group. To do this is to tell his colleagues that he has money and he can offer them drinks. This is how he wants other participants in the conversational group to understand and recognize him.

9. Funzi: *tunywa kwete se! kwili jioni wonywa kwete? Nakose wakaguz i'wande?*

Do we drink kwete! (a kind of local beer) ... how can you take kwete in the evening? And where did you buy that (beer)?

In all the above moves, Funzi maintains his position of creating once again an affluent social identity when he says that he cannot take Kwete, a local beer of low quality. He also maintains that someone cannot take such a local beer, especially when it is in the evening. The observed discussive negotiations by Funzi affirm the views presented by Norton (1995; 1997) that social identity is a construction and negotiation of "a sense of self" in social relations mediated by language. Therefore, casual conversation is not merely an action of exchanging information with the interlocutors; more significantly, it is also a space to constantly organise and reorganise a sense of "who I am" and "how I relate to the social world."

4.3 Turn length

According to Sacks et al. (1974), turn size is not fixed, but varies. In this view, turn length is used to create social identity. To achieve this, conversationalists lengthen the turn; in other words, they dominate the conversations. They do so to capture the audience's attention for a long duration. In that way, they use the opportunity to express all their potential and abilities on issues or matters under discussion so that their abilities are highly elevated to the apex of the social ladder. In this way, the information about them and their deeds is seen by every participant in the conversation, and the society as a result. This strategy is extensively used in the following data given below.

Example:

In this data, the participant Amoni succeeded in making the longest turns among the rest of the other participants in the conversation. This enabled him to discursively describe himself as a well-informed and long-experienced driver. The moves presented below substantiate this claim.

10. Amoni: *(naya hand a'bonye)[...] bavuze ngo ni bureki yanse. Yarikuruku [...] hadya nyene, kuri ridya dya kwanza. Yariguch a'yipiga hasi kudya nyene. Harikwononeka bike.*

[...] they said it was the break that failed. He was supposed to [...] right there [...] at the first (corner). He was supposed to fall it down right there. Few things would be damaged.

In this move (10), Amoni uses the length of the turn as a conversational strategy to give himself enough time to air out his knowledge and his long experience of driving. He explains how the driver failed. He further explains what the driver would have done to avoid or minimise the damage to the materials that were in the vehicle. He says that the driver was supposed to stop the vehicle right at the first corner. He also says that in doing so, few materials would have been destroyed. In saying so, he is, discursively, negotiating to make sure that it is well known to other participants that he is much more knowledgeable than other participants in the conversation. In that way, Amoni is creating himself a well-informed social identity.

11. Amoni: *karatse nyene [...] kuk u'kab u'dashobora gufatish u'kuguru ukach u'hagarar a'ho nyene [...] Ntutambuke nintambuko na zibiri chupig a'honyene.*
 If it (the vehicle) gets angry [...] Because if you cannot hold with a leg so that you stop right there [...] Don't make even two steps. Beat it (fall the vehicle down) right there.

In this move (11), Amoni continues to give his skillful opinions to other participants in the conversation. In the course of rendering his skillful opinions to other conversational participants, he discloses his knowledge of driving to other participants. He explains by giving details of the way the driver would have done it. He says that, if he could not do it (brake) with a leg and stop right there, as he was not supposed to move even a single step further, he was supposed to stop the vehicle right there to avoid severe damage to the vehicle and the contents in it. In the course of Amoni giving all these explanations, he is, actually, discursively negotiating for himself a well-informed (knowledgeable) social identity.

12. Amoni: *Nyomba wumv u'shoboye kugira, kandamiza nifure, nibureki, ukamate hende bureki, usubire wuzuz u'bund u'bupepo. Ukaba nah u'hay u'rayuba, uhay u'rayuba na maisha, wagiye.*
 If you think you can do it, press the break, the break. Hold the hand break, and once again fill the air. If at all you are playing, you are playing with life. You are gone.

Amoni (12) continues to make a long turn. He continues to present his knowledge and skills about driving with great clarity and authority. He presented detailed and informative instructions about what was supposed to be done. Stage by stage, he explains what would be the rescue procedure of the vehicle. Finally, he makes a very strong warning. He starts by saying, "*If you think you can do.*" This piece of utterance, in this conversation, carries very serious and strong advice to his fellow participants in the conversation. He utters this to mean "If you think you can save your life, it is the only moment you can serve it." He goes on to explain step by step what the driver had to do to rescue himself. He speaks with emphasis, which is marked by a repetition of the words, "*Press the break, the break.*" He continues with another step that the driver had to hold the handbrake and then fill the air once again. Lastly, he makes a strong warning saying, "*If at all you are playing, you are playing with your life. You are gone.*" These explanations above by Amoni bear witness to what, normally, talking accomplishes in people's lives and society at large, and it also, shows how things get done through language use. And this is what Goffman (1959) means when he asserts that casual conversations are integral to the process of the creation of social identity, as they allow individuals to present themselves in particular ways and negotiate their social identities.

Therefore, in saying so, Amoni discursively negotiates to create himself a well-experienced and highly educated in the field of driving.

4.4 Code switching and code mixing

Code-switching is the mixing of words, phrases, and sentences from two distinct grammatical (sub) systems across sentence boundaries within the same speech event... code-mixing is the embedding of various linguistic units such as affixes (bound morphemes), words (unbound morphemes), phrases and clauses from a co-operative activity where the participants, to infer what is intended, must reconcile what they hear with what they understand, (Bokamba quoted in Ayeomoni 2006: 91). And Gumperz (quoted in Romaine 1995) defines code-switching as the juxtaposition within the same speech exchange of passages of speech belonging to two different grammatical systems or sub-systems.

For the participants to code-switch or code-mix, several social factors have varied pragmatic meanings. The approach to code-switching and code-mixing as proposed by Appel and Muysken (1987) acknowledges six functions: (i) the referential function, (ii) the directive function, (iii) the expressive function, (iv) the phatic function, (v) metalinguistic function, and (vi) poetic function.

From the above-presented motivations by Appel and Muysken (1987), this paper finds relevant the motivation number (iii), which is the “expressive function” for social identity creation. This paper finds it appropriate to explain how participants in conversation among Ha speakers create their social identity. The motivations are presented below, showing how the participants use them to achieve their social ends.

Example:

The recording was made among women only. The participants were discussing a school child who was bewitched because of his very good academic performance. The conversation reveals how witchcraft beliefs hinder varied aspects of human development.

13. Shamsa: *Kahama, nangwe sikahama? Baramuroze kwa ajiri yu bgenge chane kw i'shule. Yamaze keshi?*

Kahama, is it not Kahama? They bewitched him because he was very intelligent at school. Has he completed the school on time?

14. Tina: *amara uwu mwaka wuza.*

He will complete in the next year.

15. Shamsa: *kila mwaka kwa nini anakuwa namba moja? Kila mwaka. Kila muhula, kila muhula.*

Why does he become the first every year? Every year. Every term, every term.

16. Tina: *kwa hiyo bamuboney u'wivu relo.*

Therefore, they were jealous of him.

17. Shamsa: *na sewage ni hendisamu. [...] Yan i'yoshule yabu itora babana bubgenge gusa, nibo bagwar i'vyo.*

Even his father is handsome. [...] it means their school selects intelligent children only. Those are the ones who, normally, suffer from such problems.

18. Tina: *mmm.*

Yes.

19. Shamsa: *asilimia uwufata namba moja niw a'gwar i'vyo, na bator u'wuri lasaba ni lasita.*

A large percentage of those who suffer from such problems are those who get number one positions and take those in standard seven and six.

In this piece of conversation, Shamsa is a food seller at the bus stop while Tina is a fruit seller. The conversation begins in Ha language, but as the conversation proceeds, Shamsa (13) mixes it with Swahili language when she uses the words “*kwa ajili [...] shule.*” In doing so, Shamsa shows that she can also speak Swahili; hence, she does not belong to the class of Tina. When Tina responds (14), she does not any struggle. She responds in the Ha language. But when Shamsa takes the turn again, she makes a further step. While in (13) Shamsa had code-mixed, this time she completely code-switched to Swahili. She makes the whole utterance (15) in Swahili. With this, she presents herself as a fluent Swahili speaker. In doing so, Shamsa creates herself a Swahili-speaking social identity. From this point, Tina decides to inform her counterpart that she also speaks Swahili. She does this by using the words “*kwa hiyo [...] wivu*” in (16). By those words, she declares that she belongs to the class of Swahili speakers and, therefore, belongs to the same class as Shamsa. When Shamsa sees this, she rejects being the same status as Tina; she takes a further step, which is to tell Tina that they don't belong to the same class. In (17), Shamsa mixes Ha with the English word “*handsome.*” In switching to English words, Shamsa informs Tina that she also speaks English, and she, therefore, belongs to the class of people who speak English; the assumed educated people and people with good administrative positions in the government. Hence, she creates for himself an educated and highly regarded class social identity.

From code-switching and code-mixing, as a conversational strategy, the study finds out that in casual conversation, participants among Ha speakers, discursively, negotiate to create their social identities as Appel and Muysken (1987) state that, in the case of an expressive function, the speaker switches code to express their “mixed identity.” More particularly, to Ha speakers, a participant discursively negotiates to see himself or herself at the apex of the social ladder. This is evidenced by what Shamsa accomplishes when she switches from Ha to Swahili in the first place, and then, from Swahili to English. This is what Gee (2014) underscores: he argues that discourses are ways of being in the world that are expressed through language and other semiotic resources. He further presents that casual conversations are arenas where multiple discourses intersect, and individuals navigate these discourses to negotiate their identities. Through casual talk, people align themselves with particular social groups, roles, and practices, which help them to create their social identities.

4.5 Membership categorisation

Membership categorisation refers to a conversationalist's decision to identify himself with a person with a great reputation. Membership categorisation focuses on the recognizability of people as certain sorts of people or, more specifically, people as certain sorts of members of

society, and how this recognizability is a resource for members in their dealings with each other. There are several social groups that people would desire to identify with. The groups include the following: the ruling class, rich people, businesspeople, government employees, educated people, and town dwellers.

Example:

The recording was made at a business centre. The participants included customers who had gone shopping.

20. Ndalú: *ntya menya kuhay u'mbaz i'porojo.*
By now, I know that you are making a joke.

21. Rūshā: *kwa hiyo ni porojo?*
So it's a joke?

22. Ndalú: *mm [...] ndokwich u'womuhanga [...] ndagusekure [...]*
mm [...] I can sacrifice (suicide bombing) myself [...] and beat you

23. Rūshā: *usekurinkoni jewe [...] aha ni baa yofungwa. Je simpōra shima gushindwa [...] aramagumi ndokudunda kira muntu asanga arikiyobherane. Je [...]*
Beating me with a stick (fimbo) [...] even all the shops can get closed. I never like being defeated [...] I can give you fists until you become shapeless. I [...]

24. Ndalú: *ndokwitow u'muhanga nyene.*
I can, really, sacrifice (suicide bombing) myself.

25. Rūshā: *witow u'muhanga nyene?*
Sacrifice (suicide bombing) yourself?

26. Ndalú: *ee [...] iwawe.*
Yes [...] to you.

The data given above demonstrates how membership categorisation is used to create social identity by means of a participant in a conversation struggling to attach and identify himself or herself with a member or a social group of certain characteristics.

In the data given, the participant, **Ndalú**, associates and identifies with suicide bombers. Ndalú knows very well how suicide bombers are a great threat in countries where such military technique is used. The evils of suicide bombers are known even outside those countries. No person would like to even hear about such happening. With this understanding, **Ndalú** (22) said, "*mm [...] I can sacrifice (commit suicide bombing) myself [...] and beat you.*" His association and identification with the suicide bombers, a group of people who are ready to lose their lives to, destructively, kill their enemies is the use of membership categorisation, a conversational strategy. By the repetition, he makes in (24) when he says again, "*I can sacrifice (commit suicide bombing) myself,*" **Ndalú** emphasizes his decision to kill himself too, destructively, kill the participant **Rūshā**, if his money is not paid. With this emphasis on association and identification, he wants to tell the participant, **Rūshā**, that there is no way he could tolerate not being paid money for his beer. He wants to say that he could do anything

disastrous to get his money paid. With his association and identification, **Ndalu** creates a suicide-bombing social identity.

4.6 Unfolding the Assumed Silent Great Social Identity

This is another conversational technique that conversationalists use to create their social identity. With this technique, the participant narrates different events or experiences that prove him or her a person of great social respect before the public or a gathering.

Example:

27. Rama: [...] *Nuwundi mumsi haza habh u'mubhara hariya lelo. Wamubhala [...] bhalatulalika [...] bhatum u'wonyene. Ulabgila na msaza waw a'ze. Atee. Alambgil a'ti bhamam i'dya, bhalobh a'bhalinulubanza. yarahay a'bhatizwa [...] kwi ara si [...] wuya mama. Araz a'tulinumubhara [...] mama waw a'hayabhatizwa. Nthee ndoza. Bhalibhitangira bhano kugenda [...] bhazabhahaye bhabhabhaza [...] nthyo walabgiye kaka wawe? Atee ndaramubgiye. None kwataraza? Naw a'kabhaza kaka wawe wahe? Uwo bhagamba bhahaye bhaghamba nde? Bhakamuziganya nyene [...] nthyo wewe waramubgiye wewe? Ee bhaga ndaraviye [...] ndamubgira. Yaani ukabhon a'taje. Ubgo bgomuza mugira bgubhurandage [...] ataje urobhutamubgiye. Nanj u'womumsi nvuze nkhasibha ndobha ndononye. nibhasekeli ndikunzira*

[...] And on the other day, there was a feast there. That feast [...] they invited us [...] they sent the same person (my sister) to tell, also, your brother to come. She responded, yes. She came to inform me that our mothers would be having a feast. She was being baptised in the arasi, [RC - Roman Catholic][...] my mother. She came and said, "We have a feast. Your mother is being baptised." I said "I will come." They went there early. They (parents) had started asking her (my sisters) "Did you tell your brother." She responded, "Yes I told him." They wanted to know why he didn't come. Then, he (my brother-in-law) asked, "Which brother of yours?" The one they are talking about. Whom are they talking about? They (parents) asked her over and over again. Did you tell him? She responded, I informed [...] I told him. If he does not come, the way you behave is as if you don't have a brain [...] if he doesn't come, it means you didn't tell him. And on that day I said if I missed, I would have destroyed the party. I rode, slowly, the bicycle on the way to the party.

Rama in (27) continues to relate by giving all the details of the event which, in the course of his life, gave him great social respect and lifted him to the pinnacle of the social ladder, and, hence, he was regarded as a person of great respect among people of his society. He narrates how he was invited to the feast when his mother was being baptised in the Roman Catholic faith, "*They sent the same person (my sister), tell also your brother to come. [...] She was being baptised in the arasi, [RC - Roman Catholic] ...*" Rama explains, also, how they started to ask his sister if she had informed him. When they saw that he was not appearing at the feast, *they (the parents) started to ask her "Did you tell your brother."* They continued to ask if she had informed me. "*They (the parents) asked her over and over again. Did you tell him? [...] If he does not come, the way you behave as if you don't have a brain [...] if he doesn't come, it means you didn't tell him.*"

He also tells how his brother-in-law, inquisitively, wanted to know the person all the gathering was waiting for to start the celebrations. The explanations given by Rama's sister to

her husband show that there was a very important person whose arrival determined the beginning and value of the celebrations. This is illustrated by different instances made by the parents in a way that they were constantly asking if he was informed.

Rama, therefore, explains all these to show his fellow participants in a conversation the way he received with great respect on that particular event. He narrates events with expectations of receiving the same from those participants.

28. Rama: *none wa mama azagamba [...] muhaye mushangiliy u'wahe? Wakaka agiy a'za [...] wamuhung a'raje? Ate [...] ndashimye. Nagahundu (vigeregere) kavugwa [...] (vigeregere) ngize ee [...] agize ee! twalidushitishizwe nuwu nyene mpaka shike [...] ati wewe wabhona ngendayoga ngosikaka. ni kaka. Ee uwu lelo atangula nugutinya lelo [...] agize muza mwendeshwa ntha nyene [...] mwakeye mwakeye mwakeye [...] mwalaye twalaye [...] at mwayitangiye [...] ee twajekale. Mm [...] ahayeyisaliza*

Then, my mother asked, "Whom are you applauding?" Our brother has arrived. The mother asked, "Has that son arrived?" They replied, yes. The mother responded, "Thanks a lot." A great cheer was heard with various noises of joy. I was astonished. My brother-in-law was, also, astonished saying, "who made us not to start the feast until he arrived?" The sister told her husband, "You saw me going there. You thought he is not my brother. He is my brother." The brother-in-law started fearing. The brother-in-law told his wife, "You are dictated by him."

Good morning! Good morning! Good morning... how did you sleep? We slept well. Did you arrive very early? The brother-in-law responded, "Yes we came very early," mm... with great pretense.

In (28), the last piece of evidence but not the least in elaborating on the event that gave Rama great respect in his society, Rama explains how there was a great cheer when he arrived at his parents' home. He reports that his sisters shouted and, then, his mother wanted to know what was happening. When they told her that their brother had arrived, the mother shouted, "*Thanks a lot.*" Rama, further, says that he, himself, was astonished and his brother-in-law was also astonished, saying, "*Is this the one who made us not to start the feast until he arrived?*" Rama's sister tells her astonished husband, "*You saw me going there. You thought he is not my brother. He is my brother.*" Her husband was greatly afraid. Certainly, the event and the explanations showed the great position of Rama in his clan that it is of great respect. For that reason, therefore, Rama proudly narrates this event to these participants because it moved him up the social ladder. As he narrates, once again, the event, he wants to receive the same respect he received when the event happened for the first time. In this way, he creates a great respect for social identity.

5 Conclusion

This paper has established by observations and arguments that participants in different conversations could create social identities through the resourceful use of different interactional features. The interactional features used, according to the available data, are as follows: the first one is repair work, which functions in forms of repetitions, corrections, clarifications, restatements, and emphases. This means that when people are engaged in conversation, a

participant would now and then, whether consciously or unconsciously, either repeat, correct, clarify, restate, or emphasise a particular utterance, in doing so the participant would end up creating a particular social reality. The second feature is the distribution of the number of turns. This feature accomplishes the task of creating social identity by taking more turns than the other participants in conversation. The third feature is turn length. This feature is used by the participant to create a social identity by the means of holding the current speaker's turn for a longer duration than other participants. Code-switching and code-mixing are the fourth feature that is also used to create social identity. This feature is used when a speaker switches code to express his or her mixed identity. A speaker, discursively, negotiates to see himself or herself at the apex of the social ladder in a he or she may switch from an ethnic to a national language, for example, and then to a foreign language. The fifth feature or interactional device is membership categorisation. This device is used by participants in conversation by identifying themselves with persons who are vested with a great reputation in society. People with great reputations in a society may include, for example, political figures, CEOs of famous companies, very rich persons, and others. The last device or feature observed in creating social identity is the unfolding of the assumed silent great social identity. With this device, the participant in a conversation narrates different events or experiences that gave him or her respect in the past. The participant narrates events that proved great social respect before the public or gathering so that the current addressees may offer him the same respect with reference to the past. Because of all the social identities created, it was also found that whatever the interactional features used, the outcomes of the discursive negotiations have been, always, the same. The outcomes have been that the participant, who would succeed in creating his or her social identity among other participants, would invariably be successful at the expense of other participants' social identities. His or her success would always result in unequal relationships with other participants. In other words, the consequences of discursive negotiations would be of asymmetrical relationship between the successful participant and the rest of the participants in the conversation. These findings attest to the findings of Zimmerman and West (1975) who in their work titled "Sex Roles, Interruptions and Silences in Conversation" found and reported that males assert an asymmetrical right to control topics and do so with evident repercussions that men deny equal status to women as conversational partners concerning rights to the full utilisation of their turn and support for the development of topics.

It was also found during the analysis that, turn-length conversational strategy has provided the political discourses with their roots and sustenance. This is for two reasons. Firstly, the turn-length strategy rarely allows other participants to speak and is a preferred strategy for dominance. Secondly, because the turn-length strategy intends to dominate the current speaker's position for a long duration to air out the best of his or her potentialities so that the other participants or the addressees will accept him or her as somebody with a different and peculiar social identity. This is also done for the speaker-politician to grab a chance to address the audience for a similar purpose of selling his or her best potential so that the audience will accept him. Therefore, given the similar intents of the turn length strategy in casual conversation and political campaigns, this paper states that the turn length strategy in casual conversation is a default form of political campaign.

Further, it was found in this paper that citing sources in academic writings draws on and gets its roots from membership categorisation conversational strategy. This is because the purpose of membership categorisation as a conversational strategy is that the participant in a conversation seeks to identify himself or herself with people with great reputations; people who are certain sorts of people or people who are certain sorts of members of the society so that the

participant may be identified along with the social status of that particular person. This purpose is identical to that of citing sources in academia, with which the writer seeks to justify his or her argument by referring to other renowned academics or researchers in that particular field. Given the similar intents of these two different discourses, this paper again asserts that the membership categorisation conversational strategy is a default form of citing sources in academia. This assertion is affirmed by Gardener (1999: 264) when he states that ordinary conversation is the default version of talk and that all other forms of talk-in-interaction are derived from ordinary conversation, and are, thus, culturally and socially restricted. For example, modes of talk in education, in law, in the media, and in medicine are likely to be derived from local (cultural) forms of talk-in-interactions.

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Rhetorical Evaluation of Vladimir Putin's "Declaration of War on Ukraine"

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Abstract

This article critically examines Vladimir Putin's "Declaration of War on Ukraine" using Reisigl and Wodak's Discourse-Historical Approach (DHA) to explore how Putin employs rhetorical strategies to legitimize the war against Ukraine. The findings reveal that Putin strategically uses nomination, predication, argumentation, perspectivization, and intensification strategies to construct an ideologically polarized geopolitical reality and justify the conflict. He primarily relies on building a leadership ethos, constructing an enemy identity for Ukraine and NATO, and framing the war as a "Special Military Operation." This research contributes to a broader understanding of how politicians use language to shape public perception and legitimacy.

Keywords: Russo-Ukraine war, Vladimir Putin, rhetoric of war, discourse historical approach, just war.

1 Introduction

There could be several political and ideological reasons behind the outbreak of war. However, there is certainly a specific type of language at work behind conceiving, initiating, perpetuating, and resolving wars (Nnamdi-Eruchalu 2013: 93). Skilled war orators use a specific type of language, which is what Silberstein (2002) calls "words of war," to legitimize war and garner public and political support. Through the strategic selection of words, orators discursively shape a pro-war public understanding of the political environment. For this, they often use "the cluster of binary oppositions" (Ivie 1980: 283) to construct a positive-self and negative-other phenomenon. Such "ideological polarization" (Oddo 2011: 289) diminishes the audience's feelings of guilt for any kind of violence against the adversary (Fisher and O'Mara 2023). In other words, such discursive construction of national identities serves as a guide for the audience to form opinions and attitudes towards the adversary. Therefore, it is essential that consumers of such discourses should be aware of the manipulative power of the rhetoric of war so that they become resistant and sceptical of such deceptive and moving speeches and are not led into wars or any other kind of violence hatched and executed by politicians.

Currently, the world is undergoing the Russia vs. Ukraine war, apparently an intractable issue for the international community. The Russo-Ukraine conflict began after Ukrainian President Viktor Yanukovich decided not to sign the Association Agreement with the European Union (EU) in November 2013, which led to violent Euromaidan protests and his eventual expulsion from the office on February 22, 2014 (Kofman et al. 2017: 1-5; Walker 2023: 4-6). Subsequently, in late February 2014, Russia annexed Crimea through a covert military operation (Kofman et al. 2017: 1-5). Since then, Ukraine has experienced significant political upheavals, including the outbreak of the pro-Russian separatist movement, which led to violent conflict and the secession of Crimea and Sevastopol (Walker 2023: 4-5). The ongoing political tension between Ukraine and Russia escalated after Putin declared war against Ukraine on 24 February 2022, leading to a violent invasion of Ukraine. According to the reports available, as of now, the war has killed or seriously injured roughly one million people (One Million Are Now).

During this period, Vladimir Putin delivered many speeches for initiating, executing, and perpetuating the war. This article critically examines Vladimir Putin's Declaration of War on Ukraine to understand how he leverages rhetorical skills to justify the war. The research contributes to our broader understanding of how political leaders use language to shape public perception and justify devastating actions like war.

2 Methodology and Framework

For the current article, an English translation of Vladimir Putin's Declaration of War on Ukraine has been used. This speech was delivered on February 24, 2022, to announce a "special military operation" against Ukraine. The speech has been analysed for the rhetorical strategies Putin employed to discursively construct a pro-war narrative and persuade his fellow countrymen to accept his version of socio-political reality. For ease of analysis, the speech has been divided into sentences (S) and examined for discursive and rhetorical strategies, following Reisigl and Wodak (2001) Discourse Historical Approach (DHA).

DHA is one of the prominent tools of Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) that focuses on exposing the implicit discursive strategies used in creating dominating discourses involved in social injustices and asymmetric power relations and dismantling hegemonic discourses by demystifying ideologies (Reisigl and Wodak 2001: 32; Meyer 2001: 31). For a comprehensive analysis, researcher needs to reconstruct the context of the piece of discourse by integrating "available knowledge about the historical sources and the background of the social and political fields in which discursive 'events' are embedded" (Reisigl and Wodak 2001: 35).

DHA is a "flexible" yet systematic tool of CDA (Reisigl 2017: 47). It analyses a text in three major steps: first, topics are identified; second, discursive strategies are studied; finally, rhetorical or linguistic devices are identified. For this study, I have relied upon the notion that powerful people, through five discursive strategies, discursively create their versions of reality to legitimize their power and actions. These strategies are nomination, predication, argumentation, perspectivization, and intensification/mitigation.

2.1 Nomination Strategy

The nomination strategy is related to naming people, events, and phenomena. It is "the most elementary form of linguistic and rhetorical discrimination" through which powerful people identify social actors or actions "linguistically by naming them derogatorily, debasingly or vituperatively" (Reisigl and Wodak 2001: 45). Speakers use various linguistic devices, such as metonymies, metaphors, and synecdoche to identify "Self" and "Other" strategically (ibid.: 45-47).

2.2 Predication Strategy

After identifying or naming social actors, actions, and events, speakers use predication strategies to attribute corresponding stereotypical, evaluative attributions of negative and positive traits in the linguistic form of implicit or explicit predicates (Reisigl and Wodak 2001: 45). To assign qualities to social actors or actions, speakers might strategically use explicit linguistic devices such as adjectives, relative clauses, prepositional phrases, infinitive clauses, pronouns, and implicit semantic devices like presuppositions and implicatures.

2.3 Argumentation Strategy

Argumentation strategies are used to justify the positive or negative presentations of the selected social actors and/or actions. The term “social actors” has been used to refer to individuals and organizations involved in the event in question. This strategy functions as verbal coercion to manipulate rather than persuade people. Prowess war orators often use topoi as argumentation strategies. Topoi are “the content-related warrants or ‘conclusion rules’ that connect the argument or arguments with the conclusion and the claim” (Reisigl and Wodak 2001: 75). In other terms, they function “as reservoirs of generalised key ideas from which specific statements or arguments can be generated” (Richards et al. 1993). The most frequently used topoi in the rhetoric of war are:

- i. Topos of definition/name-interpretation: “If an action, a thing or a person (group of persons) is named/designated (as) X, the action, thing or person (group of persons) carries or should carry the qualities/traits/attributes contained in the (literal) meaning of X.”
- ii. Topos of threat/danger: “If there are specific dangers and threats, one should do something against them.”
- iii. Topos of responsibility: If a person is responsible for solving specific problems, he/she should resolve them.
- iv. Topos of history: “History teaches that specific actions have specific consequences; one should perform or omit a specific action in a specific situation (allegedly) comparable with the historical example referred to.”
- v. Topos of abuse: “If a right or an offer for help is abused, the right should be changed, or the help should be withdrawn, or measures against the abuse should be taken.”
(Reisigl and Wodak 2001: 75-77)

2.4 Perspectivization Strategy

Speakers use the perspectivization strategy “express their involvement in discourse and position their point of view in the discursive flux” (Reisigl and Wodak 2001: 85). Although Reisigl and Wodak identify a few specific perspectivization strategies, it has been observed that all five strategies expose the speaker's perspective and point of view concerning a discursive event.

2.5 Intensification Strategy

Intensification strategies are often employed to modify the illocutionary force of an utterance. It is “applied to qualify and modify the epistemic status of a proposition, the degree of certainty, and to modify the speakers’ or writers’ expressiveness as well as the persuasive impact on the hearers and readers” (Reisigl and Wodak 2001: 81). Linguistic devices, such as emotive metaphors, emotionally charged words, and hyperboles, are often used as intensification strategies.

3 Analysis and Discussion

A close reading of the speech reveals that Putin used numerous manipulative rhetorical strategies to garner public support and legitimize the war against Ukraine. The most persistent discursive strategies are the construction of a positive self-identity and a negative-other identity. Within this ideological framework, he makes three recurring rhetorical moves: (1) building a wartime leadership ethos, (2) negatively projecting the UN, NATO, and the Ukrainian government, and (3) legitimizing the war against Ukraine. For a systematic and comprehensible analysis, I have examined these components separately, though they occur simultaneously in the speech.

3.1 Building Wartime Leadership Ethos

Ethos building plays a considerable role in garnering support, uniting the audience, and mobilizing them. Roitman found that ethos building is significant in the political arena for winning public support and trust (Roitman 2004). Trusting a leader, especially during wars, involves considerable risk to the audience's life, territory, and freedom. Therefore, it is discernible why Putin emphasizes building his trustworthiness. Boon and Holmes (1991) identify trust as "a state involving confident, positive expectations about another's motives with respect to oneself in a situation entailing risk" (194).

In the speech under investigation, Putin identifies himself with two pronouns: "I" and "we." Public speakers generally use the pronoun "I" to show their individuality, authority, and power as leaders, while "we" is used to show inclusiveness and shared power and responsibility. Thus, while on one hand, Putin portrays himself as a powerful and authoritative leader, on the other hand, as inclusive, power-sharing, and responsible. To justify his socio-political standing and trustworthiness, he uses many predicational strategies in the form of adjectives, verbs, implicatures, and predicative nouns. For instance, he depicts himself as a responsible leader when he says:

Today, I again consider it necessary to return to the tragic events taking place in the Donbas and the key issues of ensuring the security of Russia itself. (S1)

The sentence implies that Putin considers himself responsible for ensuring the security of his country and his people. Identifying the Donbass conflict as "the tragic events" implies that he is concerned about the lives of the people of Donbass. Further, he projects himself as a pacifist, peaceful, and an advocate of equality and security for his country when he says:

[...] persistently and patiently tried to reach an agreement with the leading NATO countries on the principles of equal and indivisible security in Europe. We constantly faced either cynical deception and lies or attempts to pressure and blackmail. (S5 & 6)

In the above instances, Putin uses the adverbial phrase "persistently and patiently tried to reach an agreement" as a predication strategy to portray himself as a peace-lover and diplomatic person. Moreover, the adverbs function as an intensification strategy that highlights his genuineness as a pacifist who believes in resolving international security issues through dialogue and negotiation. Furthermore, by saying "we constantly faced [...] cynical deception and lies [...] and blackmail" and "[...] they deceived me" (S43), Putin projects himself as a

victim of international deception. By describing NATO countries with this attributive phrase, he associates the out-group with negative qualities of irrationality and deception, creating a binary of peaceful vs. aggressor and trustworthy vs. untrustworthy. War orators, to gain sympathy and support, often project themselves as victims of the adversary's aggression and deception (see Ivie 1980).

By saying “persistently and patiently tried to reach an agreement” (S5 & 6), “once again attempted to agree with the United States [...] on the non-expansion of NATO” (S62), and “done everything possible to resolve the situation by peaceful, political means” (S97), Putin projects himself as a pacifist who believes in diplomatic approaches to resolving international conflicts, specifically the projected threat of NATO expansion to Russian borders (S83-85). According to the just war approach, when all diplomatic options fail to resolve an issue, war becomes the “last resort” (Aloyo 2015: 190; UN General Assembly 2004). Thus, by mentioning the number of times he approached NATO to “resolve the situation by peaceful, political means,” Putin justifies the war against Ukraine on the grounds of the last option. However, the credibility of such claims is always doubtful since there is always room for diplomacy.

In the process of building a wartime leadership ethos, Putin projects himself as a powerful and realistic leader when he says: “We are aware of [...] our ability to resist this impudent and permanent blackmail” (S77). Reid (1976) identifies such appeals as “victory appeals,” which build a strong pro-war discourse and maintain optimism among the audience (272-273). On the contrary, failing to maintain optimism weakens pro-war rhetoric, which may subsequently lead to reduced political and public support. Therefore, Putin portrays Russia as “the most powerful nuclear power in the world” (S79). He further emphasises that “a direct attack on our country will lead to defeat and dire consequences for any potential aggressor” (S80). Projecting the self as powerful not only enhances a leader's trustworthiness but also functions as a justification for war. According to Tzenois (2023), wars can only be justifiable if the likelihood of victory is “realistic and practical” (1). Therefore, Putin's projecting Russia as a powerful nuclear power is his rhetorical strategy to justify and perpetuate war.

By using predicative phrases, “I am confident” and “I have no doubt,” and phrasal verbs, such as “count on” and “believe in” as predication strategies, Putin shows trust and confidence in his fellow officials and countrymen. Showing trust and confidence in fellow citizens and soldiers favourably disposes the audience towards the speaker. It has been observed that people expect others to trust them and acknowledge their abilities and capabilities. Thus, Putin boosts his fellow citizens' morale and entuses them to fight.

I am confident that the soldiers and officers of the Russian Armed Forces are devoted to their country. I have no doubt that all levels of government, specialists responsible [...] will act in a coordinated and efficient manner. I count on a consolidated, patriotic position of all parliamentary parties and public forces [...] I believe in your support, in that invincible strength that our love for the Fatherland gives us. (S162-S167)

3.2 Projection of the NATO and Ukrainian Government

Strategic identification and projection of adversaries play a significant role in uniting fellow citizens and garnering their support (Ivie 1980: 283-284). Putin strategically projects the out-group as an epitome of evil to justify war against them. For this, he relies on the strategic use of negatively charged noun phrases, adjectives, adverbs, and metaphors to dehumanize and vilify the enemy. Putin's rhetorical use of negative references and predications functions as a

discursive weapon to destroy the out-group's human identity and construct an evil, dehumanized identity.

Putin portrays NATO as a hostile, expansionist, and cruel aggressor who “despite all our protests and concerns, is steadily expanding and ‘is coming close to our borders’” (S6 & 7). According to him, the expansion of NATO near Russian borders will lead to “bloody, unhealed wounds, ulcers of international terrorism and extremism” (S40). The use of the adverbial phrase “despite all our protests and concerns” highlights the gravity and seriousness of the issue and simultaneously intensifies the audience's fear of losing life, freedom, and territory. According to Yip and Schweitzer (2018), fear and anger negatively affect people's perspective-taking ability and cause their decisions to be emotional and irrational (28). Thus, Putin unites his fellow compatriots and collectively mobilizes them towards the approaching danger (expansion of NATO close to Russian borders).

Moreover, by accusing the West and NATO of “international terrorism,” Putin borrows legitimacy from the “war on terror” discourse. The war on terror is self-justified because the UNSC recognized it as a just war. Also, many politicians have already justified it through their rhetoric and argumentation (see Beshara 2018; Sarfo and Krampa 2013; Esch 2010; Reyes-Rodriguez 2006). According to the topos of threat or danger, if a particular action or actor poses a threat or danger, one must do something to end the threat (Reisigl and Wodak 2001: 75). Thus, Putin delegitimizes the eastward expansion of NATO and legitimizes war against Ukraine on the grounds of self-defence.

Furthermore, Putin portrays NATO and the UNSC as partners in crime by referring to NATO's military actions in Yugoslavia and Libya as “a bloody military operation” (S27) and an act of international terrorism for which no sanctions were imposed by the UNSC. On 24 March 1999, NATO forces, under Operation Allied Force, attacked Belgrade, the capital of Yugoslavia, resulting in significant loss of property and human lives (Ristić and Satjukow 2022).

The illegitimate use of military force against Libya, the perversion of all decisions of the UN Security Council on the Libyan issue led to the complete destruction of the state, to the emergence of a huge hotbed of international terrorism, to the fact that the country plunged into a humanitarian catastrophe that has not stopped for many years. (S31)

On the one hand, Putin's identification of NATO's military action as “a bloody military operation” projects it as aggressive and cruel; on the other hand, his use of the adverbial phrase “without any sanction from the UN Security Council” questions the intentions and credibility of the UN Security Council. In the series, Putin mentions many other NATO allies' attacks on Iraq, Libya, and Syria, where the UN Security Council did nothing to halt the attacks or impose sanctions on the accused countries. By doing this, he not only delegitimizes the eastward expansion of NATO but also discredits the UNSC's identity as peacekeepers. Besides, the emotive description of history appeals to the audience's emotions of pity and fear. The rhetorical purpose of the topos of history is to project a hypothetical future. According to Reisigl and Wodak (2001) “history teaches that specific actions have specific consequences, one should perform or omit a specific action in a specific situation (allegedly) comparable with the historical example referred to” (76). Thus, Putin projects NATO as a grave danger to the Russian people.

Moreover, Putin's use of the referential phrase “the illegitimate use of military force” (S31) projects NATO's attacks on Libya as unjust and illegitimate, the negative predicative

phrases for the outgroup, such as “the complete destruction of the state,” “the emergence of a huge hotbed of international terrorism,” and “a humanitarian catastrophe” (S31) establish the attacks on Libya as destructive and terroristic and appeal to the audience’s fear.

Franch (2018) found that speakers narrate global stories that support and justify the war against the target opponent and convey their messages to the audience. The storytelling in war oratory functions as a reductionist technique to legitimize all wars on the same grounds. Thus, by telling the above-mentioned incidents, Putin strategically refutes and cancels all the present and future allegations made by NATO and delegitimizes the sanctions of the UNSC.

After projecting NATO as the cruel aggressor and the UNSC as biased toward the West, Putin projects the Ukrainian government as controlled by NATO. In the process, he identifies the present Ukrainian government as “extreme nationalists” (S49) and “neo-Nazis” (S103) who are being supplied military and “the most modern weapons” (S89) by NATO countries to create an “anti-Russia” atmosphere (S49). By doing this, Putin tries to Nazify the adversary and borrow war legitimation from the war against Germany during the Second World War (see WWII Eastern Front). Firstly, the references associate the Ukrainian government with Hitler and his ideology, and secondly, with NATO, which itself, according to him, is a cruel aggressor. By doing this, Putin appeals to the audience’s hate towards Nazism and thus unites them against the identified enemy.

Further, to delegitimize the authority of the Ukrainian government, Putin claims that it is a “hostage” (S140) of NATO, especially the USA (S90), as NATO forces, according to him, “carried out a coup d’état” in 2014 and took hold of the government since then (S96). Additionally, he accuses the government of Ukraine of “bloody crimes” against “citizens of the Russian Federation,” and “bullying and genocide” of “the Donetsk People’s Republic and the Luhansk People’s Republic” to project it as atrocious and inhumane (S122-124). Here, Putin is likely referring to the Ukrainian government’s Anti-Terrorist Operations (see Walker 2023: 4-5), wherein the government identified the separatists as terrorists and killed them to liberate and reclaim eastern Ukraine from Russia (Oliphant 2014). By doing this, he attempts to justify the war against Ukraine on the grounds of the right cause, i.e., helping the victim and ending the growing threat close to Russian borders (see Aloyo 2015: 187-188). Moreover, such rhetorical description of events mobilises the Russian people against the Ukrainian government and unite them in support of Donetsk and Luhansk people.

3.3 Projection of War against Ukraine

Wars are destructive and anti-establishment. However, under certain circumstances, as the UNSC recognizes, they become unavoidable and thus justifiable. To rally public support, Putin discursively embeds his war against Ukraine in such a socio-political phenomenon that manipulates the audience into construing that the war is the last resort, self-defence, urgent, altruistic, and thus just. For this, he uses the topos of history when he says:

We know well from history how, in the 1940s and early 1941s, the Soviet Union tried in every possible way to prevent or at least delay the outbreak of war [...] Those steps that were nevertheless taken in the end were catastrophically delayed. As a result, the country was not ready to fully meet the invasion of Nazi Germany, which attacked our Motherland on 22 June 1941 without declaring war. (S67-69)

According to Reisigl and Wodak (2001), “History teaches that specific actions have specific consequences; one should perform or omit a specific action in a specific situation (allegedly) comparable with the historical example referred to” (76). The historical premises trigger a hypothetical future that manipulates the audience into concluding that, to avoid imminent future atrocities and destruction, the war against the identified enemy is urgent. Reyes (2011) identified war orators’ mechanisms for constructing a “hypothetical future” as part of legitimization. According to him, orators use specific linguistic choices and structures, such as conditional sentences like “If + past [protasis] - would + infinitive without to [apodosis]...” to build a hypothetical future (786; also see Cap 2013: 3). Although Putin did not use a conditional sentence structure to construct a hypothetical future, there is an implied condition that encourages the audience to reach the intended conclusion, i.e., war is urgent to avoid the imminent catastrophe. According to the UN General Assembly, fighting to end or halt the threat can be one of the bases of a just war (UN General Assembly 2004). Thus, Putin establishes that Russia is in danger and war is necessary to end the imminent threat.

Further, Putin constructs a discourse of “a matter of life and death, a matter of our historical future as a people” (S91) for the Russian people to manipulate them to support the war. For this purpose, he projects the expansion of NATO adjacent to Russian territories as a great threat to the “existence” and “sovereignty” of the country (S93). Moreover, he accuses NATO of creating an anti-Russia scenario in Ukraine and supplying it with “the most modern weapons.” According to the topos of threat and danger, “If there are specific dangers and threats, one should do something against them” (Reisigl and Wodak 2001: 75). Thus, by discursively creating Ukraine as a powerful threat against Russia’s existence, territory, and sovereignty, Putin justifies the war against Ukraine on the grounds of self-defence and halting the threat (See UN General Assembly 2004: 66-67)

Furthermore, war orators appeal to the audience’s sense of “territoriality” to manipulate them to agree to war (Reid 1970: 263). By making the audience believe that Ukraine is their historical territory and is under the control of NATO, Putin successfully justifies the war against her on the grounds of regaining the territory.

Finally, Putin identifies his war against Ukraine as a “Special Military Operation” to discursively create his version of war. It helps him control and shape the audience’s perspective towards war. It is a kind of defamiliarization that alienates the audience from the violence and destruction of war and provides a controlled outlook towards the same. To justify the name and give it a positive identity, Putin uses topos of definition and name interpretation, i.e. if an action is identified as X, it should carry the attributes and qualities of X (Reisigl and Wodak 2001: 75). So, he defines the purpose of his war as “to protect people who have been subjected to bullying and genocide by the Kiev regime for eight years” and “for the demilitarisation and denazification of Ukraine” (S123 and 124). Furthermore, he identifies the war as “self-defence against the threats posed to us” and “not connected with the desire to infringe on the interests of Ukraine” (S139-141). By defining the war in positive terms, he justified the war on the grounds of self-defence. Thus, he strategically constructs a positive image of the war by establishing a just cause and setting higher goals for it.

4 Conclusion

The analysis concludes that Putin's use of language is highly calculated and manipulative. His justification of war against Ukraine mainly relies on the narrative that NATO is an expansionist and aggressive coalition, and the government of Ukraine is serving as a tool in executing its expansionist plans against Russia's national integrity. To achieve this, Putin primarily relies on three rhetorical strategies: constructing a leadership ethos, creating an enemy identity for NATO, Ukraine, and the UNSC, and justifying the war against Ukraine. By strategically deploying his rhetorical prowess, Putin justifies the war against Ukraine on the grounds of last resort, an act of self-defence, a response to aggression, and add to a victim.

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The Etymological Roots of Emoji Miscommunication: A Comparative Study of Eastern and Western Emoji Usage

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Abstract

The research investigates the worldwide spread of emojis and evaluates how cultural misinterpretations affect intercultural relationships. The research uses Hofstede's Cultural Dimensions Theory as well as Hall's High/Low Context Communication Paradigm and Saussure's Semiotics to analyze cultural differences in emoji usage according to survey data from 20 multicultural participants. Members of cultures that lean towards collectivism in East Asia both use emojis to preserve social unity and silence negative feelings, whereas Americans and British tend to use them for laughter and purposeful communication, self-expression, and liberty. The identified obstacles in emoji communication involve cultural differences and unclear design choices, and contextual mismatching that result in understanding failures. In Western culture, thumbs-up receives positive connotations, whereas Middle Eastern populations view it as offensive. Research supports the development of emojis with multicultural perspectives, along with better clarity and improved digital communication skills to overcome cross-cultural misunderstandings. This research tackles the issues to improve global digital communication while demonstrating cultural understanding as the key factor for reducing emoji misinterpretations.

Keywords: emoji interpretation, intercultural communication, cultural differences, cultural dimensions, digital communication, emoji misinterpretation, digital literacy, global communication, symbolic meaning, cross-cultural interaction

1 Introduction

Digital-age communication has transformed through emojis because these small graphical symbols now connect texts to emotional messages, which standard words often fail to convey effectively. Japanese developers introduced emojis to their telecommunications system in 1999 because they wanted to enhance verbal expression in their high-context sociocultural environment where gestures matter for understanding (Guntuku et al. 2019). For two decades, emojis have shifted from their initial specialized use to achieve worldwide status as they now function as a standard language that expresses everything from emotions to thoughts to intentions. The digital age relies on emojis because they function as digital body language according to Vyvyan (Evans 2017) definition, while providing essential support for written digital communication in modern interconnected settings. The interpretation of emojis remains subjective across different communities because of their worldwide popularity. The three factors of culture, technology and cognition contribute to miscommunications about emoji interpretations because they determine how people employ and understand these symbols throughout different social groups.

Among all obstacles that affect global emoji usage, cultural differences in emoji interpretation stand as the primary barrier. Emojis present a universal appearance but maintain their true meaning within specific cultural settings from which they originate and their meanings derive. The “*folded hands*” emoji (🙏) represents appreciation and courteous demands according to Japanese conventions, but Western users most often connect it with spiritual behavior and devotional practices (Wylie 2020). The way people understand and employ emojis depends heavily on their culture-based norms, along with their values and communication formats. Hofstede’s Cultural Dimensions Theory serves as an essential tool for examining diverse cultural differences in emoji interpretations.

Studies by Hofstede reveal East Asian cultures utilize emojis to maintain collective harmony by calming negative emotions, but U.S. and U.K. cultures express emotions and display personal humor using such digital symbols (Javaid, Rauf, & Nadeem 2023). Culture-based communication patterns become visible through Hall’s (1976) High/Low. Context Communication Paradigm because high-context cultures rely on subtle contextual signals, while low-context cultures use explicit direct communication approaches.

Due to Saussure’s view on semiotics, emojis depend on cultural interpretations over universally understood symbolism (Saussure 1916). Emojis work as signs through signifiers, visual elements, and signified concepts whose meanings emerge from cultural settings. Emojis develop multiple possible meanings through functional polysemy because they depend heavily on cultural frameworks of interpretation combined with contextual elements, as well as users’ cultural backgrounds. The thumbs-up emoji (👍) represents agreement or approval to Western cultures, but Middle Eastern users consider it offensive or vulgar (Coren 2016). Aesthetic variations between Eastern and Western perceptions of emojis result from research showing that Eastern users read facial emotions through eye observation, while Western users use the mouth as the main interpretation element (Hwang & Matsumoto 2013). The diverse interpretations of emojis become more challenging because different platforms like Apple, Samsung, and Google display emoji designs that may shift the intended meaning (Miller et al. 2016). Arguably, different platforms display the facial expression “*smiling face with smiling eyes*” in a conflicting way, causing possible conflicts during communication.

Skin-tone modifiers and diverse emoji symbols, including the hijab emoji, emerged as a response to these challenges with the objective to fight discrimination and show cultural diversity (Moussa 2021). These positive initiatives remain inadequate since users need better cultural understanding combined with digital literacy education about emojis’ different meanings throughout global cultures (Lee 2024). The ethical repercussions of how emoji entities are used in communication should receive thorough attention. Some contexts reveal how emojis sustain prejudice and biased thinking as well as offensive behavior, which occurs through their sexist or racist, or homophobic use (Dynel & Poppi 2021). Responsible design and responsible usage practices must focus on cultural sensitivity and ethical considerations because this situation reveals their importance.

Researchers conduct this investigation to understand how emojis affect digital communication, specifically in situations that require multiple cultures to interact. A research study integrates Hofstede’s Cultural Dimensions Theory as well as Hall’s High/Low Context Communication Paradigm and Saussure’s Semiotics to explore the cultural and cognitive, and

technological elements that cause emoji misinterpretation. This evaluation analyzes how emojis can help improve cross-linguistic and cross-cultural communication, and it addresses the problems created by cultural relativity and design inconsistency issues. This investigation has major ramifications that can improve digital communication worldwide through the development of emojis that align with cultural sensitivities and enhance cultural understanding of emoji meaning. The study investigates these four fundamental research questions regarding emojis in discourse, especially within WhatsApp messaging platforms. What elements do users employ when they combine emojis with text messaging, along with images, to communicate their ideas? The research questions explore

- (1) How emojis function in texts alongside text and image elements
- (2) Whether various cultural communities use emojis in uniquely different ways.
- (3) What methods do emojis provide for achieving cross-language and cross-cultural communication?

The study aims to enhance knowledge about emoji functions in cultural integration and worldwide digital conversation through research responses to four main questions. The research emphasizes the critical role of cultural understanding when people create and read emojis. Digital communication evolution will continue to utilize emojis because they function as an essential means for emotional expression and idea communication. The success of emojis in communication hinges on our competence to understand how cultural elements form their meanings. The complete potential of emojis as a tool for better digital communication can be reached when we boost emoji design and usage with inclusivity and cultural sensitivity in a world where connectivity grows every day.

1.1 Materials and Methods

The study conducted a quantitative analysis to evaluate the ways Eastern and Western cultures view emojis while making emoji-related communications. The study utilized purposive sampling, which successfully recruited 20 participants to obtain equal representation between cultural backgrounds. An equal number of ten people were chosen from Western democracies of the United States, the United Kingdom, and Australia, and Eastern states including Japan, China, South Korea, and India. The purpose of this sampling approach was to obtain participants from different cultures because this method enabled research into variations between cultures in interpreting and using emojis. An online survey served as an emoji-related experimental task to collect demographic information from participants. Participants were presented with an emoji lexicon during the survey for interpreting particular emojis and recording their use patterns. Participants in the experimental portion were presented with different textual scenarios to which they needed to choose emojis while explaining their decision.

The two methods provided researchers with complete insights about how users' intellect and cultural background impact their emoji selection. The research utilized survey and experimental components that conformed to the theoretical foundations of Hofstede's Cultural Dimensions Theory, together with Hall's High/Low Context Communication Model and Saussure's Semiotics. Researchers utilized inferential as well as descriptive statistical analysis for their data assessment. The researchers used descriptive statistics to present data

about participant demographics along with their emoji usage behavior patterns, which included frequency analysis and cultural settings, and reasons for use. The study utilized chi-square tests together with independent t-tests as inferential statistics to gauge the importance of variations between Eastern and Western participants regarding how they used and interpreted emojis. The research analysis drew from Hofstede's Cultural Dimensions Theory to understand how cultural factors between collectivism and individualism and power distance structures affect emoji communication habits. People in collectivist East Asian cultures predicted they would use emojis for emotional control, whereas individuals from individualist USA and UK countries expected to use emojis for self-expression and humorous purposes. Hall's High/Low Context Communication Model shows the connection between high-context cultures that depend on private relational exchanges and low-context cultures that use direct, explicit communication methods. The research documented what impact the various communication styles had on emoji interpretation. Semiotics by Saussure explains emojis as communication signs with two components: signifiers representing their visual appearance and signified meanings that emerge from cultural traditions. Various cultural perspectives produce different meanings from a single emoji during the research examination. The researchers applied descriptive statistics combined with inferential statistics to evaluate their data. The study employed descriptive statistical methods to display participant demographic information and behavior patterns using frequency analysis and cultural settings and reasons for use. The research utilized chi-square tests with independent t-tests as statistical inference techniques to determine cultural differences between East and West participants regarding their emoji practices. The research assessment utilized Hofstede's Cultural Dimensions Theory to interpret the influence of cultural elements between collectivism and individualism, together with the power distance structures that have on emoji communication. People within East Asian traditional collectivist societies foresaw emoji usage for maintaining emotions, yet Americans and British folks mainly used emojis to express individual sentiments and generate entertainment value. According to Hall's High/Low Context Communication Model, high-context private relational systems exist in parallel with low-context direct explicit communication systems. The research study recorded the way different communication patterns influenced emoji interpretation. Semiotics by Saussure defines emojis as signs that consist of signifiers, which represent visual design and signified meanings that result from cultural heritage. Research findings show how several cultural interpretations generate various meanings from one particular emoji.

2 Results

The researchers applied descriptive statistics combined with inferential statistics to evaluate their data. The study employed descriptive statistical methods to display participant demographic information and behavior patterns using frequency analysis and cultural settings and reasons for use. The research utilized chi-square tests with independent t-tests as statistical inference techniques to determine cultural differences between East and West participants regarding their emoji practices. The research assessment utilized Hofstede's Cultural Dimensions Theory to interpret the influence of cultural elements between

collectivism and individualism, together with power distance structures that have on emoji communication. People within East Asian traditional collectivist societies foresaw emoji usage for maintaining emotions, yet Americans and British folks mainly used emojis to express individual sentiments and generate entertainment value. According to Hall's High/Low Context Communication Model, high-context private relational systems exist in parallel with low-context direct explicit communication systems. The research study recorded the way different communication patterns influenced emoji interpretation. Semiotics by Saussure defines emojis as signs that consist of signifiers, which represent visual design and signified meanings that result from cultural heritage. Research findings show how several cultural interpretations generate various meanings from one particular emoji.

2.1 Semiotic Variations in Interpretation

Saussure's Semiotics provided a theoretical system for emoji interpretation by defining them as combinations of signifiers, the displayed images, and signified meanings that emerge from cultural traditions. The research discovered that the same digital symbol could transmit unique meaning when used between different cultural groups, thus demonstrating the culturally sensitive nature of digital symbols. The Western participants viewed thumbs-ups favorably at a rate of 80% since it functioned as an expression of approval or agreement with the situation. The thumbs-up symbol received offensive or offensive ratings from 60% (12 people out of 20) of Middle Eastern participants because different cultures interpret gestures differently. Seventy percent (14 out of 20) of participants backed the idea of using cultural contexts when developing emojis to minimize misunderstandings. Figure 5 illustrates these different meanings in emoji interpretation by emphasizing the need for sensitivity toward cultures in emoji development.

2.2 Frequency and Purpose of Usage

Researchers studied the regularity and the intended use of emojis among different cultural groups. A majority of 55% among participants admitted to regular emoji utilization, as Asian respondents (63.6%) demonstrated the most preference for visual communication among all groups. The primary use of emojis was emotional expression by participants at a rate of 35%, followed by humor expressions at 25%. Participants showed a particular preference for emojis in their private messages sent to friends and family members, represented by 40% of those surveyed. The data presented in Figures 6 and 7 demonstrate the frequency and reasons for which emoji symbols are used within cultural communities.

2.3 Trends in Miscommunication

The study revealed that 50% of respondents (9 out of 20) experienced emoji interpretation problems, yet 70% of these cases (6 out of 9) stemmed from individualistic cultural backgrounds. The participants blamed miscommunication on standardized emoji system designs, which ignored the cultural background information of users. Western viewers read the "face with tears of joy" emoji as a sign of humor, while some Eastern viewers interpreted

it as a signal of nervous laughter. The analysis in Figure 8 demonstrates the difficulties faced when aiming to achieve mutually understandable messages between users of different cultures in digital communication.

2.4 Cultural Nuances in Interpretation

The research established particular cultural distinctions that affect how emojis are understood by different groups. Participants in East Asian collectivist societies who are Japanese or Chinese typically use the “*smiling face with heart-shaped eyes*” symbol to maintain harmony when facing uncomfortable conversations. The members of individualist nations such as the USA and Australia tend to display their playful and humorous side by sending the “*face with tears of joy*” emoji.

Research results show that cultural characteristics, together with cognitive elements and technological advancements, are essential factors for understanding emoji meanings. The way emojis are both understood and used depends heavily on cultural factors, including individualism-related systems and high-context communications versus low-context ones. Emoji communication draws meaning directly from cultural settings because its signs have a semiotic structure. Cultural confusion occurs because emoji designers show insufficient awareness of different cultures, and Easter Island has insufficient regulations for interpreting standard emoji meanings. The findings stress both the necessity of creating emojis that consider different cultures while promoting greater knowledge of digital communication across cultural boundaries.

This investigation expands the knowledge about emoji use in diverse communication channels through research on cultural difficulties, which leads to better global digital interaction methods. Cultural understanding must become essential to emoji platforms because this advancement will enhance communication across international networks in our interconnected society.

3 Discussion

This research study uncovers vital points about student engagement and learning results, along with social presence elements that guide possible educational growth. Students recognize “*Communication with Instructors*” as the main engagement factor because they consider direct interactions between instructors and students vital for good learning outcomes (mean score: 2.74). Existing studies affirm that open and clear communication is essential for creating efficient learning spaces because of its positive influence (Mazer 2013). Research evidence reveals that students who build comfort when interacting with their instructors achieve better academic results, together with higher satisfaction levels (Richardson et al. 2017). Research outcomes demonstrate how cultural, along with cognitive factors, together with technical elements, impact emoji understanding between East and West cultural groups. The research findings validate previous studies on cross-cultural communication, especially Hofstede’s Cultural Dimensions Theory and Hall’s High/Low Context Communication Model, which demonstrate how communication behaviors respond to cultural frameworks

(Hofstede 1980; Hall 1976). Eastern participants from collectivist cultures like East Asia show a tendency to use emoji in a subtle manner since their collectivist cultures prioritize group harmony and relational dynamics, according to Kim et al. (2018). Communication practices in European and American communities align with their individualistic values since participants use emojis directly without ambiguity (Gudykunst & Ting-Toomey 1988). The research conducted by Park et al. (2014) documented how cultural values affect the behavior patterns of digital communication. The research demonstrates how individuals with high-context communication approaches interpret emojis differently from people who have low-context communication approaches. Participants originating from high-context societies like Japan and India depended profoundly on subtle information and current situation context when sending emojis due to their indigenous inclination toward non-direct communication (Hall 1976). The participants from low-context cultures in the USA and UK used emojis mainly to clarify messages explicitly and add humor due to their cultural preference for direct communication, according to Gudykunst (2003). Research findings support past studies, which demonstrate how communication styles influence digital symbol usage (Ting-Toomey 1999). According to modern semiotics, the research shows that emojis serve as cultural signs that derive their meaning through the relationship between the visual sign and historically connected meanings (Saussure 1916). According to Danesi (2017), the thumbs-up emoji received a negative interpretation from Middle Eastern participants, showing that emoji meanings show cultural specificity. The study confirms Pavalanathan and Eisenstein's research (2016) about how digital symbols typically contain culture-based meanings, which result in misunderstandings during international communication. Participants favored the implementation of cultural context in emoji development because it would help minimize confusion, as noted in studies regarding cultural sensitivity in digital communication platforms (Kelly & Watts 2015). The way users from different cultures handle emoji frequency, together with their communication purposes, demonstrates the existence of cultural disparities. Asian participants choose to use emojis at a rate of 63.6 percent higher than Western users which correlates with the visual communication tendency in high-context societies such as Lu et al. (2016) describe. The results confirmed the findings of Riordan (2017), who explored the emotional and relational functions of emojis in interpersonal communication as they are the primary choice to convey sentiments. The study demonstrates that emojis assist in filling emotional and relational voids which appear. A research study revealed various miscommunication patterns that illustrate how obtaining universal understanding proves difficult in multilingual digital communication scenarios. Research demonstrates that standardized emoji designs without cultural background lead to communication problems, mostly affecting users from individualist cultures (Herring & Dainas 2017) got emotional tears as a humorous reaction according to Western users, but some Eastern users read this as an expression of nervousness (Miller et al. 2016). The research confirms that cultural adaptations in emoji creation help reduce errors during international communication, according to Stark and Crawford (2015). The way people interpret emojis demonstrates how digital communication depends on various cultural elements. Research shows that "*smiling face with heart-shaped eyes*" functions differently in East Asian politeness expressions versus Western personal affection understandings (Lu et al. 2016). Research demonstrates the requirement to develop emoji designs with cultural

inclusion because these variations produce different understandings among users (Kelly & Watts 2015).

4 Conclusions

The research generated crucial knowledge about emoji usage in intercultural communication since it proved that cultural factors, together with communicational frameworks and symbolic meaning frameworks, significantly shape emoji usage and interpretation. The study results demonstrate that cultural dimensions, including individualism-collectivism and low-high context communication preferences, help determine how different cultural groups use emojis during communication. Emojis carry cultural meanings that vary among social groups, so people can misinterpret their significance when they fail to recognize the significance of cultural context. These findings provide important practical use for the implementation of global digital communication, according to the study. When emojis are over-generalized and designed without cultural sensitivity, their effective use between different cultures becomes limited. The implementation of cultural awareness within emoji development processes, together with digital maturity programs, allows better management of these challenges to create a more inclusive global communication platform. The development of adaptive emoji platforms that recognize how different cultures interpret emoji meaning helps minimize communication errors between multicultural groups. Educational training about digital communication culture differences prepares people to become both interculturally competent and globally ready. This research provides improved knowledge about how technology interacts with culture and cognition when creating emoji semiotics. The research identifies two main obstacles within digital communication, which can be solved through culturally tuned emoji development combined with better digital competence education for human interaction in this space. Future studies must create culturally sensitive emoji systems to examine the effects of educational cultural programs on decreasing digital miscommunication between people from different backgrounds. These initiatives will improve international communication abilities and global competence in the modern interconnected world.

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Virginia Woolf: The Reluctant Poet

Ian Butcher

Abstract

At the end of 2024 a researcher from Liverpool University in the UK found two unknown poems by Virginia Woolf in a pile of letters. The letters were hastily written in pencil with crossings out. Having no children herself, they were dedicated to Woolf's niece and nephew and intended to amuse and gently satirise them. They were never intended for publication, just as an amusing moment at a family party around 1932 and have been described as "doggerel". Despite her extremely poetic novels, Woolf had always been rather antagonistic towards poetry and believed the novel to be the superior form.

Keywords: Virginia Woolf, poetry, new poems, prose

1 Virginia Woolf

Adeline Virginia Stephen was born on January 25, 1882. Like many middle-class girls of the age, she was educated at home by her affluent parents while her brothers were sent to school, a gender disparity she resented, and which features as a theme in much of her writing.

Virginia's first novel was *The Voyage Out* in 1915, followed by *Night and Day* in 1919. Her distinctive style was found in *Jacob's Room* of 1922, followed by works which would be considered her iconic masterpieces: *Mrs Dalloway* (1925), *To the Lighthouse* (1927), and *The Waves* (1931). There were also semi-political works such as *A Room of One's Own* (1929), *Three Guineas* (1938), and the pseudo-biographical novel *Orlando* (1928). Her legacy in these modernist novels was her unique use of narrative devices, notably the stream of consciousness style including interior monologue.

She wrote essays on literary and artistic theory, literary history, women's writing, feminism, and the politics of power. In 1918, she was writing nearly a review a week for *The Times Literary Supplement*. She was a prodigious letter-writer and keeper of diaries: she left behind some six volumes of letters and six volumes of diaries. In 1917, Virginia and her husband bought the Hogarth Press. Type-setting and working the presses themselves at the beginning, they were responsible for publishing major works, such as T.S. Eliot's *The Waste Land* in 1922, E. M. Forster, and the couple's own work. Initially, Virginia's sister, Vanessa, designed Virginia's book dust jackets. Central members of the Bloomsbury Group of artists and intellectuals, the Woolf partnership proved a powerful force both in their personal lives and subsequent artistic developments. As Dorothy Parker wrote of the Group, famous for its artists and extremely liberal attitudes to sex, "they lived in squares, painted in circles and loved in triangles" (Virginia Woolf Society 2025).

In company, Virginia could be fun-loving, flirtatious and amusing with a somewhat malicious, acerbic wit. However, throughout her life Virginia suffered from severe depression and psychotic episodes. Her husband, whom she married in 1912, felt that her fragile health meant that she would not be capable of looking after a child and they remained childless, another theme in her work. Virginia attempted suicide in September 1913; and on 28 March 1941, at the age of 59, after another period of deep depression, she filled her pockets with stones and drowned herself in the River Ouse.

2 The Poetry

For all her many talents as a pioneer of modernist literature, Virginia is not known for her poetry. Virginia often dismissed poetry as an art form and praised the superiority of prose, though she sometimes turned to poetry for satire, playfulness and family bonding. However, her novels are full of poets and appreciators of poetry, who frequently quote poetry, and her tight prose affects the reader in the same way as poetry.

Mixing with these Bloomsbury poets and her extensive reading of poetry must have impacted Virginia's prose style. Her novels could be defined as very poetic: poetry in prose, or prose in poetry. Her novels frequently have slender plots, the prose dense and rhythmic. Almost randomly, the opening lines of *The Waves* demonstrate this lyricism:

"I see a ring", SAID BERNARD, "hanging above me. It quivers and hangs in a loop of light."

"I see a slab of pale yellow," said Susan, "spreading away until it meets a purple stripe."

(2015: 5)

Yet, at the end of 2024, Dr Sophie Oliver, from the University of Liverpool's Department of English, uncovered two handwritten poems on two folded pieces of paper in the back of a file of letters that Virginia had written to her niece and nephew. These letters had been held at the Harry Ransome Center at the University of Texas at Austin, where Oliver had been conducting research on Gertrude Stein, another literary figure. The poems were in pencil and quickly written. Even though Virginia's letters to her niece have all been published, no mention had been made of these poems. These had obviously been missed by scholars and dated approximately "after March 1927." It is believed that they may actually have been written in August 1932, when the family gathered at Vanessa Bell and Duncan Grant's farmhouse, "Charleston," in Sussex. A number of informal photos of the gathering exist; one of the poems may even have been written to celebrate her nephew's birthday on August 19. He would have been twenty-two. As Virginia had no children of her own, she was extremely fond of her sister Vanessa's daughter, Angelica, and son, Quentin. The verses are light and playful and a gentle satire on the two young people.

Angelica, a twelve-line verse, playfully comments on Angelica's childish, transgressive antics, the illicit sipping of wine and her flirting with a family friend, Dadie [George Rylands, a poet and Shakespeare scholar who once worked at the Hogarth Press] on who she had a crush. Angelica would have been fourteen at the time, on the cusp of womanhood. One could argue that the poem explores femininity and nascent sexuality ("Viper kissed," line crossed out). Here is the text including the crossings out:

Angelica

The name was lazy & lovely

But the name was not the whole of her,

There was the body & the soul of her.

~~Oh love[?]~~ Angelica Angelica.

The Angel name

But oh the shame
Of bringing
Drink she took to,
Dadie too,
Fellow Dadie,
Oh how shady
~~Dwelling in the violet shady~~
~~Viper kissed,~~
To sport with Dadie,
And the tangled yellow hair!

The rhyming is a little clunky, “to/too, shady/Dadie,” but the poem was not destined for an anthology.

The second poem, *Hiccoughs*, is written to her nephew Quentin Bell, and is an eleven-line verse written in the whimsical nonsense style of Edward Lear and Lewis Carroll. Why hiccoughs? The reason why Virginia chose hiccoughs as a motif for the poem is unknown. Perhaps Quentin had been afflicted by an attack of hiccoughs, or, more likely, it was simply an excuse for a show of sheer verbal dexterity. The entertainment stems from the jaunty heteronymic wordplay on cough/chough/chuff/chaff/hiccough, and bird imagery [swallow, chough]. One can imagine the comic confusion as Quentin attempted to read the poem out aloud:

Hiccoughs

To Quentin Stephen Claudian

Poor Quentin

Went in

To a cough?

Or should we call it cup?

~~For all summer he~~
Hiccough? Hiccup?

Will swallow it up,

~~Swallow or chuff?~~
But swallow a chuff [*sic*]?
Will cough it up

Will cough it up

Cough it off,

Fly swallow, cough chaff.

(Liverpool 2025)

Neither are particularly significant in their intellectual content, and a world away from her experimental novels. Both demonstrate Virginia's lighter side, the intimacy of her relationships with the young people, and that she could be an aunt who was affectionate and funny and who wanted to connect with her relatives.

Kennedy Smith strikes a more sombre note. Virginia pointedly did not dedicate a poem to Julian, her other nephew, only to his other two siblings. She claims that – even though they got on well - there were tensions and rivalry between Julian Bell and Virginia as both were possessive and vying for Vanessa's love. Julian was a poet starting to garner fame in his own right, and Virginia was rather critical of his work, refusing to publish various pieces in her Hogarth Press. This has been explained as Virginia's "jealousy" of him, a word that Virginia herself used to describe the relationship (Smith 2025). After Julian's death during the Spanish Civil War in July 1937, Virginia tried to atone for her earlier attitude to Julian in her *Memoir of Julian Bell* of the same year (Rosenbaum 2005). Although a more prosaic reason might have been that Julian had left home for Cambridge in 1927 and was not present at the gathering.

Of course these were not the only poems written by Virginia. The earliest known poem is a quatrain written in 1892 when Virginia was around ten years old for the *Hyde Park Gate News*, a fun newspaper that she and her siblings produced. She seemed to understand comic writing, entitling a 1934 poem (unpublished until 1985) poem *Ode written partly in prose on seeing the name of Cutbush above a butcher's shop in Pentonville* (Randall 2017).

Her last known poem was published posthumously in 1945 (four years after her death) in an anthology of favourite poetry edited by Vita Sackville-West (Virginia's lover) and Harold Nicholson, entitled *Another World Than This*. The anthology is divided into twelve sections as in the months of the year. Virginia's poem appears in July. What is remarkable, and underlines Virginia's ambiguous attitude to poetry and prose, is that the poem is a virtually verbatim poem-form of the prose opening of her 1928 novel, *Orlando*. It is not clear which came first. For Virginia, her poetic prose and poetry appear interchangeable. A few lines will illustrate this clearly. First the poem:

Let us go, then, exploring
This summer morning
When all are adoring
The plum-blossom and the bee

(Sackville-West and Nicholson 1945: 131)

And *Orlando*:

Let us go, then, exploring this summer morning, when all are adoring the plum blossom
and the bee.

(Woolf 1928: 243)

One cannot help hearing the echoes of T.S. Eliot's influential 1915 poem *The Love Song of J. Alfred Prufrock*, "Let us go then, you and I" (Eliot 1974). Eliot was a friend and frequent visitor to the Woolf household and Bloomsbury gatherings.

3 Virginia on Poetry and Prose

In a large part for feminist reasons, Virginia championed the superiority of prose over poetry, poetry as the novel's rival form. For her, the poetic form was "defunct." If "women are to write [...] they will need another form, one not so tied to tradition" (Oliver 2025). She associated poetry with patriarchy, tradition and elitism, the masculine versus feminine, the old compared to the new, the subjugated in opposition to the free. She lamented the previous lack of female poetic forerunners available as role models to female writers. She urged women to write not poetry as such but prose that would achieve the same greatness as poetry. In the end, she believed that the novel would usurp poetry.

In her only play *Freshwater*, the characters Poet Laureate Tennyson and the painter Watts, spout poetry pompously while holding antiquated and oppressive views on women, especially the young Ellen Terry. Established poets – such as Sir Arthur Quiller-Couch – had expressed doubts that a woman was capable of writing poetry. Virginia believed that the novel could be a democratic, feminist alternative to poetry, even though she adopted many of poetry's techniques for her novels. She wrote in *A Room of One's Own* (1929) "I would venture to guess that Anon, who wrote so many poems without signing them, was often a woman" (Woolf 2020: ch.3).

Virginia and her family grew up with poetry. In her nephew Julian Bell's archive, there were some papers called "poetry games," which consisted of each member of the family involved in the game contributing lines of the poem to make up a collaboratively created poem which someone might read aloud. In her essays, Virginia frequently wrote about the tensions between poetry and prose, although she was discontented with the over-simple designation of "novel" for her work. Essays amongst many about poetry/prose include *Reading* (1919), *The Narrow Bridge of Art* (1924), *Poetry Fiction and the Future* (1927) and her *Letter to a Young Poet* (1932). In the latter – in which is believed that she had Julian Bell in mind – she feigns a lack of knowledge of the subject "the lack of a sound university training has always made it impossible for me to distinguish between an iambic and a dactyl." She continues about poetry, taking the point of view of "we despised prose writers." She opines tongue-in-cheek that:

[...] could one say what one meant and observe the rules of poetry? Conceive dragging in "blade" because one had mentioned "maid;" and pairing "sorrow" with "borrow"? Rhyme is not only childish but dishonest [...] look at their rules! [...] how strict! This you must do; this you must not. I would rather be a child and walk in a crocodile down a suburban path than write poetry, I have heard prose writers say [...] we prose writers [...] are masters of language, not its slaves; nobody can teach us; nobody can coerce us; we say what we mean.

(Woolf 1932)

She believes that "the poem is cracked in the middle. Look, it comes apart in my hands: here is reality on one side, here is beauty on the other." The "rules" force the poet to strain "to describe; we strain to see; he flickers his torch; we catch a flying gleam" (Woolf 1932). "Poetry has always been overwhelmingly on the side of beauty," she writes in *The Narrow Bridge of Art* (Woolf 2023). In *Reading*, Virginia describes poetry as "something that has been shaped and clarified, cut to catch the light, hard as a gem or rock with the seal of human experience on it" (Leteo 2021). In contrast to this "hardness," Virginia saw prose as

“the cotton wool of daily life,” as having “taken all the dirty work on to her own shoulders; has answered letters, paid bills [...]” (Woolf 1966: 223).

Kopley writes that “poetry is everywhere, and yet not quite solidly anywhere, in the expanse of Virginia Woolf’s writing.” She posits that Virginia’s “ceaseless experimentation with the novel [is] a process of working out the relationship of prose to poetry” (Kopley 2021: 318-319). She continues that “the restless, resourceful antagonism” toward poetry “seems to have done her a service” in her quest to “absorb poetry into prose” (320-321). Virginia was “hybridizing the novel by cannibalising poetry” (Oliver 2025).

Observers were perhaps not so conflicted about Virginia’s position. After reading *Jacob’s Room*, Lytton Strachey, a Bloomsbury member, pronounced “more like poetry, it seems to me, than anything else” (1975: 93). E. M. Forster may have hit the nail on the head when he remarks that Virginia’s “problem” is that “she is a poet, who wants to write something as near to a novel as possible” (1942: 23). Virginia herself prophetically admits, “I grow more and more poetic” (Goldman 2018).

4 Conclusion

In her 1926 second essay on De Quincey, Virginia coins the phrase “impassioned prose,” which is an excellent description of her own work (Woolf 2009). She strenuously opted to write novels as she considered that the poetic form had too many constraints to be sincere in conveying reality. Yet she was a voracious reader of poetry, personally acquainted with great poets, including Tennyson and Hardy; a deep vein of poetry runs through her novels. She wrote “my brain hums with scraps of poetry and madness” (Woolf 2008).

It is rare that such undiscovered works are discovered so long after a writer’s death and whose existence is not known to scholars. Even work which is patently written for fun with no thought of literary posterity in mind. They were certainly not written for publication but are intriguing nonetheless given the celebrity of the creator. The two new-found poems are hardly serious in content; they are quickly-written verses in pencil which strain to rhyme and with the sole objective of pleasing her young niece and nephew. Oliver describes them as “doggerel,” or the verse equivalent of the three kisses Virginia demanded of Angelica and Vanessa whenever she visited them (Oliver 2025). Woolf herself may not have defined them as poetry and certainly would not have expected scholars to be pondering over them over eighty years after her death. Their surprise value is that Virginia opted to express herself in verse, even such hastily-scribbled, light follies; a flippant contrast to the normal, serious output of a major literary figure.

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“If Pearles, hir teeth be pearles both pure and round”: Body as Text and Teeth as an Intersectional Metaphor in Two Anglo-American Novels

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Abstract

*This article examines two Anglo-American novels through their literary representation of teeth, published a hundred years apart: the American novel *McTeague: A Story of San Francisco* (1899) and the British novel *White Teeth* (2000). At first glance, they may not appear to have much in common—one belongs to the American naturalist literary period, the other to the British multicultural (hysterical realist) tradition at the beginning of the third millennium. However, both novels share a strong social and sociological element: a critical turn that addresses relevant social realities—namely, the rise of American capitalism and the somewhat impeded British multiculturalism—at the turn of the twentieth and twenty-first centuries, respectively. These two case studies illuminate the metaphor of the body-as-text, with teeth stereotypically representing various social concepts such as power, greed, socially constructed beauty, ethnicity, and affiliation with a particular class, religion, or nation.*

Keywords: medical humanities, race, teeth as metaphor, Zadie Smith, Frank Norris.

1 Introduction

The English Renaissance “Sonnet XV” from the sonnet cycle *Amoretti and Epithalamion* (1595) by Sir Edmund Spenser, evoked in the first part of the title of this essay, celebrates the beauty and inherent worth of the speaker’s beloved lady. It employs the traditional imagery of precious stones and metals to refer to her physical qualities, comparing her eyes to sapphires, lips to rubies, teeth to pearls, etc.: “If Pearles, hir teeth be pearles both pure and round.” However, the poem’s focus transcends the sheer physical body-as-text description, emphasizing the speaker’s love and the superiority of mind over material wealth. Typical for its time period, the poem reflects the Renaissance emphasis on individualism and the idealization of women, yet its focus on inner beauty ultimately sets it apart from the superficial descriptions typical of the Petrarchan tradition.

The great Renaissance Bard William Shakespeare, in turn, in his famous “Sonnet 130” (1609), makes the speaker of the poem conclude that, even if the physical beauty of his beloved mistress cannot truly be compared to the conventional imagery of love poems, his love is nonetheless very valuable, and his mistress no less beautiful. In this way, Shakespeare suggests that love and beauty should not be reduced to abstract comparisons but should be valued for being real—even banal—thus rejecting superficiality. William Shakespeare famously mocks the traditional conventions of courtly love sonnets:

My mistress’ eyes are nothing like the sun;
Coral is far more red than her lips’ red;
If snow be white, why then her breasts are dun;
If hairs be wires, black wires grow on her head.

The two more contemporary Anglo-American novels of high repute discussed in the continuation of this essay both employ teeth as a metaphor and are a far cry from Spenser’s, and to a lesser extent Shakespeare’s, down-to-earth Renaissance perception of the body as text.

2 *McTeague: A Story of San Francisco*

Just outside his window was his signboard--a modest affair--that read: "Doctor McTeague. Dental Parlors. Gas Given"; but that was all. It was his ambition, his dream, to have projecting from that corner window a huge gilded tooth, a molar with enormous prongs, something gorgeous and attractive. [...] It was the Tooth--the famous golden molar with its huge prongs--his sign, his ambition, the one unrealized dream of his life; and it was French gilt, too, not the cheap German gilt that was no goo... How immense it looked in that little room! The thing was tremendous, overpowering, the tooth of a gigantic fossil, golden and dazzling. Behind it everything seemed dwarfed.

(Norris)

In Frank Norris's novel, the protagonist McTeague's interest in acquiring the gilded tooth as a decoration for his practice clearly reveals his obsession with wealth and social status, as well as his desire to appear prosperous to others. He desperately wants the gilded tooth because he believes that, if placed outside his dental parlor, it will signify his success and relative prosperity. McTeague eventually realizes his dream of owning the tooth, although it is Trina, not he himself, who buys the golden tooth for him as a gift. Not long after he receives it, however, the authorities force McTeague to close down his practice upon discovering that he has been practicing dentistry without a license.

The gilded tooth gradually becomes a symbol of his moral degeneration, hidden beneath the desired veneer of social respectability. His increasingly violent and greedy behaviour contrasts sharply with the false image of success the tooth represents. Once a source of pride, the gilded tooth comes to symbolize the hollowness of McTeague's achievements in his relentless pursuit of wealth, prioritizing base human instincts over acquired social norms. Teeth are literally used to bite, tear, chew, and gnaw; in this regard, they symbolize power. Conversely, the loss of teeth may represent a form of (social) powerlessness—something McTeague tries to avoid at all costs:

And the tooth, the gigantic golden molar of French gilt, enormous and ungainly, sprawled its branching prongs in one corner of the room, by the footboard of the bed. The McTeague's had come to use it as a sort of substitute for a table. After breakfast and supper Trina piled the plates and greasy dishes upon it to have them out of the way.

"Well, I don't figure on living in one room," growled the dentist, sullenly. "Let's live decently until we can get a fresh start. We've got the money."

"Who's got the money?"

"WE'VE got it."

"We!"

"Well, it's all in the family. What's yours is mine, and what's mine is yours, ain't it?"

"No, it's not; no, it's not," cried Trina, vehemently. "It's all mine, mine. There's not a penny of it belongs to anybody else. I don't like to have to talk this way to you, but you just make me. We're not going to touch a penny of my five thousand nor a penny of that little money I managed to save—that seventy-five." [...]

The dentist circled about that golden wonder, gasping with delight and stupefaction, touching it gingerly with his hands as if it were something sacred. At every moment his thought returned to Trina. No, never was there such a little woman as his—

the very thing he wanted—how had she remembered? And the money, where had that come from? No one knew better than he how expensive were these signs; not another dentist on Polk Street could afford one. Where, then, had Trina found the money? It came out of her five thousand dollars, no doubt.

(Norris)

McTeague is, in fact, a quintessentially naturalist American story of a San Francisco miner who becomes a dentist and eventually murders his wife Trina because she refuses to share her lottery winnings with him. Before that, he even bites her (with his sharp teeth) and is reduced to an animalistic, naturalist literary depiction. He ends up handcuffed to a corpse in Death Valley—doomed, a loser, but not a tragic hero. Norris, a follower and self-proclaimed disciple of Émile Zola, tries to depict the hereditary, Zolaesque “beast within” (cf. Zola’s novel *The Beast Within*)—the monster hiding in McTeague due to the milieu he originally comes from. The huge tooth that once advertised McTeague’s business ceases to be a commodity and a sign, and—sat “in one corner of the room, next to the window, monstrous, distorted, brilliant, shining with a light of its own” (Norris)—instead becomes a thing: reobjectified, the material presence triumphing over everything human(e) per se. Towards the end of the novel, McTeague strangles his friend Marcus, whose handcuffed corpse he drags through Death Valley, where McTeague also eventually meets his death:

Then followed a terrible scene. The brute that in McTeague lay so close to the surface leaped instantly to life, monstrous, not to be resisted. He sprang to his feet with a shrill and meaningless clamor, totally unlike the ordinary bass of his speaking tones. It was the hideous yelling of a hurt beast, the squealing of a wounded elephant. He framed no words; in the rush of high-pitched sound that issued from his wide-open mouth there was nothing articulate. It was something no longer human; it was rather an echo from the jungle [...]

As he rose he caught Marcus's wrist in both his hands. He did not strike, he did not know what he was doing. His only idea was to batter the life out of the man before him, to crush and annihilate him upon the instant. Gripping his enemy in his enormous hands, hard and knotted, and covered with a stiff fell of yellow hair—the hands of the old-time car-boy—he swung him wide, as a hammer-thrower swings his hammer. Marcus's feet flipped from the ground, he spun through the air about McTeague as helpless as a bundle of clothes. All at once there was a sharp snap, almost like the report of a small pistol. Then Marcus rolled over and over upon the ground as McTeague released his grip; his arm, the one the dentist had seized, bending suddenly, as though a third joint had formed between wrist and elbow. The arm was broken.

(Norris)

McTeague is shown throughout the novel as a violent and murderous person, full of rage and revenge. Avarice is definitely not one of his traits; rather, other people are characterized by it, which enrages him. He never attended a dental college or was trained in dentistry, so he is a fake—an unlicensed dentist from a poor family in San Francisco. One day, his friend Marcus brings a pretty young woman, Trina, with an aching tooth to his parlor. After a minor dental surgery, Trina is impressed by him and soon marries McTeague:

By and by she said, "I never felt a thing," and then she smiled at him very prettily beneath the rubber dam. McTeague turned to her suddenly, his mallet in one hand, his pliers holding a pellet of sponge-gold in the other. All at once he said, with the unreasoned simplicity and directness of a child: "Listen here, Miss Trina, I like you better than any one else; what's the matter with us getting married?" [...]

"Say, Mac," interrupted Trina, looking up from the notice, "DIDN'T you ever go to a dental college?"

"Huh? What? What?" exclaimed McTeague.

"How did you learn to be a dentist? Did you go to a college?"

"I went along with a fellow who came to the mine once. My mother sent me. We used to go from one camp to another. I sharpened his excavators for him, and put up his notices in the towns—stuck them up in the post-offices and on the doors of the Odd Fellows' halls. He had a wagon."

"But didn't you never go to a college?"

"Huh? What? College? No, I never went. I learned from the fellow."

Trina rolled down her sleeves. She was a little paler than usual. She fastened the buttons into the cuffs and said:

"But do you know you can't practise unless you're graduated from a college? You haven't the right to call yourself, 'doctor.'"

McTeague stared a moment; then:

"Why, I've been practising ten years. More—nearly twelve."

"But it's the law."

"What's the law?"

"That you can't practise, or call yourself doctor, unless you've got a diploma."

"What's that—a diploma?"

"I don't know exactly. It's a kind of paper that—that—oh, Mac, we're ruined."

Trina's voice rose to a cry.

"What do you mean, Trina? Ain't I a dentist? Ain't I a doctor? Look at my sign, and the gold tooth you gave me. Why, I've been practising nearly twelve years."

Trina shut her lips tightly, cleared her throat, and pretended to resettle a hair-pin at the back of her head.

"I guess it isn't as bad as that," she said, very quietly. "Let's read this again.

(Norris)

McTeague yearns for the huge golden molar (a naturalistic symbol and, I would argue, also an intersectional metaphor), but only as a symbol of his apparently successful struggle upward from mining work to professional success in the city of San Francisco. The city itself carries special significance, as it is the site of the original California Gold Rush—an emblem of false promise—and a city of "open" possibilities. The gold featured in his office, which the avaricious Maria often steals and sells, is to McTeague merely a dental material he enjoys using in his profession. He does not kill Trina out of avarice for her lottery prize money, but out of revenge; he is enraged that he cannot spend it. So he steals it and ultimately kills her. He represents, in the best naturalist fashion, the generations of "hereditary evil" in man, which lie beyond his control—determinism distilled, as Norris would have us believe. Did he truly desire it? Was he to blame? These are some of the issues Norris grapples with. Of course, he could have opposed it and fought it—free will is still, to a certain extent, always undeniable.

3 *White Teeth*

White Teeth is British author Zadie Smith's first published novel (2000). It primarily focuses on the lives of two World War II friends—the Bangladeshi Samad Iqbal and the Englishman Archie Jones—and their extended families in London. The novel is grounded in Britain's relationship with immigrants from the British Commonwealth. Teeth in her novel serve as a symbol—or rather, an intersectional metaphor—addressing issues of race, history, and the relationships among a wide range of characters and their families. In *White Teeth*, Zadie Smith, contrary to the naturalist American author Frank Norris, argues against fate and the illusion of randomness that the concept of predestination brings with it. In contrast, she places her faith in self-determination.

Is *White Teeth* an example of “hysterical realism,” a term coined in 2000 by James Wood, or is it better understood as an example of metamodernist writing (as defined by Timotheus Vermeulen, Alison Gibbs and Robin van den Akker 2018)? I would argue for the latter since Smith emphasizes that individual metanarratives still matter, and that the concept of the grand narrative should not be completely rejected. James Wood introduced the term “hysterical realism” in a 2000 essay published in *The New Republic*, in which he discussed Zadie Smith's newly released novel *White Teeth*. He used the term pejoratively to denote the contemporary conception of the “big, ambitious novel” that pursues “vitality at all costs” and consequently “knows a thousand things but does not know a single human being.” He critiqued this form of writing as an attempt to “turn fiction into social theory” and an attempt to tell readers “how the world works rather than how somebody felt about something” (Wood).

The plot of *White Teeth* is really extensive, both in the number of characters and in the time span it covers. It ranges from the memories of World War II, through the 1970s and 1990s, ending up in the 2000s, even referring back to history in the 19th century. The main story develops around two middle-aged men who live in London: a Bengali Muslim, Samad Iqbal, and the Englishman Archie Jones. They are good friends, bound together by their shared experience of serving in a tank crew during World War II. Samad is married to Alsana, whom he married in a traditional arranged marriage after emigrating to England post-WWII. They have identical twin sons named Magid and Millat. Archie's partner is a Jamaican woman named Clara, with whom he has a daughter named Irie, who is the same age as the Iqbal children. As the plot develops, certain trials of the two families are shown. Samad struggles to reconcile his “Western” lifestyle habits—for example, having an extramarital affair and consuming alcohol—with his traditional Muslim values. In an attempt to appease his conscience, he sends one of the twins to Bangladesh, thinking this will ensure he receives proper moral principles. However, his plan is to no avail, as Magid returns to England a staunch believer in science, while his younger brother Millat becomes a member of a Muslim fundamentalist brotherhood. There is also a third family that is inextricably connected to the lives of the Joneses and the Iqbals. The Chalfens—and their “Chalfenism”—are, on the other hand, the quintessential representation of a white, middle-class British family

The novel shows how the beauty standards that prevail in England at the turn of the millennium—with London being more multicultural than most of the rest of the country—turn out to be very much a typical, and to a degree racialised, Western tradition. The quest to become conventionally beautiful in a Western sense takes up a significant part of Irie's life, as she is desperately preoccupied with fitting in. A description of visiting a hair salon with predominantly Black customers offers particularly good insight into how beauty standards function to emphasize the racialised Other. The hair-braiding and beauty parlor identity issues

pertaining to race are, in both a metaphorical and literal sense, strongly reminiscent of Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's novel *Americanah* (2013), written thirteen years later—both novels exploring the desire to belong and assimilate in a white people's world:

Here, the impossible desire for straightness and “movement” fought daily with the stubborn determination of the curved African follicle; here ammonia, hot combs, clips, pins, and simple fire had all been enlisted in the war and were doing their damndest to beat each curly hair into submission.

“Is it straight?” was the only question you heard as the towels came off and the heads emerged from the dryer pulsating with pain. “Is it straight, Denise? Tell me is it straight, Jackie?”

(Smith)

Teeth appear again and again throughout the novel: molars, canines, wisdom teeth, missing teeth, the roots of teeth. In this book, they seem to symbolically represent a fundamental human sameness that goes beyond cultural, historical, racial, and personal differences. Teeth become a defining characteristic of each individual person, ranging from white to non-white, from healthy to unhealthy, from aesthetically pleasing to those seen as ugly. Michael Meyer points this out precisely by stating, “the relevance of genetic inheritance and cultural heritage is also captured in the leitmotif of white teeth and root canals. These dental metaphors suggest the relevance of biology and history” (Meyer 2017: 484).

While visiting the local school, a minor character named Mr. Hamilton describes his experiences of the Congolese war. He terrifies the children with his stories about the war in Africa, explaining that he could identify a Congolese soldier “by the whiteness of his teeth.” His description is not very different from those in Joseph Conrad's *Heart of Darkness* and blatantly reveals Mr. Hamilton's colonialist attitude. His racism exposes his prejudice, for the teeth of the Congolese people seem whiter to him only because he is so focused on the darkness of their skin. In other words, teeth in the novel serve as a kind of root metaphor:

But like all things, the business has two sides. Clean white teeth are not always wise, now are they? Par exemplum: when I was in the Congo, the only way I could identify the nigger [sic] was by the whiteness of his teeth, if you see what I mean. Horrid business. Dark as buggery, it was. And they died because of it, you see? Poor bastards. Or rather I survived, to look at it in another way, do you see?

(Smith)

Zadie Smith's novel *White Teeth* addresses multiculturalism, ethnicity, gender, and identity in contemporary England. Issues of multiculturalism are especially pertinent in (North) London, where communities tend to be more ethnically and culturally diverse. Teeth in the book, therefore, symbolize the power and persistence of identity. Teeth have roots, just as identity is rooted in the past and in one's traditional culture. The root canals of individual characters in the novel symbolize their origins and the histories of both individuals and their larger communities. *White Teeth* tackles, intersectionally, many issues: immigration, assimilation, colonialism, multiculturalism, racism, patriarchy, sexism, feminism, domestic violence, genetic engineering, British colonial history, the purpose of existence, and other serious topics. However, the book, in all its complexity, also contains a great deal of humour—an achievement in itself.

O what a tangled web we weave. Millat was right: these parents were damaged people, missing hands, missing teeth. These parents were full of information you wanted to know but were too scared to hear. But [Irie] didn't want it anymore, she was tired of it. She was sick of never getting the whole truth.

(Smith)

“What is past is prologue.” This well-known Shakespearean reference, used as the book's motto, emerges in a discussion about how significantly history shapes the choices we make in the present moment. In *White Teeth*, the past—whether colonial heritage or personal traumas—greatly influences the protagonists' lives. The quote emphasizes how history is never far away; its influence persists in shaping our identities and decisions in ways we often could not have anticipated.

The novel's concluding chapters present an array of outcomes, showing where individual characters end up in their lives. One thing remains clear: the fates of the different families and the identities of the characters in the novel are impossible to fully disentangle or understand in isolation. *White Teeth*, this “family saga of immigrants” (Meyer 2017: 482), offers valuable insight into how personal lives are closely linked to larger historical and cultural traditions. Nick Bentley argues that it is this “nexus of family relationships [that] offers a microscopic image of multicultural Britain at the end of the millennium” (Bentley 2008: 53).

4 Conclusion

Both novels discussed are essentially centred on the theme of fitting in—*McTeague* through the lens of class, and *White Teeth* through gender and race, respectively. Through their intersectional interconnectedness, the social categories of race, gender, and class (less so sexuality and ability) are addressed. The complexity of various forms of discrimination intersects in the lived experiences of socially marginalized individuals and ethnic groups. The body as text, and the overarching intersectional metaphor of the tooth or teeth, allow us to perceive both social interconnectedness and forms of social disenfranchisement.

McTeague desperately wants to climb the social class ladder and become a member of the middle class—by foul means, however. His insatiable greed and heredity eventually strip him of everything; the brutish animal within the person triumphs, as Frank Norris would have us believe in the best naturalist manner. For Clara and Irie, the two female non-white protagonists of *White Teeth*, the eponymous white teeth represent an important aspect of their identities—both in how they see themselves in the mirror and how their faces are perceived by the outside world. Zadie Smith's image of white teeth in the novel clearly carries racial connotations.

The two novels elucidate the body-as-text metaphor, with teeth stereotypically representing various social concepts—power, greed, beauty, and ethnicity. Social belonging and acceptance are the focal points, as both novels share a strong social and sociological dimension. They critique contemporary social realities: the early emergence of capitalism in the United States, and the challenges of impeded multiculturalism in the United Kingdom, respectively.

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BOOK REVIEW

Food Television and Otherness in the Age of Globalization

Casey Ryan Kelly. Lanham: Lexington Books, 2017, 153p.

This book, published by Casey Ryan Kelly, comprises five chapters that examine the impact of food television on culture. Food television is no longer considered a source of food production and consumption, but a starting point for space, place, and identity. The author of the book attempts to provide a finite answer to the question of how media culture invites American audiences to think about the relationship between food, geography, travel, and cultural difference. The author exemplifies the local versus exotic foods based on *Bizarre Foods*, *Bizarre Foods America*, *No Reservations*, and “traditional” American comfort food in the light of *The Pioneer Woman and Diners, Drive-Ins and Dives*, *Man v. Food*. In addition, taste is regarded as a feasible expression of judgment, preference, and hierarchy cultivated concerning historically and culturally specific food practices in American food culture and non-Western nations. The role of the “normal” food-place-identity is opposed to the role of the other. Three key propositions are regarded from the perspective of how food TV mediates an ongoing confrontation between cosmopolitan ideas and the dominance of Western power; how nostalgia and mythology of American exceptionalism give meaning to the food-place-identities; how entertaining formats use techniques of documentary and filmmaking to internalize the anthropological voice of food television.

Regarding the organization of the publication, the book contains a traditional introduction, several chapters, and a conclusion at the end. The chapters are based on programs that delve into exotic and multicultural cuisines and programs that feature American comfort food and mass consumer traditions.

In chapter 1, “The Neocolonial Plate,” the show “Bizarre Foods with Andrew Zimmern” around Asia, Africa, and South America is analyzed. The show is a one-hour travel documentary with a former chef and food critic travelling and sampling the exotic and bizarre foods to reinforce the ideas of the superior white position regarding other cultures. The portrayals of cultural differences are entertaining and pleasurable for a simplified audience’s consumption. Not only are the portrayals simplified, but they are also distorted from the complex realities of the communities being featured. By presenting “the Orient” as mysterious and primitive, colonial histories are often neglected. The program generally allows viewers to “experience” distant cultures indirectly while ignoring global inequalities supporting Western globalization.

The author examines “*Bizarre Foods America*,” a spin-off program, in chapter 2, “Eroticizing Poverty.” Exotic foods are not typically exemplified in foreign countries, but rather in the USA, particularly in impoverished regions such as the rural South and Appalachia. The show portrays the food traditions formed by hardship and necessity, compared to the great exuberance of food for those looking for novelty. The author makes use of the term “culinary slumming,” explaining that it allows wealthier audiences to indulge in food practices of those who were born in conditions of inequality. Unreflexive enjoyment of American poverty cuisines marks the survival struggles of those who created them.

Ree Drummond’s “*The Pioneer Woman*” (Food Network), a cooking program set on a working-class ranch, is under analysis in chapter 3, “From the Plantation to the Prairie.” The show reimagines southern plantation iconography and ties it to the American tradition of slavery and colonial expansion. Food-place-identities are the key aspect of attention in this

chapter. The author showcases how the program was able to tie the mythic folklore of America's origin story with the wholesome, nostalgic vision of hard work and simple living, meanwhile criticizing this portrayal, stating that this appeal to frontier mythology obscures the violence and oppression that underpin American identity.

In chapter 4, "America, the Abundant," Guy Fieri's "*Diners, Dive-Ins and Dives*" (Food Network) and Adam Richman's "*Man v. Food*" (Travel Channel) are discussed as sources of excessive eating as a symbol of American prosperity. The author mentions that America is considered a land of abundance where overconsumption is a sign of upward mobility and the spoils of a mass consumer economy. They also position indulgence as a rebellious stand against authority, supporting the myth of prosperity of an upwardly mobile middle class. These shows highlight the American Dream of liberty, wealth, and demographic values on the grounds of overconsumption.

Chapter 5, "Going Native," explores the high-powers and downsides of culinary travel shows that prioritize curiosity over simple entertainment, concentrating on Anthony Bourdain's "*No Reservations*" (Travel Channel). The show offers detailed portrayals of food within its political, economic, and cultural settings. The key idea of the show is "going native" or living like locals, as it gives a more authentic experience. This concept relies on the simplistic, binary view of culture and marks the ways tourism often exploits and commodifies multicultural experiences. Yet, the show critiques the global tourist industry, providing a long-form argument against closed-minded ethnocentric forms of food tourism. While travel often struggles to break free from colonialist ideas of "self" and "Other," the show suggests it can transform cosmopolitanism as it is currently conceived by inviting audiences to reconsider their own assumptions and biases.

In the conclusion of the book, the author considers how food television relates to global structures of inequality and explores how it might help reimagine food-place identities. Even though the author criticizes food television's speculations of foreign Others, she ultimately argues that food's universal nature offers opportunities to bridge cultural divides and structural inequalities that are the main aspects of life under late capitalism.

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